

Thermochemical Conversion of Lignocellulosic Biomass to
Generate Hydrogen Rich Synthesis Gas for Hydrogen
Production: An Experimental and Thermodynamic Study
Using Oxy-Steam as The Gasification Agent

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*I dedicate this thesis to my parents
Shrimati Nirmala and Shri Sanjeev Gupta,
And
to my grandmother Shrimati Makhaniya!*

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Declaration

This is to certify that the work reported in this thesis is original and has been carried out by Arvind Gupta for his Ph.D. thesis work under the supervision of Prof. S. Dasappa at the Centre for Sustainable Technologies, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India. This thesis has not formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, or similar title of any university or institution.

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Contents

Contents.....	i
List of figures.....	i
List of tables.....	i
Abstract	3
Chapter 1 – Introduction.....	9
1.1 Energy scenario.....	9
1.2 Introduction to hydrogen energy	10
1.2.1 Methods of generating hydrogen.....	12
1.2.1.1 Steam reforming	13
1.2.1.2 Partial Oxidation.....	14
1.2.1.3 Autothermal reforming	15
1.2.1.4 Plasma reforming.....	15
1.2.1.5 Aqueous Phase reforming	16
1.2.1.6 Ammonia reforming.....	16
1.2.1.7 Biomass gasification for hydrogen production	17
1.2.1.8 Biomass pyrolysis	18
1.2.1.9 Water electrolysis	19
1.2.1.10 Photobiological production of hydrogen	20
1.2.1.11 Photoelectrolysis	20
1.2.1.12 Thermochemical water splitting.....	20
1.3 Biomass gasification	22
1.3.1 Oxy-steam gasification	26
1.3.2 Type of gasification systems.....	27
Chapter 2 – Literature review.....	30
2.1 Literature studies.....	30
2.2 Experiments & simulation studies.....	33
2.3 Experiments only studies	35
2.4 Simulation only studies	41
2.5 Techno-economic analysis	44
2.6 Gaps identified and the objective of present study	45
2.7 Objectives of the present study	46
Chapter 3 – Material and methods	50
3.1 Experimental setup – Oxy-steam gasification.....	50
3.1.1 The reactor	50
3.1.2 Cooling and cleaning system.....	54
3.1.3 Residual moisture removal	55
3.1.4 Induced draft in the gasification system	55
3.1.5 Filtration.....	55
3.1.6 Steam generation.....	56
3.1.6 Oxygen supply	56
3.2 Biomass – characterization and properties	57
3.3 Instrumentation	60
3.3.1 Gas flow measurement	60

3.3.2 Temperature measurement	60
3.3.3 Gas composition measurement	61
3.4 Methodology – Gasification study	62
3.5 Elemental mass balance	64
3.6 Efficiency calculation	64
3.6.1 Energy efficiency	65
3.6.2 Exergy efficiency	65
3.7 Experimental set-up – Char bed study	67
3.7.1 The reactor	67
3.7.2 The reactants	68
3.7.3 The product gas	68
3.7.4 Gas composition analysis.....	68
3.8 Methodology – Char bed study	69
3.9 Error analysis.....	71
3.9.1 Error estimation	72
3.9.2 Uncertainty analysis.....	72
3.9.3 Error Propagation	73
Chapter 4 - Oxy-steam gasification experiments with lower injection temperature (< 550 °C)	75
4.1 Dry gas composition.....	75
4.1.1 Hydrogen.....	76
4.1.2 Carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide.....	77
4.1.3 Methane	79
4.2 Hydrogen yield.....	80
4.3 Gas yield.....	81
4.4 Gasification efficiency.....	82
4.4 Hydrogen efficiency	84
4.5 H ₂ O conversion	85
4.5 Equivalence ratio	87
Chapter 5 – Effect of char bed towards water gas shift and char reactions to study in-situ reforming of CO in a gasification system.....	90
5.1 CO-H ₂ O feed on activated char bed	93
5.1.1 Effect of temperature	93
5.1.2 Catalytic activity of biomass char	100
5.1.3 Arrhenius parameters of the char samples – water gas shift reaction	104
5.1.4 CO-H ₂ O feed on the activated char bed at varying R and fixed temperature	108
5.2 Equilibrium studies for CO-H ₂ O feed at various R at 750±10 °C – with and without char bed.....	113
5.3 CO-H ₂ O-CO ₂ mixture on the char bed.....	116
5.3.1 Dry gas composition.....	117
5.3.2 Consumption and generation rates	118
5.4 H ₂ O - producer gas feed on char bed.....	120
5.4.1 Dry gas composition.....	121

5.4.2 Consumption and generation rates	122
5.5 CO-H ₂ O mixture on inert bed	125
5.6 CO-H ₂ O feed on demineralized (DM) water washed char bed	128
Chapter 6 – Oxy-steam gasification experiments with higher injection temperature (> 550 °C)	134
6.1 Dry gas composition.....	134
6.1.1 Hydrogen.....	135
6.1.2 Carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide.....	136
6.1.3 Methane	138
6.1.4 Composition vs. injection temperature	139
6.2 Hydrogen yield.....	141
6.3 Gas yield.....	143
6.4 Gasification efficiency.....	145
6.5 Hydrogen efficiency	148
6.6 H ₂ O conversion	149
6.7 Equivalence ratio	151
6.8 Gasifier bed temperature.....	152
Chapter 7 - Equilibrium studies and exergy analysis of gasification process on oxy-steam mode.....	154
7.1 Equilibrium studies	154
7.1.1 Equilibrium calculation by Gibbs free energy minimization.....	154
7.1.2 Gas composition	156
7.1.2.1 Hydrogen.....	156
7.1.2.2 CO and CO ₂	157
7.1.2.3 Hydrogen yield	159
7.2 Exergy analysis	160
7.2.1 Thermochemical conversion.....	161
7.2.2 Steam generation for oxy-steam mixture	162
7.2.3 Cleaning and cooling of hot gas.....	163
7.2.4 Exergy efficiency of the synthesis gas generation	164
Chapter 8 – Conclusion and future work	168
8.1 Conclusion	168
8.2 Contribution from the current work.....	169
8.3 Future work	170
References.....	172

List of figures

Figure 1-1 Global fossil fuel consumption (Our World in Data, 2024).....	10
Figure 1-2 Hydrogen production technologies	13
Figure 1-3 Conventional hydrocarbon reforming process (Navarro, Guil, & Fiero, 2015)	14
Figure 1-4. Operating conditions of SMR, POX and ATR processes (Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013)	15
Figure 1-5 Hydrogen from biomass gasification.....	18
Figure 1-6 Water electrolysis for hydrogen production (US Department of Energy, 2024)	19
Figure 1-7 Van Krevelen diagram for solid fuels (Trif-Tordai & Ionel, 2011)	23
Figure 1-8 Typer of gasifiers – (a) Downdraft gasifier, (b) Updraft gasifier, (c) Bubbling fluidized bed gasifier and (d) Entrained flow gasifier	27
Figure 3-1. The oxy-steam gasification system.....	51
Figure 3-2. Schematic of the oxy-steam gasification system	52
Figure 3-3 Steam generation system - boiler and superheater	56
Figure 3-4 Oxygen supply from LOX cylinder	57
Figure 3-5 Biomass used in the study (a) casuarina wood chips, (b) coconut shells and (c) corncob	58
Figure 3-6 Data Acquisition System.....	61
Figure 3-7 Gas Chromatography System	62
Figure 3-8 Experimental setup for char bed study	67
Figure 3-9 Gas analyser	70
Figure 4-1 Dry gas composition – casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C).....	76
Figure 4-2 Hydrogen in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C).....	77
Figure 4-3 Carbon monoxide in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperature (<550 °C)	78
Figure 4-4 Carbon dioxide in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)	79
Figure 4-5 Methane in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C).....	80
Figure 4-6 Hydrogen yield for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C).....	81
Figure 4-7 Gas yield for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)	82
Figure 4-8 Cold/dry gas efficiency for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)	83
Figure 4-9 Contribution of biomass and steam in input energy for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C).....	84

Figure 4-10 Hydrogen efficiency for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)	85
Figure 4-11 H_2O conversion for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).....	86
Figure 4-12 H_2 in the system by H_2O conversion for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)	87
Figure 4-13 ER for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).....	88
Figure 5-1 Temperature dependence of the Gibbs free energy (ΔrG) and equilibrium constant ($KWGS$)of the water-gas shift reaction. (S, 2021).....	91
Figure 5-2 $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$ (R) in an oxy-steam gasification system.....	92
Figure 5-3 Dry gas composition of product gas with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on coconut shell based activated charcoal bed (CC1).....	94
Figure 5-4 Dry gas composition of product gas with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on wood based activated charcoal bed (WC)	94
Figure 5-5 Rate of hydrogen generation with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on coconut shell based activated charcoal bed (CC1) at $R = 2$	98
Figure 5-6 Rate of hydrogen generation with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on wood based activated charcoal bed (WC) at $R = 2$	98
Figure 5-7 CO conversion for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on coconut shell and wood based activated charcoal.....	100
Figure 5-8 Dry gas composition of the product gas with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on an inert bed.....	102
Figure 5-9 Rate vs. partial pressure product for CC1.....	105
Figure 5-10 Rate vs. partial pressure product for WC.....	105
Figure 5-11 Arrhenius plot for WGSR for CC1.....	106
Figure 5-12 Arrhenius plot for WGSR for WC.....	106
Figure 5-13 Dry gas composition of the product mixture at various R for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on a char bed at $750\pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	109
Figure 5-14 Char consumption rate for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on char bed at $750\pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	110
Figure 5-15 Hydrogen contribution from WGS and $\text{C-H}_2\text{O}$ reaction with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on char bed at $750\pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	111
Figure 5-16 CO conversion – overall and by WGS.....	113
Figure 5-17 Dry gas composition at equilibrium for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on char bed at $750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at various R.....	113
Figure 5-18 Dry gas composition at equilibrium for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $750\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at various R (without the char bed)	115
Figure 5-19 Equilibrium composition of C-CO_2 system	116
Figure 5-20 Dry gas composition for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O-CO}_2$ on char bed feed at $R = 10$	117
Figure 5-21 Equilibrium composition of the dry gas with $\text{CO-CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on char bed at $R = 10$	118
Figure 5-22 Rate of hydrogen generation from water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction for $\text{CO-CO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on char bed at $R = 10$	120

Figure 5-23 Composition of the producer gas used as the feed with steam.....	121
Figure 5-24 Dry gas composition of the product mixture with PG-H ₂ O as the feed on char bed.....	122
Figure 5-25 Hydrogen contribution from WGS and steam char reaction.....	123
Figure 5-26 Char consumption rate with R for PG-H ₂ O feed at 730±10 °C.....	124
Figure 5-27 CO conversion for H ₂ O-PG mixture feed on char bed.....	125
Figure 5-28 Dry gas composition on inert bed with CO-H ₂ O feed at R10.....	126
Figure 5-29 CO conversion when CO-H ₂ O feed at R10 is passed through an inert bed.....	127
Figure 5-30 Composition of the dry product gas mixture for CO-H ₂ O feed over DM water washed char bed.....	128
Figure 5-31 Rate of hydrogen generation from water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction for CO-H ₂ O mixture on DM washed char bed.....	129
Figure 5-32 Dry gas composition comparison at R = 2 for CO-H ₂ O feed on different bed materials.....	130
Figure 5-33 Dry gas composition comparison at R = 10 for CO-H ₂ O feed on different bed materials.....	130
Figure 5-34 Comparison of rates of WGS and steam-char reactions at R = 2 and R10 for different bed materials.....	131
Figure 6-1 Dry gas composition for casuarina wood chips, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperature (transparent datapoints correspond to low injection temperature experiments).....	135
Figure 6-2 Hydrogen in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	136
Figure 6-3 Carbon monoxide in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	137
Figure 6-4 Carbon dioxide in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	138
Figure 6-5 Methane in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	139
Figure 6-6 Effect of injection temperature on composition at SBR 2.4.....	140
Figure 6-7 Effect of injection temperature on gas composition at SBR 1.4, 2.3, 3.1 and 3.6.....	141
Figure 6-8 Hydrogen yield for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	142
Figure 6-9 Hydrogen yield vs injection temperature at SBR 1.4, 2.3, 3.1 and 3.6.....	143
Figure 6-10 Syngas yield for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	144
Figure 6-11 Gas yield vs SBR at all injection temperatures.....	144
Figure 6-12 Gas yield vs injection temperature at SBR 2.4.....	145
Figure 6-13 Cold/dry gas efficiency for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	145

Figure 6-14 ER vs CO ₂ in dry product gas	146
Figure 6-15 Efficiency vs injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture	147
Figure 6-16 Contribution of biomass and steam in input energy efficiency for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)	148
Figure 6-17 Hydrogen efficiency higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	149
Figure 6-18 H ₂ O conversion at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	149
Figure 6-19 H ₂ in the system by H ₂ O conversion for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)	150
Figure 6-20 ER for for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C).....	151
Figure 6-21 Bed temperature profile – SBR 2.2, ER 0.31 and injection temperature 400 C	152
Figure 7-1 Average bed temperature and ER variation across the SBR	156
Figure 7-2 Equilibrium and experimental composition of hydrogen in dry syngas	157
Figure 7-3 Equilibrium and observed CO composition in dry syngas	158
Figure 7-4 Equilibrium and observed CO ₂ composition in dry syngas.....	158
Figure 7-5 Hydrogen yield comparison between experimental and equilibrium	159
Figure 7-6 Exergy loss in thermochemical conversion.....	161
Figure 7-7 Exergy loss in steam generation	163
Figure 7-8 Exergy loss in cooling and cleaning process.....	164
Figure 7-9 Overall exergy efficiency	165
Figure 7-10 Exergy flow - Input to output. (a) average of low injection temperature operations (b) average of high injection temperature operations.	166

List of tables

Table 1.1 Properties of hydrogen and comparison with other fuels (International Energy Agency, 2020)	11
Table 1.2 CO ₂ emission per kg of H ₂ generation (International Energy Agency, 2020)	15
Table 1.3 Hydrogen production technologies summary (Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013)	21
Table 1.4 Important reactions in a gasification system	25
Table 2.1 Summary of the literature review	48
Table 3.1 Properties of biomass	59
Table 3.2 Calibration composition levels of the GC	61
Table 3.3 Error from instruments	72
Table 5.1 Properties of char samples used as bed material.....	92
Table 5.2 Production and consumption rates of species – CO-H ₂ O feed at R = 2 on char bed.....	96
Table 5.3 CO conversion and rates for CO-H ₂ O feed at R = 2 at 720 °C.....	101
Table 5.4. SEM-EDS results of the ash of char samples	103
Table 5.5 Slope and intercept for Arrhenius parameters	107
Table 5.6 Arrhenius parameters for the char beds used	107
Table 5.7 Consumption and generation rate for CO-H ₂ O feed at 750±10 °C	110
Table 5.8. CO conversion by WGS reaction.....	112
Table 5.9 Rates of generation/consumption of the species with CO-H ₂ O-CO ₂ feed on char bed at R = 10	119
Table 5.10 Consumption and generation rate for PG-H ₂ O feed at 730±10 °C	122
Table 5.11 Generation and consumption rates for the CO-H ₂ O feed at R10 on an inert bed	126
Table 5.12 WGS rate and CO conversion for CO-H ₂ O feed at R10 over char and inert bed	127
Table 5.13 Rates of consumption and generation of species for CO-H ₂ O feed at R10 over DM washed char bed	129
Table 5.14. EDS results of washed and unwashed char ash.....	132

Nomenclature and symbols

SBR	Steam to biomass ratio (mole basis)
WGSR	Water gas shift reaction
ER	Equivalence ratio
LHV	Lower heating value (MJ/kg)
LNG	Liquified natural gas
HTWGS	High temperature water gas shift
LTWGS	Low temperature water gas shift
POX	Partial oxidation
ATR	Autothermal reforming
SMR	Steam methane reforming
APR	Aqueous phase reforming
NTP	Normal temperature and pressure, 20 °C and 1 atm
STP	Standard temperature and pressure, 0 °C and 1 atm
PSA	Pressure swing adsorption
CFD	Computational fluid dynamics
CBP	Carbon boundary point
GC	Gas chromatography
MS	Mass spectroscopy
LOX	Liquid oxygen
Q_{actual}	Actual volumetric flowrate
C_d	Coefficient of discharge
A_1, A_2	Area of inlet and area of throat
g	Acceleration due to gravity, 9.8 m/s ²
h	Manometric head in U-tube manometer
TCD	Thermal conductivity detector
LHS	Left hand side
RHS	Right hand side
η	Efficiency
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate
$h_{cryo-sep}$	Energy required to produce oxygen by cryogenic separation
E_{Aux}	Auxiliary energy consumption in operating the gasification system
e_{ph_gas}, e_{ch_gas}	Physical exergy, chemical exergy
$e_{ch_biomass}$	Chemical exergy of biomass
e_{H_2O}	Exergy associated with superheated steam
e_{O_2}	Exergy input in cryogenic separation process to generate liquid oxygen
ψ	Exergy efficiency
h_0	Standard enthalpy
T_0	Standard temperature
S_0	Standard entropy
X_i	Mole fraction of component i
Ex_0	Standard exergy
R	Gas constant

z	Mass fraction in biomass
β	Ratio of the chemical exergy to the LHV of the organic fraction of the biomass
PID	Proportional integral derivative
NDIR	Non-destructive infra-red
σ	Standard deviation
x	Measured value
\bar{x}	Average of measured value
$\Delta_r G$	Gibbs free energy of reaction
K	Equilibrium constant
CC	Coconut shell based char
WC	Wood based activated charcoal
EDS	Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
k	Rate constant
p_i	Partial pressure of component i
E_a	Activation energy, J/mol or kJ/mol
A	Pre-exponential factor
PG	Producer gas
DM	Demineralized
IB	Inert bed
AC	Activated charcoal
cas	Casuarina wood chips
coco	Coconut shells
corn	Corn cob
CEA	Chemical Equilibrium and Applications
tp	Assigned temperature and pressure
Exp.	Experimental

Abstract

Hydrogen can help decarbonize and bring a paradigm shift in the global energy mix. Green hydrogen, with its potential to mitigate carbon emission, offers an inexhaustible supply – free from the constraint of finite reserves. The aim of the present work is to generate hydrogen rich gas from biomass for green hydrogen and chemicals. This thesis presents an experimental investigation of the oxy-steam gasification of biomass in order to study the non-catalytic in-situ reforming of CO for the enrichment of hydrogen in product synthesis gas. The in-situ reforming of CO has been aimed by utilizing the steam in the oxidizing media to favor the water gas shift reaction. The work also presents the effect of steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) and the injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture in the product syngas yield and hydrogen enrichment.

The current state of literature discusses several studies on a bench scale or gasification with external energy support or studies with lower SBR operations or recommended external catalytic reactors to enhance hydrogen concentration (Hamad, Radwan, Heggo, & Moustafa, 2016; Khan, Yusup, Kamble, Naqvi, & Watson, 2018; Peng, et al., 2017; Ozbas, Aksu, Ongen, Aydin, & Ozcan, 2019; Li, et al., 2020; Yao, et al., 2016; Fremaux, Beheshti, Ghassemi, & Shahsavan-Markadeh, 2015). A study with external energy support for gasification has reported a maximum yield of 92 g/kg of biomass by using Ni catalyst (Yao, et al., 2016) while another autothermal oxy-steam gasification study has reported a maximum hydrogen yield of 104 g/kg (Kumar, 2016).

The literature review has highlighted several critical research needs in the field of biomass gasification for hydrogen production. There is a pressing demand for studies on autothermal gasification systems, which could reduce reliance on external energy sources. In-situ reforming, particularly those utilizing the water gas shift reaction, require further investigation to enhance hydrogen concentration in the product gas. Research into higher Steam-to-Biomass Ratio (SBR) operations is necessary to optimize the gasification process. The catalytic effects of hot char beds derived from biomass on the water gas shift reaction need to be explored, potentially eliminating the need for external catalytic

reformers. Studies should address multi-fuel compatibility in gasification reactors to accommodate diverse feedstocks. The impact of gasifying media temperature on the process requires thorough examination. Importantly, there is a significant need for large-scale experimental investigations, as most current studies are limited to bench-scale setups. To advance biomass gasification as a viable method for green hydrogen production, this study aims to address these research needs using a scaled-up setup capable of processing approximately 14 kg/h of biomass.

The present work aims to address the needs identified in the literature, and has been carried out in three parts: (1) study of the oxy-steam gasification at lower injection temperature ($T = 375 - 550$ °C), (2) study of the reduction zone of the gasification system by simulating the environment in a separate experimental set-up of char bed, and (3) study of oxy-steam gasification at higher injection temperature ($T = 550 - 750$ °C).

In the present study, three kinds of biomass were used as the solid fuel for the gasification experiments namely, casuarina wood chips, coconut shells and corncob with higher heating values 18.3, 20.5 and 17.5 MJ/kg, respectively. The biomass feeding took place in batch mode with an average feed rate of about 5 to 15 kg/h. The steam and oxygen flow rate varied from about 9 to 25 kg/h and 3 to 5 kg/h, respectively.

The present study was conducted with a closed top downdraft gasification system with thermal rating of about 14 kW. The gasification system is a cylindrical reactor with 2 m in height and 200 mm diameter.

The first phase of the experimental study demonstrates the attainment of stable oxy-steam gasification operations surpassing the previously established carbon boundary point of SBR 1.5 through the introduction of oxy-steam mixtures at elevated temperatures. Results show that with an increase in SBR, hydrogen fraction increases with a corresponding decrease in CO, substantiating the occurrence of the water gas shift reaction (WGSR). However, beyond an SBR threshold of approximately 3, the progression of the water gas shift reaction does not manifest in the gas composition data.

The low-temperature injection experiments encompassed an SBR range of 1.3 to 4.7 and equivalence ratio (ER) from 0.25 to 0.5. The highest hydrogen concentration in the dry gas mixture was recorded for casuarina wood chips at 49.5% (83.4 g/kg biomass) at an SBR of 3.6 and ER of 0.34, yielding an overall efficiency of 50.6% and hydrogen efficiency of 35.7%. Similarly, the maximum hydrogen yield reached 96.6 g/kg (47.6%) of biomass at an SBR of 4.2 and ER of 0.36, with an overall efficiency of 55.9% and hydrogen efficiency of 37.8% with casuarina wood chips as feed. Overall efficiency considers the heating value of the cold syngas as the output while hydrogen efficiency considers the heating value of hydrogen in the cold syngas as the output. Notably, H₂O conversion peaked at the lowest SBR of 1.3, reaching 43%, before gradually declining with increasing SBR. Beyond an SBR of 2, H₂O conversion remained relatively stable, fluctuating between 11% and 20%, with an average of 15% considering both kinds of biomass.

The second part of the study investigates in-situ catalysis by the char bed in a gasification system. To investigate the impact of temperature and SBR on reactions occurring within the reduction zone, separate experiments were conducted in a scaled down char bed. The experimental setup was a ceramic cylindrical reactor with a diameter of 50 mm and height of 400 mm externally heated to maintain desired temperature. To account for SBR, H₂O/CO ratio was varied on the basis of prevailing H₂O/CO in a gasification system. Results show that rates of water gas shift and steam char reactions increased with an increase in temperature from 520 to 760 °C at H₂O/CO = 2 when reactant mixture contained H₂O and CO. These reactions contribute to the enrichment of the product gas mixture with hydrogen. Notably, the temperature range of 720–760°C was identified as crucial for char conversion by steam and increased hydrogen production. Further, the effect of H₂O/CO was studied by fixing the temperature at 750 °C. It was seen that char consumption increased (8.1 to 16.4 mmol/h-gchar) when H₂O/CO increased from 2 to 10 while rate of water gas shift reaction decreased. The decrease in water gas shift reaction rate can be attributed to CO addition from steam-char reaction which decreases the effective H₂O/CO in the system. Experiments with producer gas-H₂O mixture

as the reactant mixture at $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$ from 2 to 10 at temperature $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ showed that increase in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$ favors hydrogen enrichment by water gas shift reaction and steam-char reaction, however, the rates of reactions were lower than in case of $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{CO}$ mixture in the feed. At $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO} = 10$, with $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{CO}$ mixture, the water gas shift reaction was 2.3 times faster than with producer gas – H_2O mixture, for steam-char reaction, this factor was 2.4 at the same $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$. This decrease could be attributed to dilution effect of other components in the reactant mixture which contains CO_2 , H_2 , CO , CH_4 and N_2 . The inhibition effect due to the presence of H_2 to water gas shift reaction is also a reason for the decrease in reaction rates of water gas shift reaction and char reaction. The catalytic effect of the char bed was also found to be favoring the water gas shift reaction due to presence of inorganics and higher surface area, as validated by results from experiments with an inert bed under similar conditions. The presence of potassium in char has been shown to enhance the activity of char towards both the reactions.

On understanding the effect of $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$ and temperature over char bed separately conducted for reactant mixtures ($\text{CO}+\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and producer gas+ H_2O), oxy-steam gasification experiments were conducted at higher injection temperatures ($550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of oxy-steam mixture in the SBR range of 1.3 to 3.7. Elevating the injection temperature led to an improved hydrogen yield of 110 g/kg-biomass (53.4%) at an SBR of 2.4 and ER of 0.24 for casuarina wood chips, achieving an overall efficiency of 69.8% and hydrogen efficiency of 47.8% when the oxy-steam injection temperature reached $734\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Furthermore, increasing the injection temperature resulted in a product gas mixture containing higher hydrogen concentration of 56.6% (vol.) at $750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for casuarina wood chips while at a lower injection temperature of $445\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ it was 46.7% (vol.%) at an SBR of 3.1. Results show higher temperature of injection results in better yield at lower SBR. The study recommends operating the gasification system at SBR of 2.3 ± 0.1 with injection temperature more than $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Present work also establishes the multifuel capability of the gasification system where biomass like casuarina wood chips, coconut shells and corncob can be used to generate syngas.

Further, exergy analysis was done to identify the inefficiencies by quantifying the conversion efficiency at various subsystems of the gasification system. Exergy analysis reveals the maximum work obtainable by a process. This analysis takes into account thermodynamic irreversibilities, which result in energy degradation. In the context of the present study, solid biomass undergoes thermochemical conversion in a fixed bed downdraft reactor to produce synthesis gas. The gasification process occurs within the reactor, while subsequent cooling and cleaning stages remove sensible heat and moisture from the product gas mixture.

The exergy analysis of the process reveals that with an increase in injection temperature, the thermochemical conversion efficiency increased, with an average conversion efficiency of 77%, whereas steam generation for the process incurred the highest exergy loss. The conversion efficiency considered the exergy of biomass, steam and oxygen as the input and exergy of the hot gas mixture after gasification as the output. The equilibrium studies show that lower injection temperature favors higher H₂ yield as dictated by thermodynamics. While SBR improves hydrogen composition in the output, the rate of increase plateaus at higher SBRs (>2.5), explaining the observation recorded in the first part of the study.

Thesis outline

Chapter 1 – Introduction
Energy scenario, hydrogen generation methods, biomass gasification.

Chapter 2 – Literature review
State of the art, gaps identified, objectives of the thesis.

Chapter 3 – Materials and methods
Oxy-steam gasification system, feed characterization, instrumentation, char bed setup, methodology, Error analysis

Chapter 4 – Oxy-steam gasification experiments with lower injection temperature
Composition, yield, efficiency, H₂O conversion

Chapter 5 – In-situ reforming of CO in a gasification system -
*Effect of char bed towards water gas shift and char reactions
Effect of temperature, catalytic activity of char, effect of H₂O/CO ratio, dilution effect*

Chapter 6 – Oxy-steam gasification experiments with higher injection temperature
Composition, yield, efficiency, H₂O conversion comparison

Chapter 7 – Equilibrium studies and exergy analysis of oxy-steam gasification process
Gibbs energy minimization, composition and yield comparison with experiments, exergy analysis

Chapter 1 – Introduction

The whole world is going through an unprecedented time of growth and development and the main driver for development and growth is energy. With an increase in the population and advancements in technology the energy requirement is constantly going up. This is also aided by the lifestyle shift of most of the population which is adopting an urbanized way of living resulting in an increase in energy demand (Franco, Mandla, & Rao, 2017). The existing trend of energy generation and utilization heavily depends on fossil fuel-based sources. The data shows that in year 2022; oil, gas and coal accounted for 81.8% of primary energy share in the total energy mix (Energy Institute, 2023).

Fossil sources are carbon-based fuels which once utilized release CO₂ in the atmosphere. Carbon in anthracite is almost 100%, bituminous coals can have carbon more than 85%, oil can contain carbon between 82 to 84% and methane which dominates the natural gas composition constitutes of 75% carbon (Smil, 2017). Releasing the carbon into atmosphere as CO₂ has been proven to be detrimental for earth as it acts as a greenhouse gas and traps the long wave radiation reflected from the Earth's surface and raises the temperature of the planet. Exploitation of fossil fuels started with the industrial revolution in eighteenth century has been on increasing trend ever since which has caused present concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere at 419 parts per million and rising (Lindsey, 2024).

1.1 Energy scenario

Fossil fuels have been the prime source of energy since the beginning of 19th century and the trend took a drastic change in mid-twentieth century when annual consumption started to rise at enormous rate, as depicted in Figure 1-1.

Figure 1-1 Global fossil fuel consumption (Our World in Data, 2024)

According to the US Energy Information Administration International Energy Outlook 2019 world energy consumption will grow nearly by 50% between 2018 and 2050. And, as per the data, energy is the main contributor to climate change where it accounts for 73% of human-caused greenhouse gases (United Nations Development Programme, 2021). Rising energy demand and requirement of affordable and clean energy have made it compulsory to explore sustainable energy sources which do not cause climate change and can last endlessly (Goals 7 & 13 of Sustainable Development Goals). In this respect, hydrogen has been identified as the cleanest energy carrier which has water only as the product along with the energy as the output with no carbon footprint.

1.2 Introduction to hydrogen energy

Hydrogen has long been recognized as an energy carrier. It was the first fuel to be used in an internal combustion engine nearly 200 years ago. With the current energy scenario, as discussed in section 1.1, the interest of scientific community towards hydrogen energy future has reinvigorated and there is a constant effort to develop a renewable hydrogen production technology to make it an

important part of clean and secure energy future. Properties of hydrogen as the fuel is presented in Table 1.1.

Hydrogen is recognized as the future energy carrier which addresses environmental emission concerns and answers the questions around threat of limited supply, provided the source feed for hydrogen generation is not fossil fuels and the process utilizes only non-fossil-based energy. Currently, most of the hydrogen produced globally is fossil fuel based. Of all the hydrogen production globally, 96% supply comes from fossil fuels with about 48% from natural gas and 30% from oil and 18% from coal gasification (Li, et al., 2020; Dou, et al., 2019).

Table 1.1 Properties of hydrogen and comparison with other fuels (International Energy Agency, 2020)

Property	Hydrogen	Comparison
Density (gaseous)	0.089 kg/m ³ (0 °C, 1 bar)	1/10 of natural gas
Density (liquid)	70.79 kg/m ³ (-253 °C, 1 bar)	1/6 of natural gas
Boiling point	-252.76 °C (1 bar)	90 °C below LNG
Energy per unit of mass (LHV)	120.1 MJ/kg	3x that of gasoline
Energy density (ambient cond., LHV)	0.01 MJ/L	1/3 of natural gas
Specific energy (liquefied, LHV)	8.5 MJ/L	1/3 of LNG
Flame velocity	346 cm/s	8x methane
Ignition range	4–77% in air by volume	6x wider than methane
Autoignition temperature	585 °C	220 °C for gasoline
Ignition energy	0.02 MJ	1/10 of methane

There are two ways hydrogen can play a crucial role to bring about this paradigm shift in the energy mix of the present and the future.

1. The existing application of hydrogen can be substituted by using hydrogen produced using alternative methods which are cleaner.
2. Hydrogen use can be expanded to a wide range of new applications as an alternative to current fuels and inputs, or it can complement to the greater use of electricity in these applications. For example, in transport, heating, steel production and electricity hydrogen can be used in its pure form or converted to hydrogen-based fuels, including synthetic methane, synthetic liquid fuels, ammonia and methanol (International Energy Agency, 2020).

Since hydrogen is not available in molecular form, it is extracted from the various sources on earth. The existing practice is dominated by steam-methane reforming process which utilizes natural gas as feed to generate hydrogen rich synthesis gas.

All the processes have been discussed in detail in the next section.

1.2.1 Methods of generating hydrogen

Hydrogen is the most abundant element in the universe. On earth, most of the hydrogen exists in combined form with other elements and is available on earth as part of water, biomass, and fossils. A variety of methods exist to generate hydrogen from several primary feedstock. These feedstocks can be natural gas, oil, coal, water and biomass. In specialized cases, algae strains have also been used to derive hydrogen using direct sunlight. On the basis of feedstock supply, hydrogen production can be classified into two categories: renewable and non-renewable. Non-renewable technologies feed on fossil sources which include natural gas, oil and coal. Renewable technologies are based on non-fossilized source i.e. biomass, solar etc. Hydrogen production by water electrolysis can be renewable or non-renewable depending on the source of electricity for the electrolysis.

Hydrogen production from fossil fuel takes place by hydrocarbon reforming process while other feedstocks undergo non-reforming routes to generate hydrogen. A broad categorization of the production technologies can be done as presented in the Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-2 Hydrogen production technologies

1.2.1.1 Steam reforming

Steam reforming is an endothermic chemical process in which high temperature steam reacts with the hydrocarbon to produce hydrogen and carbon monoxide. Most used hydrocarbon is the natural gas which majorly is composed of methane (typically ~95% by volume). The process is popularly known as steam-methane reforming. The main operating variables influencing the natural gas steam reforming are temperature, steam-to-carbon (S/C) ratio and pressure. Steam-methane reforming of natural gas is a mature production process in which steam at 700 °C – 1000 °C reacts with methane at 3 – 25 bar pressure in a catalytic environment (US Department of Energy, 2023).. The S/C ratio in case of methane reforming is maintained at 4 for the lowest CO₂ emission due to the process. The reforming reaction takes place in a bed containing catalyst, mainly nickel-based (Navarro, Guil, & Fiero, 2015; Kalamaras & Efstathiou,

2013). The hydrogen enrichment of the product at the downstream of the steam reforming process is further done by water gas shift reaction. Figure 1-3 presents a flow diagram of a conventional steam reforming process. The thermal efficiency of the steam reforming process on an industrial scale is around 70-85% (Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013; Holladay, Hu, King, & Wang, 2009).

Figure 1-3 Conventional hydrocarbon reforming process (Navarro, Guil, & Fiero, 2015)

1.2.1.2 Partial Oxidation

Partial oxidation (POX) is carried out by partially combusting the hydrocarbon. The process is exothermic and does not require high temperatures. Non-catalytic partial oxidation of hydrocarbons in presence of oxygen typically occurs with flame temperatures of 1300-1500 °C to ensure complete conversion and to reduce soot formation. Catalysts are added to the system to lower the operating temperatures; usually in the range of 700-1000 °C (Holladay, Hu, King, & Wang, 2009; Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013). Catalysts used for natural gas is typically nickel or rhodium based. In comparison with the steam reforming process, more CO is produced with respect to H₂ on the product side. POX is therefore complemented by the water gas shift reaction to convert CO with H₂O to H₂ and CO₂.

1.2.1.3 Autothermal reforming

In autothermal reforming (ATR), steam is added in partial oxidation process assisted by a catalyst. The process involves a thermal zone where partial oxidation takes place and generates heat which supplies heat to the catalytic steam reforming reaction in the downstream. Oxidation process coupled in the process makes the process self-supported and there is no need of external heat source. ATR is a combination of steam reforming and partial oxidation processes. Figure 1-4 presents the relative operating conditions of the three kinds of reforming processes. ATR process has the advantage over steam reforming process that it can be stopped and started very rapidly.

Figure 1-4. Operating conditions of SMR, POX and ATR processes (Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013)

Table 1.2 CO₂ emission per kg of H₂ generation (International Energy Agency, 2020)

Source of hydrogen generation	CO ₂ emission (tCO ₂ /tH ₂)
Natural gas	10
Oil	12
Coal	19

1.2.1.4 Plasma reforming

Plasma reforming processes are same as that in the case of conventional reforming reactions except for the energy and free radicals required for the reactions which are provided by the plasma. Plasma is typically generated with

electricity or heat. When steam or water is injected with fuel, in presence of plasma, H^* , OH^* and O^* radicals and electrons are formed which facilitate reduction and oxidation reactions to take place.

1.2.1.5 Aqueous Phase reforming

Aqueous phase reforming (APR) process is a technology in development. In this process oxygenated hydrocarbons, that contain oxygenated functional groups, such as carbonyl (-CO-) and alcoholic (-OH) groups such as ethanol, methanol, biodiesel, glycerol (main by-product in biodiesel production by transesterification of vegetable oil, animal fats or waste cooking oil) and sugars etc. The process takes place at pressures up to 25 – 30 MPa and temperature ranging from 220 to 270 °C (Holladay, Hu, King, & Wang, 2009). APR is a catalytic process, mostly using Pt based catalyst. Prevailing conditions make the process to generate H_2 and CO_2 in a single reactor with low amounts of CO in contrast to steam reforming processes that require multiple reactors to achieve low levels of CO in the product gas. Equation 1.5 (equation 1.6 + 1.3) presents the overall stoichiometry for hydrogen production from glycerol.

1.2.1.6 Ammonia reforming

This is a process of breaking down ammonia into its constituent elements in presence of a heterogeneous catalyst. It involves cracking process at 800 – 900 °C and unlike ammonia synthesis process low pressures are preferred. Cracking is an endothermic process where reverse ammonia synthesis process takes place. The high temperature can be obtained by burning a part of hydrogen produced (Holladay, Hu, King, & Wang, 2009).

1.2.1.7 Biomass gasification for hydrogen production

Biomass gasification is a promising renewable technology for hydrogen production. In this process, biomass in controlled oxidizing environment is converted thermochemically into producer gas or synthesis gas. Gasification technology commonly used with biomass and coal is very mature and commercially used. The important subprocesses in gasification are pyrolysis, oxidation, and char gasification. Pyrolysis process releases volatiles from the biomass which causes a significant weight loss in biomass and char is generated. Further, in oxidation process, a part of the volatiles combusts to generate thermal energy in the system to support the gasification process. The char further takes part in gasification reaction in reduction zone where steam and CO₂ react with char and generate CO and H₂. In autothermal gasification process, the thermal requirement is met by burning a part of the volatiles in oxidation process. The process of gasification can also be achieved by employing an external source of energy for heat to drive the process, known as allothermal process. The product gas mixture contains H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and N₂. The product gas can be reformed in a separate WGS reactor to enrich the product gas with hydrogen, The H₂ enriched gas mixture when passed through a separation unit (e.g., pressure swing adsorption), generates pure hydrogen. In attempt to enrich the syngas with H₂, steam as the gasifying media is also used in the gasification process. Equation 1.8 presents the overall chemical equation for oxy-steam gasification where oxygen and steam mixture is used as the gasifying agent resulting in synthesis gas mixture.

Increasing the steam-to-biomass ratio in the feed has been shown to increase the hydrogen yield at the gasifier output (Kumar & Dasappa, 2013). The operating parameters, such as temperature, gasifying agent, and residence time play an essential role in the formation and decomposition of tar. There are various configurations for the gasification reactor, among which downdraft system have proven to generate syngas with the lowest amount of higher

hydrocarbons known as tars as it avails hot char bed for the tar to crack into permanent gases (Reed & Das, 1988; Kumar & Dasappa, 2013). A few researchers have also used some additives like dolomite and olivine in the gasifier to reduce the tar. Addition of dolomite has shown to eliminate 100% tar (Ni, Leung, Leung, & Sumathy, 2006).

Figure 1-5 Hydrogen from biomass gasification

1.2.1.8 Biomass pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is thermal decomposition of biomass in absence of any oxidizing media to convert biomass into liquid oils, solid charcoal, and gaseous compounds. Based on the heating rate of particle, temperature, and residence time, pyrolysis can further be classified into slow and fast pyrolysis. The yield of the pyrolysis process depends on the operating conditions. In slow pyrolysis, biomass is heated to about 773 K where vapor residence time varies from 5 min. to 30 min. and the product is mostly char with smaller amounts of oil and gas. The vapors do not escape rapidly, thus, components in vapor phase continue to take part in secondary reactions. Fast pyrolysis takes place at relatively higher temperatures and fast pyrolysis of biomass produces 60 – 75% of liquid bio-oil, 15 – 20% of char and 10 – 20% of non-condensable gases, depending on the feedstock used (Mohan, Jr, & Steele, 2006). Hydrogen from bio-oil can be produced by steam reforming of biooil (Stefan Czernik; Robert Evans; Richard French, 2007). Hydrogen rich gas produced from slow pyrolysis can also be used to obtain pure hydrogen (HongtaoJiang, Wu, Fan, & Ji, 2012). However, to maximize hydrogen yield in pyrolysis the process should employ high temperature and long residence time with the use of a catalyst as hydrogen

concentration in pyrolysis product is low to be commercially viable (Dou, et al., 2019).

1.2.1.9 Water electrolysis

Water electrolysis is a promising option for hydrogen production from renewable resources, however about 2-4% of hydrogen produced globally comes from water electrolysis (Rissman et al., 2020; Shiva Kumar & Lim, 2022). It is the process of splitting the water molecule into molecular hydrogen and oxygen.

Figure 1-6 Water electrolysis for hydrogen production (US Department of Energy, 2024)

The electricity acts as a source which supplies energy for the dissociation of water molecule and expand the generated gases. The electrolysis of water can be renewable provided the emission resulting from generating electricity is zero. However, the high capital cost and lower energy efficiency are the main challenges that have hampered the widespread adoption and utilization of this technology, freshwater access being another issue in water-stressed areas.

1.2.1.10 Photobiological production of hydrogen

Photobiological systems use microalgae i.e. green algae and cyanobacteria to carry out the conversion of water into hydrogen ions and oxygen ions in presence of sunlight. Further, hydrogen ions are combined directly or indirectly to generate pure hydrogen molecule (US Department of Energy, 2024). The process essentially converts solar energy into chemical energy as hydrogen. Presence of hydrogenase in microalgae makes them able to produce hydrogen. Since hydrogenase is sensitive to presence of oxygen, the yield is affected negatively when oxygen level is more than 0.1% (Ni, Leung, Leung, & Sumathy, 2006). This technology is limited by low hydrogen yield and safety issues with the simultaneous generation of oxygen as the mixture is combustible at a certain ratio.

1.2.1.11 Photoelectrolysis

In photoelectrolysis process, sunlight decomposes water into hydrogen and oxygen with the help of semiconductor materials. The semiconducting material absorbs solar energy and creates the necessary voltage for the water decomposition. The process utilizes a photoelectrochemical light collection system for driving the electrolysis.

1.2.1.12 Thermochemical water splitting

Thermochemical water splitting is the process of decomposing water to its constituents - hydrogen and oxygen using high temperature. The process is also known as thermolysis. The process with water alone takes place at about 2500 °C and the efficiency can go up to 50%. However, the material and heat source at these temperatures pose a limitation and therefore chemical reagents have been developed which lower the process temperatures. The operating temperatures have come down but require high pressures. There are more than 300 water splitting cycles available in the literature. A few of them are sulfur-iodine cycle, Ispra-Mark 10 and sulfuric acid decomposition.

Section 1.2.1 discussed various methods of hydrogen production from conventional sourced and non-conventional sources. To combat the energy crisis in a sustainable way which guarantees energy supply endlessly without harming

the atmosphere, biomass as a promising alternative has the potential. Biomass based hydrogen production technologies can prove to be a replacement to the existing natural gas-based technologies. Table 1.3 lists all the hydrogen production technologies and compares their efficiencies. Biomass gasification is a mature technology and its application for hydrogen production can yield efficiencies up to 50%. Present work explores biomass gasification technology for hydrogen production by utilizing steam and oxygen as the gasifying media. Next section of this chapter presents biomass gasification as the technology, different approaches to it, and oxy-steam gasification process for hydrogen enriched synthesis gas production.

Table 1.3 Hydrogen production technologies summary (Kalamaras & Efstathiou, 2013)

Technology	Feedstock	Efficiency	Maturity
Steam reforming	Hydrocarbons	70 – 85%	Commercial
Partial oxidation	Hydrocarbons	60 – 75%	Commercial
Autothermal reforming	Hydrocarbons	60 – 75%	Near term
Plasma reforming	Hydrocarbons	9 – 85%	Long term
Biomass gasification	Biomass	35 – 50%	Commercial
Aqueous phase reforming	Polyols, carbohydrates	35 – 55%	Medium term
Electrolysis	Water + electricity	50 – 70%	Commercial
Photolysis	Water + sunlight	0.5%	Long term
Thermochemical water splitting	Water + heat	NA	Long term

1.3 Biomass gasification

Biomass has been the source of energy for the humanity since ages and till mid 1800s it supplied the majority the worlds energy. Its usage started to phase out only in industrialized countries at the onset of fossil fuel era and it contributes to about 10% of total primary energy supply globally at present. However, with the oil crisis of 1970 the interest in biomass utilization as an alternate source has invigorated. The motivation for the development of biomass-based technologies is to reduce dependency on fossil fuels and ensure endless energy supply, and not to add harmful emissions to the ambient.

Biomass is an organic substance that occurs in multitudes of physical forms. Biomass as definition is any biological material derived from living, or recently living organisms. However, in the energy context, biomass means plant-based material. Plants utilize solar energy in the process called photosynthesis to produce oxygen and simple sugars, like glucose and sucrose. The plants then use these sugars to make more complex sugar starched for storage as energy reservoirs and to produce cellulose and hemicellulose (Mukunda H. S., 2011). Biomass is a C-H-O complex consisting of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin as the main constituents. These components are of energetic value and can be broken down into smaller gaseous fuel molecules in a controlled process like gasification. The atomic ratios H/C and O/C can be compared for the different solid fuels using Van Krevelen diagram as presented in *Figure 1-7*. which also gives an idea of their relative energetic values.

Figure 1-7 Van Krevelen diagram for solid fuels (Trif-Tordai & Ionel, 2011)

Biomass gasification is a thermochemical conversion process in which the biomass, a solid fuel, is converted to a gaseous mixture of fuel. The gas mixture contains hydrogen, carbon monoxide and methane (small fraction) as the combustible part with some amount of carbon dioxide. In case of air gasification, the mixture also contains nitrogen. The product gas mixture is known as synthesis gas (producer gas when nitrogen is also present). Process of biomass is accomplished through four subprocesses, namely – drying, pyrolysis, oxidation, and reduction. With respect to a packed bed downdraft gasification system, the process can be understood as below.

Drying: This physical process removes the moisture from biomass as the temperature of the biomass increases after the feeding into the reactor. The temperature levels can be up to 200 °C in the drying zone.

Pyrolysis: As the temperature of the biomass increases in the reactor pyrolysis process starts taking place. The pyrolysis process breaks down the dry biomass into volatiles and solid char.

Dry feedstock + heat \rightarrow volatiles + char

It is a chemical process where less strongly bonded C-H-O are released as volatiles as a consequence of degradation of biomass constituent cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin when subjected to temperatures at around 350 to 400 °C. Strongly bonded C-C is obtained as char as a product of pyrolysis. This process takes place in absence of oxidizing media, however, in case of open-top gasification system this process may be defined as an oxidative pyrolysis process as the prevailing environment is air in sub stoichiometry. Breakdown of hemicellulose takes place at around 220 – 315 °C, cellulose breaks down at 315 – 400 °C while lignin requires a wider temperature range to completely break down into volatiles (Mukunda H. S., 2011). About 80% of dry biomass gets devolatilized in temperatures below 500 °C (Reed & Das, 1988). The process of pyrolysis can be further classified as – primary, secondary, and tertiary. Primary pyrolysis takes place when direct devolatilization takes place as the biomass particles are in high temperature zone. Further, the devolatilization process makes the particle porous as the particles becomes char. The volatiles, the primary products take the path through the crevices in the porous char and react with the solid char. This part of the process is known as secondary pyrolysis. The primary pyrolysis product contains CO, CO₂, H₂O, and complex oxygenated higher hydrocarbon. Upon reaction with the char in secondary pyrolysis the product volatiles contain CO, CO₂, H₂O, H₂, CH₄ and more complex polymerized compounds. The product of secondary pyrolysis reacts with hot char which leads to tertiary compounds containing CO, H₂, CH₄, CO₂ and H₂O with some amount of more polymerized higher hydrocarbon (tars).

Oxidation: The volatiles from the pyrolysis product reach the high temperature zone where a part of the volatiles burns to release heat which sustains the entire process. The energy required to vaporize the moisture content in biomass during drying process is supplied from the oxidation zone via radiation. Also, pyrolysis is an endothermic process which is energetically supported by the exothermicity of the reactions taking place in oxidation zone.

Reduction: The hot char below the oxidation zone further conditions the incoming volatiles and products of combustion. The solid char also takes place in heterogeneous reactions with H_2O and CO_2 to produce H_2 and CO (R1 and R = 2). These reactions are reduction reactions of H_2O and CO_2 which are endothermic in nature. Energy for these reactions to take place is supplied from the oxidation reactions in oxidation zone. In this zone, higher hydrocarbons generated as a result of primary and secondary pyrolysis processes breakdown into simpler molecules CO , H_2 , CO_2 , CH_4 and H_2O due to prevailing high temperatures. Another important reaction taking place is water gas shift (WGS) (R9) reaction which takes place between CO and H_2O to generate CO_2 and H_2 . WGS is mildly exothermic and is thermodynamically favoured at low temperature and kinetically favoured at high temperatures. This reaction is widely used to enhance the hydrogen concentration. All the important chemical reactions that take place during gasification process have been listed in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4 Important reactions in a gasification system

Reaction type		Enthalpy of reaction, kJ/mol
<i>Carbon reactions</i>		
Boudouard (R1)	$C + CO_2 \leftrightarrow 2CO$	+172
Water gas (R2)	$C + H_2O \leftrightarrow CO + H_2$	+131
Hydrogasification (R3)	$C + 2H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_4$	-74.8
R4	$C + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow CO$	-111
<i>Oxidation reactions</i>		
R5	$C + O_2 \rightarrow CO_2$	-394
R6	$CO + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow CO_2$	-284
R7	$CH_4 + 2O_2 \leftrightarrow CO_2 + 2H_2O$	-803

R8	$H_2 + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow H_2O$	-242
<i>Shift reactions</i>		
R9	$CO + H_2O \leftrightarrow CO_2 + H_2$	-41.2
<i>Methanation reactions</i>		
R10	$2CO + 2H_2 \rightarrow CO_2 + CH_4$	-247
R11	$CO + 3H_2 \leftrightarrow CH_4 + H_2O$	-206
R12	$CO_2 + 4H_2 \rightarrow CH_4 + 2H_2O$	-165
<i>Steam reforming reactions</i>		
R13	$CH_4 + H_2O \leftrightarrow CO + 3H_2$	+206
R14	$CH_4 + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow CO + 2H_2$	-36

1.3.1 Oxy-steam gasification

In a gasification system, the heterogeneous (R2) and homogeneous (R9) reactions of H₂O generate hydrogen. Steam is added in the gasification system to obtain higher hydrogen concentration in the product gas mixture. In application where hydrogen generation is aimed through the biomass gasification process, oxy-steam mode of operation is preferred. In oxy-steam gasification process, oxy-steam mixture is used as the gasifying agent where oxygen is utilized to make the process the process autothermal and steam to enhance the hydrogen concentration. The steam reaction with solid char, water gas reaction (R2) is endothermic for which energy is supplied by utilizing externally sent oxygen. Another important hydrogen generating reaction, water gas shift reaction (R9) is mildly exothermic.

Oxy-steam mixture flow rate regulates the equivalence ratio and the steam-to-biomass ratio which are important control parameters in a gasification system employing oxygen and steam mixture as the gasifying agent instead of air.

Introducing oxy-steam mixture as the gasifying agent also brings in the endothermicity into the system. In order to ensure the process sustains, it is essential to maintain injection temperature of the mixture to avoid the

quenching of the bed. The bed temperature can also be regulated by changing the prevailing equivalence ratio (by changing the oxygen flow rate in the oxy-steam mixture), however, in this case, at the expense of some additional amount of combustible gases (CO, H₂ and CH₄ and volatiles) inside the system which eventually results in lower heating value gas at the output with lower concentrations of fuel gases. For an oxy-steam gasification operation, oxy-steam injection temperature also becomes a crucial parameter, in addition to equivalence ratio and steam-to-biomass ratio.

1.3.2 Type of gasification systems

Gasification can be achieved using different configuration of reactors: downdraft, updraft, entrained flow and fluidized bed.

Figure 1-8 Types of gasifiers – (a) Downdraft gasifier, (b) Updraft gasifier, (c) Bubbling fluidized bed gasifier and (d) Entrained flow gasifier

Downdraft: In the downdraft configuration, the solid fuel and the oxidizing media move from the top to bottom. The feeding takes place at the top and under steady condition of operation, different zones get established from top to bottom – drying, pyrolysis, oxidation and reduction. In this case, oxidizing media comes in contact with the pyrolyzing biomass before it contacts char and supports a flame, and limited oxidizer gets rapidly consumed. This flame in limited oxidizer supply is known as the flaming pyrolysis. Flaming pyrolysis produces most of the combustible gases produced in the gasification process and consumes 99% of the tars (Reed & Das, 1988).

Updraft: In updraft gasifiers the oxidizer enters the reactor from bottom and product gases exit the reactor from top. The biomass is fed from the top and travels top to bottom opposite to stream of hot gases. The biomass passes through the drying and pyrolysis zones as it travels downwards and reaches reduction zone. The oxidation zone lies at the bottom where char is burned to produce heat and CO₂. The burning of char supplies energy for carrying out reduction reactions, pyrolysis and drying. The gases generated in pyrolysis zone, in updraft configuration pass through the bed of biomass and do not get an opportunity to breakdown. Hence, the gasifier generates wide range of vapours containing tar

Fluidized bed: In a fluidized bed air rises through a grate at the bottom at high velocity to levitate the particles above the grate, fluidizing the bed. The fuel is fed from the side into the hot bed and mixed with an inert bed material such as sand. Thorough mixing inside the reactor maintains a constant temperature and drying, pyrolysis, oxidation, and reductions reactions take place simultaneously. These gasifiers operate at higher temperatures (800 – 900 °C) to attain higher carbon conversion (90-95%) (National Energy Technology Laboratory, 2021; Bermudez & Fidalgo, 2016). Limitation with a bubbling fluidizing bed is that it cannot achieve complete char conversion because of the back-mixing of solids, however, high degree of solid mixing helps a bubbling fluidized bed gasifier achieve temperature uniformity. Due to large thermal

inertia and vigorous mixing in the fluidized bed gasifiers, a wider range of fuels gasified (Basu, 2010).

Entrained flow: In these kinds of gasifiers a powdered fuel is entrained in the gasifying medium where the operation takes place at 20 – 70 bar pressure and typically 1400 °C. Powdered fuel of size <75 micron is injected into the reactor chamber along with the oxygen and steam (air rarely used). The gas velocity remains sufficiently high to fully entrain the fuel particles.

Summary

Chapter 1 provides an introduction to this thesis by setting the context of global energy scenario and bringing the relevance of hydrogen energy in energy mix. This chapter briefly describes all the hydrogen generating technologies with a comparison, and the discussion finally converges to biomass gasification process as a route. This chapter also introduces oxy-steam gasification as a process with its important control parameters and discusses the importance of steam-to-biomass ratio and oxy-steam injection temperature. This chapter helps in understanding the importance of biomass gasification as a potential route to generate green hydrogen.

Chapter 2 – Literature review

Hydrogen production from biomass gasification has garnered significant attention from researchers over the past few decades. The existing literature consistently highlights the effectiveness of steam as a gasification agent in enhancing hydrogen concentration in the output gas. Various approaches have been explored to achieve steam gasification of biomass for hydrogen enrichment.

Some studies in the literature focus on utilizing external energy sources to maintain the gasifier temperature and provide the necessary thermal energy for endothermic gasification reactions. Another approach involves introducing oxygen alongside steam as the gasification agent, where oxygen supports the process by combusting a portion of the volatiles generated from biomass during the devolatilization/pyrolysis process within gasification. Different reactor configurations, such as fluidized bed and fixed bed, have also been investigated in the literature.

In addition, the utilization of catalysts and external reformers to increase hydrogen concentration in syngas has been discussed. Many of the reported works are based on experiments, while others present modeling and simulation results. This chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of recent studies, examining their state-of-the-art contributions and conducting a critical review to establish a solid foundation for the subsequent discussion in this thesis.

The review of the literature is presented by categorizing the studies, starting with the literature studies followed by experimental and modeling studies.

2.1 Literature studies

Prakash Parthasarathy and K. Sheeba Narayanan (2014) provided a review of hydrogen production by steam gasification. They highlighted that biomass feed rich in starch or sugar is suitable for biochemical gasification, while thermochemical gasification can utilize a wide range of feedstocks. Temperature

was identified as the most influential parameter, with an optimal range of 800 to 900°C for hydrogen generation thorough steam gasification process.

Nikolaïdis and Poullikkas (2017) compared different hydrogen production technologies and concluded that pyrolysis and gasification are economically viable options with high potential for large-scale use. They emphasized the advantages of biomass gasification and pyrolysis, such as their CO₂-neutral nature, abundance, and low cost. However, challenges include tar formation, variable hydrogen content due to seasonal availability, and impurities in the feedstock.

Karl and Proll (2018) reviewed dual fluidized bed gasifiers in the context of steam gasification. They found that excess steam increases hydrogen, CO₂, and water content, and promotes tar reforming, thus improving dry gas quality. However, the authors suggested that adding steam after gasification rather than running the gasifier with high quantities is a better choice due to improved cold gas efficiency.

In a review by Zhang et al. (2019), they explored the exergy analysis of hydrogen production through biomass steam gasification. The study found that the gasification temperature had a positive impact on exergy efficiency, while the steam-to-biomass ratio initially increased the efficiency but later led to a decrease. The initial increase in efficiency was attributed to enhanced steam reforming reactions, while the subsequent decrease was caused by a lower reaction temperature due to higher levels of low-temperature steam. The review identified a critical range of steam-to-biomass ratios, typically between 0.7 and 3.41, for achieving higher efficiencies. The flow rate of steam exhibited a similar trend as the steam-to-biomass ratio, as they were directly proportional to each other. Increasing the steam flow rate initially increased the exergy efficiency due to factors such as increased partial pressure of moisture, improved mixing, and enhanced reforming reactions. However, further increases in flow rate led to a decrease in exergy efficiency due to reduced residence time and insufficient char for moisture. The authors defined exergy efficiency by considering the hydrogen yield as the output stream and the biomass as the input stream,

without considering other parameters. The review also discussed the impact of different catalysts on exergy efficiency.

Cao et al. (2020) examined hydrogen production through biomass gasification and emphasized the significance of temperature and steam flow rate as crucial operating parameters for economic and efficient processes. The review reinforced the suitability of steam as the preferred gasification agent for producing hydrogen-enriched syngas. To promote the widespread applicability of biomass gasification technology, the authors recommended the use of cost-effective catalysts. The review highlighted that alkali and alkaline earth metallic catalysts have the potential to enhance reforming reactions, hydrogen production, char conversion, and tar destruction. The particle size of biomass was identified as a key factor influencing gasification performance. Smaller biomass particles were found to yield higher levels of hydrogen and lower tar content due to their larger surface area, which facilitates improved heat and mass transfer, thereby increasing the gasification rate. Furthermore, the review underscored the critical role of temperature selection in achieving higher hydrogen yields. It was noted that higher temperatures do not always correlate with increased hydrogen production, primarily due to the exothermic nature of the water-gas shift reaction. Thermodynamically, this reaction is not favored at higher temperatures, and certain experiments demonstrated that hydrogen levels tended to decrease when the temperature rose above 1000°C.

Leonel J.R. Nunes (2022) discussed concurrent fixed bed gasifiers as popular options for biomass gasification, citing their advantages of low tar levels. The article also addressed syngas cleaning strategies for hydrogen production and highlighted biomass gasification as a capable technology for hydrogen generation. This review establishes that fixed bed gasification systems are most suitable from low tar levels perspective.

Tezer et al. (2022) conducted a techno-economic review of biomass gasification for hydrogen generation. The authors reviewed the theoretical models, designs and configurations along with the operating conditions. They concluded that improvements are needed in the areas of biomass gasification for hydrogen

generation to address global environmental and economic issues associated with this technology.

A few of the review articles focused on the catalytic biomass gasification for hydrogen rich syngas. In their review article, Tan et al. (2020) discuss the catalytic steam reforming of tar for hydrogen-rich syngas production in biomass gasification. They emphasize that tar reforming is a cost-effective method compared to other tar elimination techniques, as it converts tar into more valuable products at a lower cost. However, the presence of other gaseous species with tar can lead to catalyst poisoning and reduce the conversion of feedstock. The authors highlight the lack of literature on the steam reforming of tar in conjunction with the raw gaseous mixture produced during the gasification process.

In another review by Ren et al. (2019), the focus is on catalytic biomass gasification for syngas production. The authors emphasize the importance of catalysts in biomass gasification, particularly for tar cracking to generate high-value syngas. The article concludes that Ni-based catalysts with high activity and economic characteristics are the preferred choice. However, these catalysts are prone to coking and deactivation. To enhance their activity and stability, the authors suggest doping the Ni-based catalysts with transition metals, noble metals, and rare-earth metals.

2.2 Experiments & simulation studies

Balu, Lee, and Chung (2015) conducted both experimental and modeling investigations on an allothermal gasification system. The system employed high-temperature steam (877 °C and 1000 °C) as the gasifying agent in a laboratory-scale setup. The researchers found that the hydrogen content in the syngas ranged from 50% to 60% by volume, with a lower heating value of 9-10 MJ/m³. According to the study, increasing the steam temperature led to higher volume fractions of H₂ and CO, while the fraction of CH₄ decreased. These experimental results were consistent with the outcomes of the modeling study. The experiments were carried out at steam-to-biomass molar ratios ranging from 3 to 7, while the simulations were performed at a ratio of 5. The hydrogen

content and lower heating value of the syngas showed good agreement between the experimental and simulation studies. However, the modeling underestimated CO and overestimated both CO and CH₄, which the authors attributed to assumptions made in the modeling process. The authors recommended a steam-to-biomass molar ratio greater than 1.3 at 100°C steam temperature to prevent net char generation in the system. Based on the modeling studies, the cold gas efficiency reached its peak at a steam-to-biomass ratio of approximately 1.4, and then declined. Additionally, the authors calculated the hot gas efficiency, which exceeded 95% within the steam-to-biomass molar ratio range of 1.4 to 10. Below the ratio of 1.4, the efficiencies increased with the steam quantity.

Sandeep Kumar (2016) conducted experiments in a closed-top downdraft biomass gasification system using oxy-steam as the gasifying agent, as their PhD thesis work. Their study was in the SBR range of 0.75 to 2.7 and a maximum hydrogen yield of 104 g/kg-biomass was reported at the maximum SBR of the study. The ER varied from 0.18 to 0.30. The study noted that operating at higher SBR (>2.7) was not sustainable due to drop in bed temperatures as higher steam flowrate brings in endothermicity. The study also established a carbon boundary at the SBR of 1.5 where the residual carbon in the gasification system becomes zero. It is shown in their study that with an increase in SBR, carbon conversion increased and reached 100% at SBR 1.5. Before experiments with oxy-steam mixture, the author explored operations with oxygen as the gasifying medium and introducing H₂O in the system as the moisture in the biomass with moisture-to-biomass ranging from 0.75 to 1.4. Experiments with moist biomass showed a hydrogen yield of 63 g/kg-biomass at moisture-to-biomass ratio of 1.4. It should be noted that to maintain the bed temperatures, the ER at moisture-to-biomass ratio of 1.4 was 0.37, higher than usual for a gasification process. The study showed that increasing SBR or moisture-to-biomass ratio decreased the overall efficiency of the gasification process. The overall efficiency at SBR of 2.7 was reported to be ~66%. The author concluded that oxy-steam gasification operation beyond 2.7 was not

sustainable as the high flow rate of steam brought in endothermicity. The work mentioned the temperature of superheated steam to be about 427 °C.

Billaud et al. (2016) investigated the influence of H₂O, CO₂, and O₂ addition on gasification products in an entrained flow gasifier. They observed that H₂O and CO₂ addition had no significant influence on gasification, as the output gas composition mainly changed due to the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction, reaching equilibrium at approximately 1200 °C. The study showed that water-gas shift reaction is an important reaction inside a gasification system which dictates the output gas composition. In the context of oxy-steam gasification where steam is added in the system to enhance hydrogen component, water-gas shift reaction becomes even more critical.

Aydin, Yucel, and Sadikoglu (2018) performed numerical and experimental studies on a downdraft gasifier to understand the relationship between syngas production and gasification parameters. They concluded that an air-steam mixture as the oxidizing medium could be used for hydrogen production, reporting maximum hydrogen concentrations in syngas of 30.09%, 43.05%, and 42.59% for air, oxygen, and air-steam gasification, respectively.

Huang and Jin (2019) conducted experimental and simulation studies on a downdraft gasifier using pine wood particles of different sizes, temperatures, and steam-to-biomass ratios. They found that the hydrogen content in the product gas increased with decreasing particle size, attributed to increased porosity and surface area for reactions. However, the CO content decreased with decreasing particle size.

2.3 Experiments only studies

Sattar et al. (2014) conducted experiments on steam gasification of various types of char produced through intermediate pyrolysis. Their aim was to generate hydrogen-rich syngas. The researchers found that increasing steam flow and temperature had a significant positive effect on gas yield and char conversion. They also concluded that the particle size of the char had minimal impact on gas composition.

Fremaux et al. (2015) conducted experiments on a research-scale fluidized bed to produce hydrogen-rich syngas from biomass. They used a 2-kW electrical heater to externally heat the gasifier. The study revealed that increasing the steam-to-biomass ratio favored lower carbon monoxide (CO) levels and higher hydrogen (H₂) concentrations. They also observed that increasing the temperature significantly improved hydrogen production and reduced tar formation. The duration of the batch experiment also influenced hydrogen yield. Additionally, the researchers found that reducing the particle size of the biomass led to a significant improvement in hydrogen yield. The experiments were conducted at a steam-to-biomass ratio (wt. basis) ranging from 0.5 to 1 and temperatures between 700 and 900 °C. The reported maximum hydrogen yield was below 70 g/kg of wood.

Zhang et al. (2015) conducted steam gasification experiments on wet biomass (35% wt.) using a fixed bed system with a CaO/MgO sorbent. They achieved the highest hydrogen yield of 204.6 ml/g-biomass (~17 g/kg-biomass at NTP) at 850 °C. The researchers concluded that the sorbent prepared by wet mixing with limestone/dolomite exhibited higher activity in hydrogen production and resulted in lower CO₂ emissions. They found that higher temperatures favored hydrogen yield but also increased CO₂ production. The steam-to-biomass ratio studied ranged from 0 to 2.5 on a mass basis.

Yao et al. (2016) investigated hydrogen production from biomass gasification using biochar as the catalyst and catalyst support. While their study primarily focused on the efficacy of biochar, they reported a maximum hydrogen yield of 92.08 g/kg (64.02 vol.%) when cotton char supported by nickel was used as the catalyst. The researchers observed that gasifying char with H₂O and CO₂ at higher temperatures promoted CO generation while reducing the concentration of other gases. They noted that higher temperatures were not favorable for the water gas shift reaction, which contributed to a reduction in hydrogen concentration. The study also highlighted the positive effects of water in the water gas shift reaction and hydrocarbon reforming, resulting in increased production of H₂ and CO₂. Wheat straw with particle sizes of 100 and 200

microns was used as biomass, and the reactor employed a two-stage fixed bed gasifier with a quartz tube of 51 mm diameter.

Hamad et al. (2016) produced hydrogen-enriched syngas from biomass gasification using only oxygen as the gasification agent and catalysts. The study considered various operating parameters such as equivalence ratio, reaction temperature, and residence time, which ranged from 0.12 to 0.4, 700 to 850 °C, and 45 to 120 minutes, respectively. The researchers determined that the best operating conditions were an equivalence ratio of 0.25, a temperature of 800 °C, and a residence time of 90 minutes. They used calcined cement kiln dust as the catalyst and externally supported the gasification system for thermal requirements. The biomass used included cotton stalks, corn stalks, and rice straw, with a particle size of 0.8 mm. The maximum hydrogen yield reported was 45% by volume in the product gas when cotton stalks were used as biomass.

Kraussler et al. (2016) evaluated the performance of a water gas shift (WGS) reactor used to process the product gas from a biomass steam gasification plant. The WGS reactor employed a Fe/Cr-based catalyst. The researchers reported a maximum hydrogen production of 63 g H₂ per kg of biomass (dry and ash-free basis) after reforming using commercial catalysts. They emphasized that biomass steam gasification is a proven technology and a CO₂-neutral alternative to steam methane reforming. The steam gasification was performed in a dual fluidized bed system that generated gas from woodchips, with a hydrogen concentration of 40% by volume. Olivine was used as the bed material, which was maintained at around 850 °C and ambient pressure to produce high hydrogen content gas. The gas for reforming at the WGS unit was extracted before and after the scrubbing process, which involved the use of Rapeseed Methyl Ester.

Peng et al. (2017) conducted an experimental study on the air-steam gasification of wood residue in a fluidized bed using metal catalysts. The researchers concluded that a high temperature of approximately 900 °C and a higher catalytic loading (around 40%) were favorable for tar cracking and high-purity hydrogen production. They reported a maximum hydrogen concentration

of 42.5% in the cold gas at a steam-to-biomass ratio of 0.71 (wt./wt.) with an equivalence ratio of 0.17 and a temperature of 823 °C. The reactor used external support for heating.

Khan et al. (2018) analyzed hydrogen production by steam gasification of biomass using palm kernel shells as feedstock. The study utilized a pilot-scale bubbling fluidized bed reactor with a Ni-based catalyst and CaO as the CO₂ adsorbent and bed material. The reactor was externally heated. The steam-to-biomass ratio (mass basis) ranged from 1.5 to 2.5, and the temperature varied from 600 to 750 °C. The biomass particle size was up to 2 mm. The researchers found that hydrogen-based energy efficiency increased with temperature, reaching a maximum at an SBR (mass) of 2 and then slightly decreasing or remaining constant. The steam temperature before injection ranged from 250 to 300 °C. The energy requirement for gasification decreased when gasification temperature increased from 600 to 675 °C, but increased at 750 °C. This was attributed to the exothermic reaction of CO₂ adsorption on CaO, which occurred at higher rates at 675 °C and contributed to a decrease in the overall external energy required.

Li et al. (2018) presented a unique indirect biomass steam gasification system that utilized a dual bed, bubbling fluidized reactor with a circulating fluidized bed combustor. The system included a circulation pipe to circulate a mixture of bed material and char through a U-bend to a riser where combustion occurred. Wood pellets were used as the fuel, and silica sand served as the bed material. An external natural gas combustor was used for startup and to supplement char combustion. The gasification results showed consistent composition for different types of pellets, including softwood and hardwood. The researchers observed that both hydrogen (H₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) decreased with increasing temperature within the range of 750 to 831 °C, while carbon monoxide (CO) increased with temperature. The experiments were conducted at a steam-to-biomass ratio (mass basis) of 1.

Ozbas et al. (2019) conducted an experimental study on a lab-scale updraft gasifier using air and pure oxygen as the gasifying agents. The reactor was

externally heated to carry out the gasification reactions at 700 °C. The maximum hydrogen concentration obtained was 35% by volume, with an H₂/CO ratio ranging from 1.4 to 2.2. The authors also developed supervised machine learning algorithms to predict hydrogen composition, which showed good agreement with experimental values.

Wang et al. (2020) used Ni-based catalysts with in-situ CO₂ capture using CaO to improve the hydrogen yield in a two-stage fixed bed reactor. They reported a maximum hydrogen concentration of 19.32% by volume at a temperature of 424 °C. The biomass used was sawdust with a particle size of 1 mm, and the reactor was externally heated.

Barisano et al. (2021) presented the experimental results of an auto-thermal bubbling fluidized bed reactor operating at atmospheric pressure. They used an oxygen and steam mixture as the gasification medium. The authors reported hydrogen concentrations of 28.5% and 30.3% at steam-to-biomass ratios of 0.4 and 0.5, respectively, with an equivalence ratio of 0.25 and 0.28. The syngas yield in the test conditions was 1.2 Nm³/kg, which corresponds to hydrogen yields of 28.7 and 30.5 g/kg-biomass. The compositions also contained higher levels of methane (CH₄) at approximately 10%. The authors claimed that their experimental observations were validated by Aspen simulation results.

Vecten et al. (2021) presented microwave-induced plasma gasification using steam to produce hydrogen-rich syngas, with hydrogen concentrations exceeding 60%. They reported achieving 98% carbon conversion efficiency into syngas. The laboratory-scale experiments utilized a 6-kW microwave generator with a reactor feed of 50 g, operating in batch mode. The overall efficiency of the process was low (10.2%) compared to other gasification technologies, but the authors noted that efficiency could increase with higher biomass feed rates.

The studies by J. Udomsirichakorn et al. (2014) (Udomsirichakorn et al., 2014) and J. Udomsirichakorn & P. A. Salam (2014) (Udomsirichakorn & Salam, 2014) investigate the steam gasification of biomass for hydrogen production, with a particular focus on the use of CaO (calcium oxide) as a catalyst and in situ CO₂ capture. The researchers aim to address the challenges of CO₂ and tar

formation in conventional steam gasification processes. In the first study, Udomsirichakorn et al. (2014) conducted experiments in a fluidized bed reactor using CaO as a catalyst. They found that CaO facilitated in situ CO₂ capture and tar reduction during the gasification process. The maximum hydrogen yield reported was 78%, with a minimum CO₂ content of 4.98%. The hydrogen yield was measured at 578 ml (STP) per gram of biomass, equivalent to approximately 51 g/kg-biomass. The authors observed that removing CO₂ as soon as it was generated altered the equilibrium and promoted hydrogen production. In the second study, Udomsirichakorn and Salam (2014) reviewed the prospects of CaO-based chemical looping gasification for hydrogen production from biomass. They highlighted CaO as a cost-effective and abundant chemical that could serve as a catalyst for hydrogen-rich syngas production, in addition to capturing CO₂ and cracking tars within the reactor. By utilizing CaO in chemical looping gasification, they suggested that expensive and complex downstream clean-up processes could be avoided. However, they acknowledged that CaO deactivation and the need for frequent replenishment of CaO posed challenges and made the process less attractive.

The researchers emphasized the potential of CaO-based chemical looping technology to overcome the challenges associated with CO₂ and tar formation in conventional steam gasification processes. They also noted that the hydrogen production was influenced by biomass characteristics, such as higher cellulose content and a higher hydrogen-to-carbon (H-to-C) ratio. Moreover, they found that increased gasification temperature, higher steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR), and lower equivalence ratio (ER) favored hydrogen production. Overall, these studies highlight the promising role of CaO as a catalyst and in situ CO₂ capture agent in steam gasification for hydrogen production from biomass. However, they also acknowledge the challenges associated with CaO deactivation and the need for frequent replenishment, which could be addressed by the CaO-based chemical looping concept. In another similar study by Wang et al., (2020), Ni based catalysts were used with in-situ CO₂ capture using CaO in a two-stage fixed bed reactor. The study by Wang et al., (2020) report hydrogen yield at 19.32% by volume when gasification temperature was 424 C with sawdust as

feed. The study was limited in the temperature range for the study and its external energy dependency for heating would make overall efficiency go down. Also, the use of catalyst makes it operationally complex and less economical for it to be competitive.

2.4 Simulation only studies

In a study conducted by Shanmughom Ropesh et al. (2014), a thermodynamic equilibrium model was used to investigate the air-steam gasification of coconut shells. The researchers found that the maximum hydrogen yield of 36.14% was achieved at an equivalence ratio of 0.15, SBR of 1, and a gasification temperature of 1500 K. The model considered the balance of carbon, hydrogen, and oxygen, as well as the equilibrium reactions of the water-gas shift (WGS) and methanation for stoichiometric calculations.

Palozzi et al. (2016) performed a simulation study using ChemCAD software to analyze a biomass-to-hydrogen system. The system consisted of a dual fluidized bed for steam gasification, a hot gas cleaning system, a low-temperature atmospheric pressure WGS reformer, and a pressure swing adsorption (PSA) system for gas separation. The researchers investigated the effects of steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) on the gas yield and composition. Their study revealed that increasing the SBR in the range of 1 to 2 did not significantly affect the gas yield and composition, but the hydrogen yield varied between 66.9 and 74.2 g/kg-biomass. The highest hydrogen yield of 75.2 g/kg-biomass was obtained at an SBR of 2 and a residence time of 0.8 s in the WGS reactor at a temperature of 300 °C.

Moneti et al. (2016) conducted a simulation study on a dual bubbling fluidized bed biomass gasification system aiming to produce pure hydrogen. The system also included catalytic filter candles, WGS reactor and pressure swing adsorption (PSA) separator. They found that operating temperature and steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) positively affected the hydrogen yield in their study with SBR ranging from 0.5 to 2 and operating temperature range of 750 to 850 C with the entire process being autothermal.

Shayan et al. (2018) conducted a theoretical comparison of hydrogen production from biomass gasification using different gasification agents. They employed the first and second laws of thermodynamics and used an equilibrium model to simulate the gasifier. The study concluded that steam gasification resulted in a higher concentration of hydrogen and the highest exergetic efficiency compared to air gasification. The calorific value of the product gas exceeded 11 MJ/Nm³. The analysis involved four gasifying agents (steam, oxygen, oxygen-enriched air, and air) and two types of biomass (wood and paper) in a downdraft gasifier. The study found that the hydrogen concentration in the product gas decreased with increasing gasification temperature, with a maximum hydrogen content of 47.5%.

Li et al. (2020) conducted numerical modeling studies on solar-driven fluidized bed steam gasification of sewage sludge and validated the results with lab-scale fluidized bed experiments. The authors reported a hydrogen yield ranging from 61.2 to 67.6 g per kg of sludge and concluded that steam, as the gasifying agent, increased the heating value of the cold gas.

Faraji and Saidi (2021) conducted a simulation study on hydrogen-rich syngas production from various algal biomass. The study examined the effects of various operational parameters on syngas composition and H₂/CO ratio. The results showed that the operating temperature generally improved the hydrogen yield, but the increase became insignificant at higher temperatures. The authors determined 600 °C as the optimum temperature for studying other parameters. The study also found that increasing the pressure led to a decrease in hydrogen concentration, with 1 atm considered as the optimal pressure. The effect of the air volume flow rate on gas composition was also discussed, revealing that increasing the air flow rate increased the hydrogen concentration. However, a further increase in the air flow rate decreased the hydrogen yield due to combustion. The steady-state equilibrium model results were validated against experimental data reported in the literature.

In a simulation study by Yong and Abdul Rasid (2022), the introduction of steam into the gasifier was found to increase the hydrogen concentration by

10.1%. The Aspen model used in the study incorporated torrefaction and gasification processes and reported a highest H₂ concentration of 59.25% at 800 °C, with a cold gas efficiency of 84% when steam was introduced. The study concluded that the use of torrefied feed increased the overall efficiency of the system. The authors focused on the efficiency of the system, considering only the calorific value of the input feed and the output syngas, without accounting for the energy input required to maintain the reactor's temperature.

A CFD simulation study by Salem and Elsherbiny (2022) investigated the effects of changing the gasifying agent and injection point on the quality of the output syngas. The study concluded that the optimum result was obtained at a steam/biomass ratio of 0.5 when steam was used as the gasifying medium. This resulted in an increased hydrogen yield and higher heating value of the syngas. The study also considered air and CO₂ as alternative mediums. When oxy-steam was used as the gasifying agent, the simulation resulted in approximately 47% hydrogen in the syngas at a steam/biomass ratio of 1 and an equivalence ratio of 0.2. The authors noted that injecting steam within the reduction zone led to higher hydrogen concentration, higher heating value, improved performance, and reduced CO₂ emissions.

Ishaq and Dincer (2022) presented a simulation study on Aspen and Engineering Equation Solver of an integrated biomass gasification system for power, heat, and hydrogen generation. The system included an entrained flow gasifier, a cryogenic air separation unit, a Rankine cycle, a water gas shift reactor, a combined Brayton cycle, and a proton exchange membrane electrolyzer. The researchers reported an overall energy efficiency of 53.7% and an exergy efficiency of 45.5%. Steam was used as the gasification agent in the entrained flow gasifier, resulting in a hydrogen yield of 10.74 mol/s and a biomass consumption of 0.4 kg/s, equivalent to approximately 53.7 g/kg-biomass. The paper focused on the integration of different systems to generate multiple outputs rather than enhancing the hydrogen concentration.

2.5 Techno-economic analysis

Yao et al. (2017) conducted a techno-economic analysis of hydrogen production from biomass steam gasification, biogas steam reforming, and water electrolysis processes. The study concluded that the dual fluidized bed biomass gasification process had a higher H₂ conversion rate of 51.4%, which was nearly twice the conversion rate of biogas steam reforming. However, the gasification route exhibited a low fuel-based H₂ production efficiency of 38.9%. H₂ conversion rate was defined as the ratio of extracted pure H₂ to the total H fed into the process. The analysis was performed using Aspen Plus process simulation.

AlNouss et al. (2020) conducted a techno-economic and sensitivity analysis of biomass gasification using Aspen Plus, with coconut coir pith as the fuel. The analysis considered steam-to-biomass ratios ranging from 0.5 to 2.5 and temperatures between 1023 and 1223 K. The study concluded that temperature had a favorable effect on syngas output up to a certain point, beyond which the yield decreased with increasing temperature. The steam-to-biomass ratio showed a positive effect on syngas output. Simulation results indicated that increasing the temperature increased the concentrations of H₂ and CO, while decreasing the concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄. Increasing the steam-to-biomass ratio enhanced the compositions of H₂ and CO₂, while reducing the concentrations of CO and CH₄. The heat for the gasification process was obtained by burning a portion of the char in a separate reactor. The authors conducted pyrolysis experiments and used the results, along with proximate analysis, to conduct the simulations. The study focused on char gasification along with coir pith, and the techno-economic analysis at a temperature of 1123 K and a steam-to-biomass ratio of 0.75 indicated that biomass char steam gasification was more advantageous than sole biomass gasification.

In another comprehensive techno-economic study by Poluzzi et al. (2022), the authors simulated and analyzed bio-methanol and bio-hydrogen plants coupled with carbon capture and storage. The plants utilized steam and oxygen as the gasifying agent in the case of direct gasification (circulating fluidized bed) configuration, and steam and air in the case of indirect gasification (double

fluidized bed - bubbling bed gasifier and circulating bed combustor). The hydrogen concentration in the syngas after gasification was reported to be 34.3% and 44.7% for direct and indirect gasification, respectively. To further improve the hydrogen concentration, the authors proposed using two additional catalytic water-gas shift reactors after syngas generation from gasification. The fuel efficiency of the hydrogen plants was reported to be 67.6% to 68.5%, slightly higher than that of the methanol plants.

Table 2.1 presents selected works from the reviewed in this thesis which can act as the summary of the state of the art.

2.6 Research needs identified and the objective of present study

The literature review conducted for the present study has identified several needs that can add to the comprehensive understanding of the gasification process for hydrogen generation. These research needs are summarized as follows:

1. Limited research on autothermal gasification: Most existing works rely on externally supplied energy for the gasification process, with scarce data available on autothermal gasification systems aimed at producing hydrogen-enriched synthesis gas.
2. Insufficient literature on in-situ reforming: There is a lack of literature exploring in-situ reforming techniques in autothermal gasification systems, particularly utilizing the water gas shift reaction to enhance hydrogen concentration. Consequently, there exists a limited understanding of utilizing CO reforming via water gas shift reaction within the hot char bed inside a gasifier.
3. Need for higher SBR operations: The majority of studies have restricted their investigations to lower Steam-to-Biomass Ratios (SBR). There is a need to explore higher SBR operations of the gasification system utilizing steam in the gasifying media.
4. Understanding the reduction zone reactions: There is a scarcity of studies examining the catalytic effect of the hot char bed derived from biomass

on the water gas shift reaction. Understanding this phenomenon could obviate the need for an external catalytic reformer downstream of the gasifier to enhance hydrogen content in the product gas mixture.

5. Neglect of multi-fuel compatibility: Existing studies often overlook the factor of multi-fuel compatibility in the reactor used for the gasification process, which is crucial for accommodating diverse feedstocks and optimizing hydrogen enrichment.

6. Lack of study on effect of gasifying media temperature: The state-of-the-art shows that there is lack of studies on effect of injection temperature on gasification processes.

8. Limited studies on a large-scale gasification system: The literature reported is mostly on a bench-scale experimental setup.

The review underscores the immense potential of gasification as a source for hydrogen generation. However, unlocking this potential necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the technology through extensive experimental investigations. The current state of the art indicates a need for further knowledge to establish biomass gasification as a viable alternative for green hydrogen production. Building upon the identified needs in the literature regarding hydrogen generation from biomass gasification, the present study aims to address these inadequacies by conducting experimental investigations in a scaled-up setup capable of consuming approximately 14 kg/h of biomass.

2.7 Objectives of the present study

The objectives of this thesis are outlined as follows:

1. To investigate the effect of steam-to-biomass (SBR) ratio on both the process and product gas mixture yield, particularly focusing on higher ranges of SBR beyond the previously established carbon boundary point of 1.5.
2. To examine the impact of injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture on hydrogen concentration and yield, thereby elucidating optimal conditions for hydrogen production.

3. To understand the hydrogen enrichment by the catalytic behaviour of biomass char towards water gas shift reaction in a gasification system.
4. To conduct a holistic analysis of energy and exergy flow throughout the entire gasification process and its subprocesses, providing comprehensive insights into energy utilization and efficiency.

Summary

This chapter presented and consolidated the information available in literature relating to the hydrogen generation from biomass gasification route. The gaps in literature were pointed out to chart out the objectives of the present study. Present study aims to perform a comprehensive experimental examination of oxy-steam gasification process till higher regime of SBR and varying injection temperature with an aim to optimize syngas generation with maximum hydrogen.

Table 2.1 Summary of the literature review

Researcher(s)	System	H ₂	Comment
J Udomsirichakorn et al. (2014), J Udomsirichakorn & PA Salam (2014)	Fluidized bed	78% (CO ₂ 5%) – 51 g/kg biomass	CO ₂ capture using CaO, no mention of efficiency, external heating, air as the gasification agent
Prakash Parthasarathy & K. Sheeba Narayanan (2014)	Review of steam gasification	NA	Temperature and SBR important parameters
S Fremaux et al. (2015)	lab scale fluidized bed	70 g/kg	External energy, SBR 0.5 to 1
Bo Zhang et al. (2015)	fixed bed	17 g/kg	No efficiency data, SBR (mass) – 0 – 2.5
Balu, Lee, & Chung (2015)	No mention	50 – 60%	SBR 3 – 7, 1.3 as CBP, no data on efficiency, yield
Sandeep Kumar (2016)	closed top downdraft	H ₂ 50.5%, 104 g	O ₂ -H ₂ O temperature – 427 °C, SBR 0.75 – 2.7, CBP at 1.5, efficiency 66%
Moneti et al. (2016)	bubbling fluidized bed with WGSR and PSA	NA	No mention of yield and efficiency, sensitivity study, temperature and SBR favour H ₂ yield, SBR 0.5 – 2
Yao, D. et al. (2016)	lab scale fixed bed	92 g/kg (64%)	External energy, Ni catalyst on char support, SBR 4, no mention of efficiency

Hamad et al. (2016)	bench scale fixed bed	45%	External energy, No yield or efficiency data
Kraussler et al. (2016)	fluidized bed with a WGSR	63 g, 40%	No efficiency data
Peng et al. (2017)	fluidized bed	42.5%	Catalyst, external energy, SBR 0.71
Khan et al. (2018)	pilot scale fluidized bed	NA	Ni catalyst, external energy, SBR 1.5-2.5
Ozbas et al. (2019)	lab scale updraft	35%	External heating, no efficiency data
Li, et al., (2020)	lab scale fluidized	61.2 to 67.6 g	Solar driven steam gasification, no efficiency data
Barisano et al. (2021)	Bubbling fluidized bed	30.5 g	Autothermal, lower SBR of 0.5, high level of methane (10%)

Chapter 3 – Material and methods

This chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the experimental setups and methodologies utilized in the study, covering a range of fuel specifications employed in the current experimental campaign. All necessary materials required for conducting the experimental investigation are detailed herein.

The present study employed two distinct experimental configurations: a downdraft gasification system and a packed bed reactor, each designed to address specific objectives outlined in previous chapters. The gasification system facilitated the comprehensive evaluation of the entire syngas generation process, while the packed bed reactor utilized hot biomass char as the bed material to replicate the reduction zone environment of a gasification system. The gasification system enabled the quantification of the effects of steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) and injection temperature on output parameters, while the char bed reactor assessed the catalytic effect of hot char on the water gas shift reaction, ultimately leading to hydrogen enrichment.

This chapter also delves into the auxiliary systems and instruments utilized in conjunction with the gasification unit in detail. The latter portion of the chapter outlines the methodologies employed for the treatment and analysis of the data recorded during the experiments, aiming to derive meaningful metrics of performance.

3.1 Experimental setup – Oxy-steam gasification

3.1.1 The reactor

The gasification system is a downdraft fixed bed cylindrical reactor with an internal diameter of 200 mm and height 2 m. The reactor is a modified version of the open-top downdraft gasification system developed at the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, as discussed by researchers (Dasappa, Paul, Mukunda, Rajan, & Sridhar, 2004; Mukunda, Dasappa, Paul, Rajan, & Shrinivasa, 1994; Dasappa, Shrinivasa, Baliga, & Mukunda, 1989). The fuel is fed at the top of the reactor and the gaseous product exits the reactor from the bottom. The

downdraft gasifiers have been proven to be consistently generating product gas with the low tar content as the pyrolysis product gases get to pass through the hot char bed. The high temperature in the reduction zone breaks down the

Figure 3-1. The oxy-steam gasification system

higher hydrocarbon into simpler gaseous molecules (H_2 , CO , CO_2 , and CH_4). The modified version the of gasifier ensures an extended zone of high temperature assisting in obtaining the gas with lower tar (Kumar & Dasappa, 2013).

In the modified configuration of the open-top downdraft gasification system, the design now incorporates an oxy-steam mixture as the primary gasifying agent. Additionally, a lock-hopper mechanism has been integrated at the top of the system to ensure leakproof operation. The pneumatic lock-hopper system allows feeding of the biomass keeping the reactor isolated from the ambient. The biomass feeding was done in regular intervals for continuous operation of the system. The biomass travels downwards undergoing subprocesses (i) drying, (ii) pyrolysis, (iii) oxidation, and (iv) reduction as it comes from top to bottom of the reactor.

Oxy-steam injection system comprised of a supply line carrying mixture of steam and oxygen. The superheated steam and oxygen mix into a common stream just before entering the reactor. The line was well insulated to retain the temperature of the oxy-steam mixture till the injection nozzles of the reactor. The oxy-steam mixture enters the reactor at a height of 600 mm from the bottom of the reactor. The two injection points were located diametrically opposite to each other, and the arrangement was such that the oxy-steam mixture entered as jets penetrating towards the core of the cylindrical reactor for homogeneous distribution across the porous bed in radial

Figure 3-2. Schematic of the oxy-steam gasification system with cleaning and cooling system. The reactor has different zones (top to bottom): 1. Drying (100 – 200 °C), 2. Pyrolysis (200 – 500 °C), 3. Oxidation (750 – 900 °C), and 4. Reduction (600 – 750 °C).

direction. The oxygen in mixture allows a part of pyrolytic product to combust to raise the temperature of the bed; identified as the oxidation zone promoting self-sustained auto-thermal operation. The exothermicity of the oxidation reactions near the injection points aids sustain the endothermic pyrolysis process and the reduction reactions that would take place in the char bed beneath the oxidation zone. The pyrolysis process also generates char that moves downwards and takes part in char gasification reactions, predominantly with CO_2 and H_2O generating more CO and H_2 . Char reaction with oxygen is understood to be insignificant as the oxygen availability is scarce and the gas

phase reactions of oxygen take precedence over heterogeneous reaction with char leaving no oxygen for char oxidation to CO and CO_2 . Residual char after the entire gasification process can be extracted at the bottom part of the reactor.

The cylindrical reactor has a screw conveyor system at the bottom to facilitate char and ash extraction at regular interval. Char extraction can be controlled depending on the operation and its generation rate inside the reactor; the char bed builds up when there is a net char generation (char generated by pyrolysis minus char consumed in gasification reactions minus char extracted). The char building up results in hot char bed extending above the injection level to the pyrolysis zone leading to insufficient length/time for the pyrolysis process to complete. In such cases, the temperature in the pyrolysis zone increases and goes up to 700 °C as it gets occupied by char. This scenario suggests that the char extraction is lower than required. There may also be a deficit of char in the system due to excess extraction rate of char. The char deficit leads to char bed depletion, and this reflects as the decreased temperature levels of the bed below the injection point as the space gets occupied by the biomass. In short, the extraction rate is dictated by the char bed level. The extraction system helps in avoiding the building-up of the char bed inside the reactor along with the ash removal to avoid formation of clinkers due to ash agglomeration. Char extraction also disturbs the bed by causing its movement which helps in avoiding an increase in pressure drop across the packed bed of biomass and char inside the reactor due to plugging. Plugging can happen due to trapping of fine particles in the porous bed of fixed bed particles. Extraction also helps overcome the bridging problem inside the reactor. The product gas finally leaves the reactor at the bottom for cleaning and cooling. The gas exiting the reactor is laden with dust and particulates along with water vapours and some higher molecular weight compounds which need to be removed to obtain clean, dry, and cold gas.

The cylindrical reactor is fitted with thermocouple to monitor and record the bed temperatures at different zones of the gasifier. The thermocouples along

with an acquisition system are used to display and store the temperatures in a computer. A pressure tapping at the exit of the reactor gives the pressure drop in the reactor which is one of the indicators of the healthy operation of the gasifier.

3.1.2 Cooling and cleaning system

The conditioning of the raw gas is done in the cooling and cleaning unit of the reactor at the downstream. The first component in this unit is cyclone separator. The high temperature raw gas is led to the cyclone where dust and particulates get separated by using the principle of inertia. The incoming stream of hot gas enters the cyclone tangentially at the top to establish a spiral pattern of gas flow ending at the bottom end before exiting the cyclone in a straight stream through the centre of the cyclone from the top. The denser and larger particles in the rotating stream, due to their inertia, get collected at the bin provided at the bottom of cyclone. The hot gas cyclone separators are well suited for removal of solid particles larger than 10 microns (Reed & Das, 1988). The cyclone acts as a prefilter for cooling unit and fine particulate removal as they can operate at higher separation or collection efficiency. The cyclone separator also helps in bringing the temperature of gas down by 250 to 300 °C by losing heat to the ambient.

The gas from the exit of the cyclone is drawn through a series of wet scrubbers where dust and moisture removal take place and gas is brought down to nearly ambient temperature. The wet scrubbers use water as the scrubbing liquid where gas is passed through a direct water spray system. This direct gas-liquid contact promotes condensation of the water vapour in the hot gas. Also, the finer particles smaller than 0.1 micron which are difficult to separate using inertia and follow Brownian motion principles, can be collected by diffusion using water sprays (Reed & Das, 1988). The gas gets cooled by direct free convective cooling. The water condensable tars are also removed in the water scrubbers when the temperature falls below the dew point of tars. The water scrubber creates conditions of maximum contact between the raw gas and the scrubbing liquid as the liquid gets atomized by the spray nozzles. The cooling

and cleaning unit has three stages of cleaning water scrubbers: two with water at room temperature and one with the chilled water. The inlet water temperature in the chilled scrubber is kept at 6 to 8 °C. The chilled water spray reduces the fine particulate matter, and its lower temperature ensures that the water vapour in gas reaches its dew point.

The wet scrubbers also serve the purpose of creating a draft in the upstream of the system, water being the motive fluid and the product gas from the gasifier being the secondary fluid, which helps in drawing the gas by venturi effect.

3.1.3 Residual moisture removal

The scrubbing unit ensures that the raw gas gets dried while passing through the scrubbers. However, during the process of water vapor condensation, the gas also picks up moisture which get convected with the cold gas. This residual moisture removal is done at the moisture traps installed in the cooling and cleaning unit. The moisture containing gas impinges on a surface which causes coalescence resulting in conversion of moisture into water droplets. The moisture traps or mist removing system with a complicated pathway enables mist drops to interact with each other and coalesce and drop down (Mukunda H. S., 2011). Finally, the output gas is devoid of the moisture and at near ambient temperature.

3.1.4 Induced draft in the gasification system

The gas generated in the gasifier needs to overcome the pressure drop of the packed bed, and in the cleaning and cooling unit before its delivery as cold and dry gas. The cyclone separator, wet scrubbers, moisture traps, and passageway for the gas with several bends cause a pressure drop in the flow. This is overcome by inducing draft using a blower immediately after the cleaning and cooling unit. The blower delivers the clean and cold gas at marginally above ambient pressure.

3.1.5 Filtration

The cold and cleaned gas is further cleaned for residual finer particulates and tars. This is achieved by using a pre-coat candle filter at the downstream of the

blower. The gas coming out of the candle filter is cleaner with the lowest tar content of 2.7 mg/Nm³ by gravimetric analysis and 37.6 mg/Nm³ by GC-MS method (Rakesh & Dasappa, 2018).

3.1.6 Steam generation

The steam for the process is generated using a custom-made 36 kW electric boiler with 200 L capacity which could withstand 10 bar (g) of pressure. The boiler is equipped with a safety valve to avoid pressure build up beyond 4 bar (g). The steam generation rate was controlled by switching on the modular heating coils fitted with the boiler. The boiler is equipped with a magnetic level indicator to record the water level with time to calculate the steam generation rate. The saturated steam from the boiler is taken to an electric superheater where steam temperature is raised by radiant heating. The steam at the superheater outlet could go up to 900 °C.

Figure 3-3 Steam generation system used in gasification - boiler and superheater

3.1.6 Oxygen supply

Oxygen supply for the experiments was ensured from a liquid oxygen (LOX) cylinder procured commercially. The arrangement has an evaporator which at ambient temperature delivers gaseous oxygen. The oxygen line meets the steam

supply line coming from the superheater near the reactor. The flow rate of oxygen supply is regulated using a rotameter.

Figure 3-4 Oxygen supply for gasification from LOX cylinder

3.2 Biomass – characterization and properties

Three kinds of biomass were used in the present study: casuarina wood chips (*casuarina equisetifolia*), coconut shells and corncobs to assess the multifuel capability of the system. The bulk density of the biomass ranged from 150 to 425 kg/m^3 with a variation in shape and sizes. The biomass was prepared before feeding to the system. The biomass underwent thorough preparation, which included cleaning, size segregation, and air drying prior to being fed into the system. Subsequently, random samples were taken from the clean and air-dried biomass lot for moisture content evaluation.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3-5 Biomass used in the oxy-steam gasification study (a) casuarina wood chips, (b) coconut shells and (c) corncob

Table 3.1 Properties of biomass

	Casuarina wood chips	Coconut shells	Corncob
Size	45mm×19mm×10mm	34mm×27mm×3mm	23mm×50mm (D×L)
Density (kg/m^3)	650 ± 10	1100 ± 100	238 ± 34
Bulk density (kg/m^3)	400 ± 10	425 ± 10	150 ± 6
Proximate analysis (mass%)			
Volatiles	88 ± 1.02	81.40 ± 0.65	80.90 ± 0.25
Fixed carbon	10.90 ± 1.02	18.25 ± 0.62	16.12 ± 0.70
Ash content	1.20 ± 0.04	0.39 ± 0.06	3 ± 0.52
Ultimate analysis (mass%)			
C	48.70 ± 1.2	51.40 ± 0.8	45.23 ± 0.9
H	6.10 ± 0.2	6.10 ± 0.2	6.24 ± 0.2
O	45.03 ± 1.1	42.40 ± 0.9	48.14 ± 1.3
N	0.07 ± 0.01	0.06 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.02
S	0.15 ± 0.1	0.16 ± 0.06	0.14 ± 0.1
Higher Heating Value (MJ/kg)	18.3 ± 0.4	20.5 ± 0.3	17.5 ± 0.4
HHV/kg-O ₂ ($MJ/kg/kg-O_2$)	13.6	14.4	14.2
Higher Heating Value (MJ/kg) – Boie equation (Annamalai & Puri, 2007)	19.2	20.5	17.8
Chemical formula	CH _{1.5} O _{0.69} N _{0.001}	CH _{1.42} O _{0.62} N _{0.001}	CH _{1.65} O _{0.8} N _{0.005}
Molecular weight ($kg/kmol$)	24.7	23.4	26.5

3.3 Instrumentation

3.3.1 Gas flow measurement

The cold gas after the cooling and cleaning process passes through a venturimeter for the flow measurement. The differential head created in the U-tube manometer gives the flow rate of the cold and dry gas according to the formula as below.

$$Q_{actual} = C_d \frac{A_1 A_2}{\sqrt{A_1^2 - A_2^2}} \sqrt{2gh} \quad 3.1$$

The actual flow rate was calculated considering the coefficient of discharge (C_d) as 0.98. A separate calibration exercise was done to find out the coefficient to calculate the actual volume flow rate of the gas. In equation 2.1, Q_{actual} is the actual volume flow rate, A_1 and A_2 are the areas of cross-section at the inlet section and the throat of the venturimeter, respectively, h is the differential head and g is the acceleration due to gravity (9.8 m/s^2). Mass flow rate was subsequently calculated by multiplying the density of the gas with the volume flow rate calculated using the differential head.

3.3.2 Temperature measurement

The reactor has thermocouples installed at an interval of 100 mm of height, starting from the bottom, in oxy-steam mixture supply line just before its injection in the reactor and at the exit of the reactor for hot gas temperature. The thermocouples used were K-type (temperature up to 1260 °C) with a data acquisition system (IOtech Personal DAQ 55) connected to a computer for monitoring and storing the data. The acquisition of data took place each 2 seconds and real-time data was monitored on the computer for smooth and steady operation of the system.

Figure 3-6 Data Acquisition System for temperature

3.3.3 Gas composition measurement

The clean and cold gas at the downstream of the system was sampled and its composition was measured by a gas chromatography (GC) system of Perkin Elmer make (model: Clarus 680). The GC uses Carboxen 1010 column (30 m length and 530 μm diameter) and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) to calculate the volumetric composition of the sample. Carboxen 1010 column is used to separate the permanent gases which include hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen, carbon monoxide, methane carbon dioxide, helium, and light hydrocarbons (C_2 - C_3) in the same analysis. The GC was calibrated using standard composition mixtures before doing the analysis. The calibration exercise involved creating a method file. A method is a collection of parameters that control the GC. Method includes the temperature conditions in the oven, injector and detector, flow rate of the carrier gas, split ratio along with the standard reference compositions, among other parameters. The composition of the different levels of calibration is presented in the Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Calibration composition levels of the GC

Level	H_2	O_2	N_2	CO	CH_4	CO_2	C_2H_2	C_2H_4	C_2H_6
1	0	20.9	79.1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	51.09	0	0	9.44	2.99	34.98	0.5	0.5	0.5
3	20.12	0	45.74	20.11	2	12.03	0	0	0
4	34.95	0	8.16	27.98	4.01	24.9	0	0	0

The total analysis time by the GC was 25 minutes including for the elution of C_2 compounds.

Figure 3-7 Gas Chromatography System for gas composition analysis

3.4 Methodology – Gasification study

Before starting the reactor, a char bed is ensured at the lower part of the reactor, at least till the ignition nozzle which lies at 300 mm from the bottom. However, a larger char bed enables a quick start-up, and it is preferable to maintain this up to the oxy-steam injection point. Further, biomass is fed from the top and reactor is filled till the top of the reactor. The blower connected at the downstream of the set-up is switched on which induces a draft in the system. The top of the reactor is kept open and ambient air is sucked. The reactor is ignited using a wick through the ignition nozzles provided at the reactor bottom, and the gasifier is started in air mode of operation. The cooling and cleaning unit of the system is also switched on, which starts water circulation through the scrubbers. Due to incoming air from the top char bed starts glowing and the partial oxidation of the char bed sustains the propagation of flame front towards the unignited parts of the char bed. Heat release due to char oxidation raises the bed temperature. The temperature profile is monitored, and the reactor is operated in air mode till the flame front reaches the biomass in the vicinity of the char bed. Once the reactor is ready with the hot char bed (temperature $> 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and biomass starts pyrolyzing, oxy-steam injection can

be done. Monitoring cold gas composition also helps in knowing the onset of biomass gasification process. As biomass in the reactor starts pyrolyzing, an increase in the cold gas flow rate and hydrogen composition can be seen. The clean and cold gas is finally flared in the ambient using a specially designed burner.

The oxygen from the LOX cylinder and superheated steam from the superheater mix just before the injection nozzle at the reactor. The oxy-steam mixture supply takes place at a pressure slightly above the ambient. The top of the reactor is closed, and the gasifier operation in oxy-steam mode sets in. Slightly above ambient pressure condition inside the reactor also helps in preventing air leakage into the system. Any leakage into the reactor will increase the oxidizer availability and burn a part of combustibles unwantedly. Also, air leakage into the system will bring nitrogen into the system adding to the energy loss from the system as the sensible enthalpy. The set flow rate of oxygen and the steam dictate the operating condition of the experiment. Another crucial control parameter is the oxy-steam temperature (controlled by superheated steam temperature). Before sending the reactant mixture of oxygen and steam, by the time the gasifier gets ready for oxy-steam mode, the oxy-steam mixture is vented to the ambient so that the temperature of the mixture becomes steady.

The amounts of oxygen and the steam supplied are represented as equivalence ratio (ER) and steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR), respectively. These also are the operating parameters along with the oxy-steam injection temperature. ER for a solid fuel is calculated as the ratio of actual oxygen to fuel ratio to the stoichiometric air to fuel ratio. In case of air gasification, instead of oxygen, amount of air is considered for the ER calculation. SBR is calculated as the ratios of moles of steam going into the system and the biomass. The definitions of ER and SBR are presented in equations 3.2 and 3.3.

$$ER = \frac{(kg/h)_{oxygen}/(kg/h)_{biomass}}{[(kg/h)_{oxygen}/(kg/h)_{biomass}]_{st}} \quad 3.2$$

$$SBR = \frac{Moles_{steam}}{Moles_{biomass}} \quad 3.3$$

3.5 Elemental mass balance

To assess the performance of the gasification system and hydrogen yield, output parameters, gas composition and cold gas flow rate were used. Equation 3.5 presents the overall gasification process in terms of a global chemical reaction. The raw gas produced from the gasifier contains water vapor which is one of the combustion products of any hydrogen containing fuel. However, in present study the process involves superheated steam and some amount of moisture in the input side. During the process, a part of it takes part in chemical reactions inside the reactor and some amount remains unconverted. To completely establish the mass balance, quantification of H_2O is necessary. Along with H_2O and cold gas on the product side, amount of char extracted (residual) at the bottom must be quantified too.

The input parameters, mass flow rates of biomass, oxygen, and steam are known and using the flow rate and composition of cold gas the coefficients $m_3 \dots m_6$ can be calculated. Further, coefficients m_1 and m_2 were obtained using the $C - H - O$ elements balance. Equating C on LHS and RHS we get the coefficient m_2 , while coefficient to H_2O on the RHS, m_1 , can be obtained using the H or O balance. Finally, total mass at input side and output side was verified to check the correctness of the analysis. The input and mass must be theoretically equal, however, due to uncertainties in measurement and inherent inaccuracies in biomass elemental composition, perfect equality cannot be established. The uncertainties were accounted for and an error analysis for all the data was carried out. These results have been reported in a separate section.

3.6 Efficiency calculation

To evaluate the efficacy of any conversion process energetic efficiency is popularly reported. Energy efficiency accounts for the total energy input to carry out the process and the energy in the desired output. In case of

gasification, the input to the process is the fuel, energy spent in the steam generation process and the energy cost of the oxygen. The process also incurs additional energy consumption in the cooling and cleaning part along with that required in operating the blower. These energy expenses have been account and collectively presented in the current study as the auxiliary power required.

3.6.1 Energy efficiency

Energy efficiency of the process can be calculated in two ways. The synthesis gas can be treated as the output in one approach while another approach can treat hydrogen in the product gas as the desired output. In present study, the analysis of results was done in both the approaches. The formulae for the calculation are presented as 3.5 and 3.6.

$$\eta_{gasification} = \frac{\dot{m}_{coldgas} \times LHV_{coldgas} \times 100}{(\dot{m}_{biomass} \times LHV_{biomass} + \dot{m}_{steam} \times \Delta h_{steam} + \dot{m}_{oxygen} \times h_{cryo-sep} + E_{Aux})} \quad 3.5$$

$$\eta_{hydrogen} = \frac{\dot{m}_{hydrogen} \times LHV_{hydrogen} \times 100}{(\dot{m}_{biomass} \times LHV_{biomass} + \dot{m}_{steam} \times \Delta h_{steam} + \dot{m}_{oxygen} \times h_{cryo-sep} + E_{Aux})} \quad 3.6$$

In equations 3.5 and 3.6, η is the efficiency, \dot{m} is the mass flow rate in kg/h , LHV is the lower heating value in MJ/kg , Δh_{steam} is the energy spent in generating steam, $h_{cryo-sep}$ is the energy required to produce oxygen by cryogenic separation and E_{Aux} is the auxiliary energy consumption in operating the gasification system.

3.6.2 Exergy efficiency

Exergy efficiency is calculated to study the true process efficiency. This analysis provides information on the maximum available work from a process while accounting for the irreversibilities. In present work, the exergy balance has been established by taking chemical exergy of the biomass as the input exergy flow into the process. The output exergy flow corresponds to exergy in the product synthesis gas. The exergy of syngas can be calculated as a total of two components: physical and chemical exergy. Physical exergy of a gas mixture is

associated with its state – temperature and pressure, in other words, the deviation from the ambient state, while the chemical exergy component is calculated using the chemical potential of the gaseous species which defined as the maximum work (useful energy) that can be obtained from it in taking it to chemical equilibrium composition with the environment.

Exergy efficiency is defined as the exergy in the product of the process divided by the exergy of the stream in the input. This is mathematically presented as follows:

$$\psi = \frac{e_{ph_gas} + e_{ch_gas}}{e_{ch_biomass} + e_{H_2O} + e_{O_2}} \quad 3.7$$

Exergy efficiency is denoted as ψ . In equation 3.7, e_{ph_gas} is the physical exergy in the output syngas stream, e_{ch_gas} is the chemical exergy, $e_{ch_biomass}$ is the chemical exergy in the biomass, e_{H_2O} is the exergy associated with the superheated steam in the input and e_{O_2} is the exergy input in cryogenic separation process to generate liquid oxygen.

Further, physical and chemical exergy in the output stream are calculated as given below.

$$e_{ph_gas} = \sum [(h_i - h_{0i}) - T_0(S_i - S_{0i})] \quad 3.8$$

$$e_{ch_gas} = \sum X_i Ex_{O,i} + RT_0 \sum X_i \ln X_i \quad 3.9$$

In equations 3.8 and 3.9, h_i & S_i are enthalpy and entropy of the component i , respectively, X_i is the mole fraction of component i and Ex_O is the standard exergy.

Exergy in the biomass was calculated using equation 3.10 as taken from (Karamarkovic & Karamarkovic, 2010).

$$e_{ch_biomass} = z_{org}(\beta LHV_{org}) + z_S(e_{ch,S} - C_S) + z_{water}e_{ch,water} + z_{ash}e_{ch,ash} \quad 3.10$$

$$\beta = \frac{1.044 + 0.0160 \left[\frac{H}{C}\right] - 0.3493 \left[\frac{O}{C}\right] \left\{1 + 0.0531 \left[\frac{H}{C}\right]\right\} + 0.0493 \left[\frac{N}{C}\right]}{1 - 0.41240 \left[\frac{O}{C}\right]} \quad 3.11$$

In equations 3.10 & 3.11, β is the ratio of the chemical exergy to the LHV of the organic fraction of the biomass and, $\frac{H}{C}$, $\frac{O}{C}$ and $\frac{N}{C}$ are the atomic ratios in the biomass, with z representing the mass fraction in the biomass.

3.7 Experimental set-up – Char bed study

The experimental investigation also involved study on a packed bed of biomass char to understand the influence of hot bed of biomass char on homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions. An independent small-scale set-up was developed for the study.

The set-up contained a reactor, a steam generating furnace, a venturi mixer, a muffle furnace to heat the reactant mixture before the reactor, a condenser to remove moisture from the product gas, and a gas chromatography system for the dry gas composition of the product mixture.

Figure 3-8 Experimental setup for char bed study

3.7.1 The reactor

A ceramic tube (66% alumina) of 50 mm internal diameter and 400 mm length was used as the reactor. The reactor had electrical heating coils cemented from the outside and insulation from all around to maintain an isothermal condition inside the reactor during an experiment. The reactor stood vertical where the provision for reactant entry was at the bottom and product gas exited from the

top. A grate was placed inside the reactor to support the packed bed of activated charcoal. The temperature in the reactor was set and maintained using a proportional integral derivative (PID) controller and the char inside the ceramic reactor was supported on a porous grate to allow the passage for gases from bottom. Temperature monitoring and acquisition was done using K-type thermocouples inside the reactor.

3.7.2 The reactants

The reactants in this study were pure gases or gas mixtures procured commercially. The flow rates were controlled by using Alicat make mass flow controllers (MC series). The experiments took place with CO-steam mixture, CO-CO₂-steam mixture, and producer gas-steam mixture. Producer gas contained H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄ and N₂. The reactant gases mixed with superheated steam before they were sent to the reactor with the char bed. Steam was generated using an electric furnace which received demineralized water at one end and gave superheated steam at the other end. Steam supply took place with the help of a peristaltic pump which could pump the demineralized water at a set flow rate. The steam and gas stream mixed in a venturi mixer before passing through a muffle furnace which raised the temperature of the mixture to closer to that intended at the reactor. The reactant mixture with steam entered the reactor from bottom and passed through the hot char bed which was kept at a fixed temperature maintaining an isothermal environment.

3.7.3 The product gas

The product gas exited the reactor from the top. The hot gases were first cooled, and the unreacted steam was condensed in a condenser where condensate was regularly measured. Further, the cool and dry gas was made to pass through a calcium chloride filter for filtering residual moisture from the gas. A part of the gas flow was taken for sampling for gas composition using a gas analyser and a GC before flaring in a burner.

3.7.4 Gas composition analysis

A gas analyser, SICK S715 was used to monitor the gas composition. SICK S715 is an online gas analyser with sensors for detecting and quantifying the

gases in a mixture. The response time of the instrument was < 45 s. The gas analyser contained OXOR-P, Thermor, and a Multor sensor (SICK AG, 2021). The module OXOR-P is a precision oxygen which operates on a rotating diamagnetic dumbbell which is suspended in an inhomogeneous magnetic field. The paramagnetic nature of oxygen exerts a torque on the dumbbell which is proportional to the oxygen concentration in the analyte mixture. Module Thermor is used for hydrogen detection. This module is based on the different thermal conductivity of gases. The measuring cell in the module contains a chamber containing four resistance wires of highly stable temperature coefficient. The resistances are arranged as a Wheatstone bridge where each pair of opposite resistances are arranged as one chamber. Heat is generated in the resistances electrically and is dissipated by the surrounding sample gas. In equilibrium condition the resistance attains a temperature depending on the thermal conductivity of the gas in the chamber which changes the resistance of the wire. This change in resistance creates an unbalanced voltage across the bridge which is proportional to the change in resistance and thus to the change in concentration of gas in the chamber. The Multor module functions on the principles of non-destructive infra-red (NDIR) spectroscopy and can detect up to 3 infra-red components. This module detects CO_2 , CO & CH_4 . In this module infra-red light is emitted from a source and is not dispersed or scattered by the substance between the light source and the detector. The gas in the path of the infra-red light absorbs the light which is a function of the abundance of the gas between the source and the detector.

3.8 Methodology – Char bed study

The study of homogeneous and heterogeneous reactions in the hot char bed started with loading biomass-based activated charcoal on the reactor. A measured amount of char was loaded, and the height of the bed was measured to obtain the residence time of the reactant gases. The heater of the reactor was switched on and the desired temperature was set. During the process of heating the char bed a continuous flow of nitrogen was maintained to keep the environment inert and prevent oxidation of the char bed as the temperature raised.

Figure 3-9 Gas analyser

As the bed temperature was achieved, the reactants supply to the reactor was switched on after stopping the nitrogen flow. The reactants passed through the char bed where all the possible reactions took place to generate product gas. The product gas also would contain some amount of the unreacted reactants species. The dry gas composition was recorded at the gas analyzer and the GC. The control parameters in these experiments were H₂O/CO ratio, temperature, and the residence time. The residence time of all the experiments was maintained at ~0.5 s which approximates to the time scale the gases spend in the hot char bed of a downdraft gasifier. Each experiment took place for about 200 min. Experiment concluded with stopping the supply of the reactant and sending nitrogen to prevent char oxidation. The supply of the nitrogen took place till the temperature of the char bed reached ambient condition. Char was unloaded from the reactor after the reactor cooled down, and weight was measured.

The overall chemical equation for the experiment can be presented as equation 3.12.

In equation 3.11, coefficients of the species on the left-hand side ($a_1..a_7$) are the amount of char, the gas composition, gas flow rate and steam flow rates are known quantities. The coefficients to the species on RHS can be treated as unknown quantities except for x_1 , which is the char measured after the experiment. The condensate quantity x_7 has been taken as the unknown and computed and tallied with the collected amount. There are 6 unknowns on the RHS and the 6 equations can be obtained by using the C , H , O balance, H_2 & CO volume fraction in the cold gas and equating nitrogen on the both sides.

3.9 Error analysis

Error analysis is important in scientific investigations. As a study is conducted, the uncertainty in measured values and analysis can bring in some error in the measured and derived values. Hence, it becomes essential to assess all uncertainties for reporting the results with accurate conclusions.

The present study involves sample preparation, measurements, calculations, and analyses. All these steps come with inherent uncertainties. The errors are broadly categorized into two types.

1. Systemic error
2. Random error

Systemic error in a study arises from measurements using an instrument. These are defined as a consistent and proportionate difference between measured and true values. These are fixed errors which cause repeated readings to be in error by same amount. Random error, however, is unpredictable and occurs due to fluctuations in environment, instrument limitations, or human interpretations.

In the present study, biomass and char samples were used as feed. Before the experiment, samples were characterized, dried, and weighed. Further, the experiments involved steam flow measurements, oxygen flow measurements, on the input side; and, gas flow measurements, residual char measurements, gas composition measurements on the output side. For further analysis of data, elemental mass balance technique was used. Experimental data collection and processing can be a potential source of errors. These need to be estimated to

assess the degree of accuracy of results. The section below presents systemic errors associated with different instruments used, and random errors incurred during sample collection and data analysis.

3.9.1 Error estimation

Table 3.3 Error from instruments

S. No.	Instrument	Error
1.	Venturimeter	±1%
2.	Thermocouple (K-type)	±2.2%
3.	IOtech DAQ system	±1.2 °C
4.	Gas chromatography system	
	H ₂	±0.5%
	CO	±1.8%
	CO ₂	±1.6%
	CH ₄	±10%
	N ₂	±1.6%
5.	Gas Analyzer	±0.005%
6.	Weighing balance	±0.5g
7.	Bomb calorimeter	±0.05MJ/kg

3.9.2 Uncertainty analysis

Sampling errors are random errors which occur when finite samples are used for measurements to represent a larger population. In present study, for size and density measurements, samples (biomass & char) were measured, and average results have been presented with standard deviation to account for the error.

Standard deviation can be calculated as below:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \bar{x}|^2}{n - 1}}$$

σ : standard deviation

x : measured value

\bar{x} : average of measured value

n : sample size

Present work has considered $\bar{x} \pm \sigma$ for reporting sampling error which translates to about 68% confidence interval.

While reporting the output gas composition, the gas was sampled and sent for gas chromatography. At the end of each experiment, the average composition was calculated and reported with the standard deviation as error bars. The standard deviation in such measurements were calculated as presented below.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum |x - \bar{x}|^2}{n - 1}}$$

The measured values are then presented as $\bar{x} \pm \sigma$.

3.9.3 Error Propagation

We can quantify the errors from measurements and instruments as discussed in preceding discussion; and we use these when we calculate some desired results from experiments. The uncertainty in the calculated result can be obtained from the uncertainties in primary measurements. For example, if R is the calculated results from several measurements in the experiments, we can express R as a function of independent variables as below.

$$R = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, \dots, x_n)$$

If u_R is the uncertainty in the result R and $u_1, u_2, u_3, u_4, \dots, u_n$ be the uncertainties in the independent variables, the u_R can be calculated as

$$u_R = \left[\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1} u_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_2} u_2 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_3} u_3 \right)^2 + \dots + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_n} u_n \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

Some desired results are the product of multiple independent variables (measurements). We can generalize such functions as

$$R = x_1^{a_1} x_2^{a_2} x_3^{a_3} \dots x_n^{a_n}$$

Fractional uncertainty in such cases can be derived as

$$\frac{u_R}{R} = \left[\sum \left(\frac{a_i u_{x_i}}{x_i} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

For results which are additive function as

$$R = \sum a_i x_i$$

the uncertainty can be expressed as

$$u_R = \left[\sum (a_i u_{x_i})^2 \right]^{1/2}$$

Summary

Chapter 3 illustrates comprehensively the materials and methods used in the present study. It starts with a detailed description of the gasification reactor along with supplementary systems for supplying oxygen and steam used for conducting the experiments. This chapter covers all the instruments used in measurements with the characterization of the feed material used. The chapter also explains the additional experimental setup designed to study the impact of hot char bed on hydrogen enrichment during the gasification process. A discussion on the experimental procedure has also been included with remarks on the methods to analyze the data collected during the experiments. The chapter concludes with a brief description on the uncertainty analysis.

Chapter 4 - Oxy-steam gasification experiments with lower injection temperature ($< 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

As highlighted in the literature survey (Chapter 2), the study conducted by (Kumar, 2016) demonstrated that oxy-steam gasification operation, with an oxy-steam temperature of $377\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ establishes carbon boundary point (CBP) at steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) of 1.5. In the present study, the sustainability and performance of operation at various injection temperatures were evaluated with the aim of maximizing the hydrogen yield from oxy-steam gasification of biomass. This chapter discusses the performance and stability of a fixed bed downdraft oxy-steam gasification system at injection temperatures lower than $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Experiments were conducted to study the operation of the gasification system in SBR above and beyond the previously identified CBP (SBR 1.5). The experiments took place with two kinds of biomass: casuarina wood chips and coconut shells; different from each other in physical properties. The successful use of different kinds of biomass in the gasification system as feed makes the system multifuel capable.

The SBR, ER and oxy-steam injection temperature ranges for the two feeds used in the present study are as follows:

Casuarina: SBR: 2.7 – 4.7, Injection temp.: $375 - 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, ER: 0.28 – 0.48

Coconut shells: SBR: 1.3 – 3.6, Injection temp.: $380 - 500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, ER: 0.25 – 0.40

4.1 Dry gas composition

Figure 4-1 presents the dry gas composition of the syngas obtained at the outlet of gasification system for the two types of biomasses used as feed. The oxy-steam injection temperature varied from $375\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and equivalence ratio (ER) varied from 0.25 to 0.5 (0.25 to 0.48 on wet biomass basis).

The volumetric composition of the product gas mixture shows that beyond the previously established CBP of SBR 1.5, the change in hydrogen composition is insignificant when SBR increases from 1.3 to 4.7. An increase in SBR has also resulted in little to no change in methane concentration. With respect to CO

and CO₂ concentration, as SBR increased, a decrease in CO has accompanied an increase in CO₂ concentration. However, CO and CO₂ would further stagnate at SBRs beyond 3.5. A discussion is presented in the following sections for individual components variation with SBR.

Figure 4-1 Dry gas composition – casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

4.1.1 Hydrogen

The hydrogen composition in dry gas mixture is presented in Figure 4-1. The variation of molar hydrogen composition shows that there is marginal or no increase when SBR increased from 1.3 to 4.7. Experiments with casuarina and coconut shells took place beyond previously established CBP of SBR = 1.5 (Kumar, 2016) (barring two data points with respect to coconut shells as feed corresponding to SBR 1.3). For coconut shells, hydrogen increased from $43.7 \pm 0.2\%$ at SBR 1.3 to $48.3 \pm 0.6\%$ at SBR 3.6. In case of casuarina wood chips, maximum hydrogen recorded was $49.5 \pm 2.1\%$ at an SBR of 3.6 while $44.9 \pm 2.1\%$ hydrogen was obtained at SBR of 2.9.

Figure 4-2 Hydrogen in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

4.1.2 Carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide

From Figure 4-3, carbon monoxide in dry gas mixture can be observed to decrease consistently with an increase in SBR. However, beyond SBR of 3.7, the CO concentration does not decrease, instead the level stagnates with marginal increase for casuarina wood chips. For coconut shells, the SBR variation from 1.3 to 3.6 shows a consistent decrease in CO concentration. Decrease in CO fraction in dry gas mixture can be explained as a direct result of water gas shift reaction favoring at higher steam concentration in the system, with corresponding increase in hydrogen concentration. However, further increase in SBR does not result in a similar decreasing trend in CO concentration. It is also evident from Figure 4-3 that CO levels in the case of two types of biomasses are different. In the case of coconut shells, the CO concentration in the product syngas is higher than that in case of casuarina wood chips, at similar SBRs. This difference could be due to the difference in water gas shift reaction rates and corresponding CO conversion because of variation in morphology of char generated in the system after pyrolysis process for the two biomass types. The difference in CO level can be due to different catalytic behavior of the biomass chars generated in the system – the catalytic

behavior can be exhibited by activated char due to inorganic materials present in char and its porous structure. The role of water gas shift reaction in decreasing trend of CO can also be validated by CO₂ concentration variation with SBR as presented in Figure 4-4. It is evident that CO₂ concentration increases with an increase in SBR (accompanied by corresponding decrease in CO concentration in Figure 4-3)

Figure 4-3 Carbon monoxide in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperature (<550 °C)

Similar to CO concentration, the CO₂ concentrations for the two kinds of biomasses are different over a range of SBR. It is clear that CO₂ concentration for casuarina wood chips is more than that for coconut shells. From Figure 4-3 & Figure 4-4, it can be observed that for casuarina wood chips, the CO levels are lower and CO₂ levels are higher than coconut shells, indicating more CO conversion in case of casuarina wood chips. As discussed, the difference in water gas shift reaction rates in both the cases can be different due to different char properties. This can be attributed to higher reactivity of coconut shells based char generated in the system than the wood based char.

Figure 4-4 Carbon dioxide in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

4.1.3 Methane

Figure 4-5 presents CH₄ in dry gas mixture at the gasifier exit for both the biomass as feed. The variation of CH₄ concentration with SBR shows that the concentration remains almost invariant when SBR increases from 1.3 to 4.7. The average concentration in dry gas observed is 3.4%. Comparing the average composition for the two biomasses used, the CH₄ concentration in case of coconut shells is 3.6%, higher than that for casuarina wood chips at 3.1%. It can be inferred that oxy-steam mode of gasification operation results in more CH₄ concentration in the product syngas in comparison to air gasification in a downdraft gasification system which is ~1% in dry gas mixture (Mukunda H. S., 2011). A relatively higher concentration of methane in oxy-steam gasification can be attributed to the methanation reaction of hydrogen with CO in the system. Steam present in oxy-steam gasification promotes hydrogen generation and the hydrogen in system in comparison to air gasification is higher. Higher amounts of hydrogen can result in reaction with CO to generate CH₄ and H₂O.

Figure 4-5 Methane in dry gas - casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

4.2 Hydrogen yield

Hydrogen yield can be defined as the hydrogen obtained in the product syngas per kg of biomass consumed. Figure 4-6 presents hydrogen yield over a range of SBR for the cases when oxy-steam injection temperature is in the range $375 - 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The trend shows that yield increases with SBR, however, it is also seen that it is variable at an SBR (captured in y-error band). This variation is due to different oxy-steam injection temperatures. The effect of injection temperature has been discussed in an upcoming section. The plot also shows that hydrogen yield is more for coconut shells than casuarina wood chips when the experimental data points are fitted linearly. In the SBR range of 2.7 to 4.7 for casuarina wood chips, maximum hydrogen yield obtained was 96.6 g/kg at SBR of 4.2. For coconut shells, in SBR range of 1.3 to 3.6, maximum yield was obtained at SBR of 3.6 and yield was 95.2 g/kg of biomass.

Figure 4-6 Hydrogen yield for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

4.3 Gas yield

Gas yield is an important indicator of the gasification performance along with the composition of the product dry gas. Higher conversion ratios are desirable as this results in higher hydrogen yield, biomass conversion and gasification efficiency. Figure 4-7 presents the variation of dry gas yield in kg/kg for casuarina and coconut shells. The average gas yield for both the biomasses comes out to be 1.9 kg per kg of dry biomass. The minimum yield has been obtained as 1.5 kg/kg (SBR 3.2) and 1.7 kg/kg (SBR 3.2 & 3.6) for coconut shells and casuarina wood chips, respectively. Maximum yield for casuarina wood chips in the experimental range corresponding to lower oxy-steam injection temperatures is 2.2 kg/kg at SBR 4.2 while that for coconut shells is 2.1 kg/kg at SBR of 2.1. It should be noted that Figure 4-7 shows the variation with SBR discounting the effect of oxy-steam injection temperature. Effect of oxy-steam temperature will be discussed separately in upcoming sections.

Figure 4-7 Gas yield for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

4.4 Gasification efficiency

To assess the performance of the gasification system, cold gas (energy) efficiency has been calculated for each experiment according to the mathematical expression as presented in equation 3.5. Increasing SBR corresponds to higher quantities of steam in the system which consequently results in higher input of energy to the system. In an effort to explore hydrogen enrichment, the increased energy expenditure is accounted using the cold gas efficiency. Figure 4-8 presents the efficiency of gasification for casuarina wood chips and coconut shells in the injection temperature regime up to $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is evident that the gasification efficiency decreases with increasing SBR. Maximum efficiency for coconut shells was obtained at the lowest SBR of experiment, 1.3, and it was 78% (average). Similarly, for casuarina wood chips, the maximum gasification efficiency of 64.2% was observed at SBR 2.7, the lowest SBR for casuarina wood chips with lower injection temperature. Minimum efficiencies for coconut shells and casuarina wood chips were recorded as 44.8% and 42.3%, at SBR 3.2 and 3.7, respectively.

Figure 4-8 Cold/dry gas efficiency for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

The gasification efficiency decreases as the SBR of experiment increases. This decrease in energy efficiency is attributed to increasing energy required to generate more steam. Figure 4-9 presents the energy mix at the inlet of the system to give a picture of major contribution from steam in the energy perspective. It is evident that energy input with superheated steam keeps on increasing with SBR with expected corresponding decrease in energy input with biomass, for both the biomasses. It is also seen that, at the same SBR, contribution from biomass and steam is different for casuarina wood chips and coconut shells. This can be attributed to the fact that calorific value of coconut shells (20.5 MJ/kg) is higher than that of casuarina wood chips (18.3 MJ/kg). The energy input through biomass was observed to as high as 82.7% at SBR 1.3 to the lowest of 52.5% at SBR 4.7. As expected, the input energy from steam becomes significant at higher SBR resulting in lower efficiencies. The operation at higher SBR can only be justified as long as the gas yield with higher hydrogen yield accompanied with higher efficiencies can be obtained. In present study, the hydrogen yield and gas yield (Figure 4-6 & Figure 4-7) stagnate while energy efficiency of the process continuously decreases. Optimum operation of the gasification system process requires that the increase in

hydrogen yield with an increase in SBR should be able to justify the energy cost of generation.

Figure 4-9 Energy input percentage contribution by biomass and steam versus SBR at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for casuarina and coconut shells

4.4 Hydrogen efficiency

Hydrogen efficiency is defined as the ratio of energy obtained at the outlet of the gasification system in form of hydrogen in dry gas and the total energy input (see equation 3.6). Figure 4-10 presents the variation of hydrogen efficiency with respect to SBR for casuarina wood chips and coconut shells. The hydrogen efficiency tends to decrease with an increase in SBR. However, the decrease is less steep than that in the case of overall gasification efficiency. The average hydrogen efficiency for casuarina wood chips is about 35% (maximum 42.9% at SBR 1.3) while that for coconut shells is 36.2% (maximum 41.6% at SBR 3.5). Barring one data point corresponding to SBR 3.2 for coconut shells, the efficiency for both types of biomasses is above 30%. From Figure 4-10, it can be inferred that, although hydrogen yield (Figure 4-6) shows an increasing trend with the SBR, the hydrogen efficiency does not increase, instead, a decrease with a gradient (lesser than that of overall efficiency) is observed because of the energy spent in generating steam for higher SBR operation.

Figure 4-10 Hydrogen efficiency for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

4.5 H₂O conversion

Oxy-steam gasification is usually employed to increase the hydrogen concentration in the product synthesis gas. Steam present in oxidizing media mixture helps promote the reactions which result in hydrogen generation. The major hydrogen generating reactions involve water gas shift and steam-char reactions which reduce H₂O on the reactant side to H₂ on the product side. These reactions are H₂O conversion reactions from a hydrogen generation point of view. The conversion efficiency can thus be calculated for the gasification process to assess the effect of increasing the partial pressure of H₂O by increasing the SBR. Equation 4.1 presents the formula to calculate the H₂O conversion. H₂O_{in} includes the moisture content incoming with the biomass.

$$\text{H}_2\text{O conversion, \%} = \frac{(\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{in}} - \text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{out}})}{\text{H}_2\text{O}_{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad 4.1$$

Figure 4-11 conducted using casuarina wood chips and coconut shells as feed materials, focusing on lower injection temperatures. The data reveal a general trend of decreasing H₂O conversion as the steam-to-biomass ratio (SBR) increases. An observation drawn from the data is that the average conversion

rate was approximately 15% for both types of biomass within the SBR range of 2.4-4.2 (highlighted region in Figure 4-11). Specifically, for casuarina wood chips, the average H₂O conversion within the SBR range of 2.7 to 4.2 is 12.8%, while for coconut shells, the average H₂O conversion within the SBR range of 2.4 to 3.6 is 17.4%. Additionally, higher H₂O conversion rates were recorded at lower SBR values (1.3 - 2.2) for coconut shells, ranging from approximately 27-50%. The variation in conversion percentage with SBR indicates that the addition of steam to the system does not significantly decrease H₂O conversion above an SBR of 2.4; moreover, it remains within the range of 9 to 20%. The lack of decrease in H₂O conversion percentage at higher SBR values implies that the net amount of H₂O consumed would increase. Higher SBR corresponds to a greater amount of steam in the system. The increased amount of steam, resulting in an insignificant change in conversion percentage, suggests that the absolute amount of H₂O converted during the process is higher. This indicates that an increase in SBR would introduce additional hydrogen into the system by reducing H₂O through water gas shift and steam-char reactions. The addition of hydrogen in the system from H₂O can also be illustrated for both types of biomass to comprehend the effect of higher SBR on H₂O conversion.

Figure 4-11 H₂O conversion for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

Figure 4-12 presents the hydrogen addition in the gasification system from H₂O. The average hydrogen addition from H₂O conversion for casuarina wood chips is about 37 g/kg-biomass while the same for coconut shells comes out to be about 43 g/kg-biomass. Considering the hydrogen bonded in biomass i.e., about 61 g/kg-biomass, the hydrogen addition from H₂O conversion results in higher hydrogen yield in oxy-steam mode of operation.

Figure 4-12 H₂ in the system by H₂O conversion for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures (<550 °C)

4.5 Equivalence ratio

Equivalence ratio (ER) is the parameter to account for the oxidizer amount with respect to fuel. In the case of a gasification system the fuel is solid biomass, and the process requires oxygen to make it autothermal. ER is calculated according to the formula presented in equation 3.2. ER affects the energetics of the process which results in various compositions of the product gas mixture. In the present study, the ER varied in the range of 0.25 to 0.50. The average ER in the case of casuarina wood chips is 0.37 while in case of coconut shells it is 0.31. It should be noted that in present discussion, lower injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture, the experiments with casuarina took place at higher SBRs, i.e., 2.7 to 4.7, and the SBR range for coconut shells is from 1.3 to 3.6. Operating at higher SBRs implies that a higher amount of steam

going into the system brings endothermicity which can bring down the average temperature inside the reactor and halt the operation. For sustained operation, to compensate for the endothermicity due to incoming steam into the system, the system is operated at relatively higher ER. Higher ER facilitates a higher amount of combustibles generated post pyrolysis to release energy on oxidation to maintain a conducive thermal environment to sustain and promote gasification reactions. Figure 4-13 presents the ER for varying SBR for low injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture for both kinds of biomass. The plot shows a general trend of increasing ER with SBR.

Figure 4-13 ER for casuarina and coconut shells at lower injection temperatures ($<550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Summary

Chapter 4 presents the results from the first part of experimental studies where the injection temperature of the gasifying agent is less than $550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The discussion on the results comprises of analysis of composition, hydrogen yield, and efficiency among another derived parameters which indicate the process efficacy. The study spanned across SBR ranging from 1.3 to 4.7 with two types of biomass feeds, casuarina wood chips and coconut shells, and the experiments were aimed at higher SBRs (beyond the previously established CBP of 1.5). It

was found that the reactor could be operated beyond CBP by maintaining the thermal stability in the system, by increasing the injection temperature and maintaining the ER, as SBR increases. The results show that hydrogen concentration improves marginally when SBR increases from 2.1 to 4.7. The maximum hydrogen concentration was 49.5% at SBR 3.6 with casuarina wood chips. The maximum hydrogen yield obtained was about 97 g/kg at SBR of 4.2 at lower injection temperatures. The average gas yield was 1.9 kg per kg of biomass. Similar study will be subsequently presented with higher oxy-steam injection temperatures.

Chapter 5 – Effect of char bed towards water gas shift and char reactions to study in-situ reforming of CO in a gasification system

During oxy-steam gasification of biomass, the volatiles, oxidation product and oxidizing agent pass through the hot char bed in reduction zone. Important gasification reactions of solid C with H₂O and CO₂ take place in reduction zone to yield H₂ and CO. Along with the two heterogeneous gasification reactions of C, a homogeneous reaction between CO and H₂O known as water gas shift reaction takes place over the char bed. Water gas shift reaction plays an essential role in overall gasification process, especially in oxy-steam or steam gasification process where hydrogen enrichment in product synthesis gas is intended.

To understand the water gas shift reaction on a char bed which can have a catalytic effect on the reaction while the char bed is subjected to a reactant mixture containing CO and H₂O, a separate experimental setup was developed to simulate the reduction zone of a gasification system in oxy-steam mode. The main objectives of this study are summarized as two points below.

1. To study the catalytic effects of biomass char on water gas shift reaction
2. To evaluate the effects of temperature and partial pressure of steam on hydrogen generation

The reduction zone of the gasification system was simulated using the activated charcoal bed in a ceramic reactor, as explained in Chapter 3.

Initial experiments were conducted to investigate the temperature effects on the water gas shift reaction over the char bed. These experiments aimed to comprehend the impact of temperature by maintaining a constant H₂O/CO (R) ratio of 2. A lower R was chosen where the steam partial pressure influence on WGS reaction is lower, and temperature effect can be captured. Subsequently,

the R was varied from 2 to 10 by keeping the temperature constant to capture the effect of partial pressure of steam.

Commercial catalytic water gas shift reactors intake feed contains 3-75% CO (Lloyd, Ridler, & Twigg, 1989) and steam/gas ratio ranges from 1 to 5 (Kohl & Nielsen, 1997). Higher ratios of R correspond to higher steam partial pressure which promotes the water gas shift reaction resulting in higher conversion pushing the equilibrium towards product side (Reddy & Smirniotis, 2015).

Figure 5-1 Temperature dependence of the Gibbs free energy ($\Delta_r G$) and equilibrium constant (K_{WGS}) of the water-gas shift reaction. (S, 2021)

Figure 5-1 presents the variation of Gibbs free energy and the equilibrium constant for the WGSR. The plot shows that the reaction is favoured at lower temperatures since the equilibrium constant of the reaction increases as the temperature decreases and correspondingly, the Gibbs free energy of the reaction approaches minimum at the lowest temperature. The plot clearly shows that the WGSR is dominant in the lower temperatures zone while at higher temperatures reverse WGSR is dominant. The forward and reverse WGSR are equally favoured at 1100 K and an equilibrium exists when Gibbs free energy is zero and the corresponding equilibrium constant is 1.

Typical R in an oxy-steam gasification is presented in Figure 5-2. In Figure 5-2, x-axis is an independent parameter of an oxy-steam operation known as SBR* which represents the net H₂O (steam + moisture in biomass) in the input stream per atom of carbon in the biomass, and y-axis is the H₂O/CO in the product synthesis gas. Figure 5-2 shows that H₂O/CO in oxy-steam gasification system is about 5 at SBR* of 2 and can go as high as 18 at SBR* of 4.

Figure 5-2 H₂O/CO (R) in an oxy-steam gasification system

Three kinds of biomass based activated charcoal samples were used as the char bed material in the present study: two coconut shell based, and a wood based. These samples were procured commercially. Table 5.1 presents the properties of all the biomass-based samples used as the bed material for the study.

Table 5.1 Properties of char samples used as bed material

Char type	Coconut shell based (CC1)	Coconut shell based (CC2)	Wood based (WC)
Iodine value (mg/g)	900	1120	900
Surface area (m ² /g)	614	930	543
Bulk density	590	590	300-400
Mesh size	4 – 8	4 – 8	4 – 8
Ash	1.7	1.5	13

5.1 CO-H₂O feed on activated char bed

Experiments started with the feed containing CO-H₂O mixture at a ratio (R) of 2 to understand the progress of water gas shift reaction on biomass char bed when no other species is present in the reactant mixture. The feed was sent through hot char bed where the temperature was varied from 520 °C to 760 °C. The experiments with the same feed took place with two kinds of activated charcoal: coconut shell based (CC1), and wood based (WC).

5.1.1 Effect of temperature

5.1.1.1 Dry gas composition of the product gas

Temperature has exhibited a favourable effect on the water gas shift reaction when the reactant mixture contained pure CO and H₂O. The dry gas composition of the product gas is depicted in Figure 5-3 and Figure 5-4. It can be observed from the gas composition that an increase in temperature leads to a decrease in the CO fraction in the product, accompanied by an increase in the fractions of CO₂ and H₂. This decrease in CO volume% and the corresponding increase in H₂ and CO₂ volume% validate the occurrence of the water gas shift reaction. Notably, the water gas shift reaction generates CO₂ and H₂ in equal moles, and it is evident from the plots that the H₂ and CO₂ volume% in the dry gas are approximately the same as long as no char consumption is observed (refer Table 5.2). With an increase in temperature the H₂ and CO₂ fractions can be seen to increase. The increase in these fractions can be attributed to temperature favouring kinetics of the water gas shift reaction. Water gas shift reaction is an exothermic reaction which is thermodynamically favourable at lower temperature, however, higher temperature, as in present case, favours the kinetics of the reaction, as evident in the Figure 5-3 and Figure 5-4. It should be noted that water gas shift reaction in present case takes place in char bed which can potentially have a catalysing effect on the reaction, proven and discussed in the next section.

Figure 5-3 Dry gas composition of product gas with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on coconut shell based activated charcoal bed (CC1)

Figure 5-4 Dry gas composition of product gas with $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed at $R = 2$ on wood based activated charcoal bed (WC)

The dry gas composition of the product mixture also shows that CO_2 and H_2 volume % remain almost equal up to a temperature, 570 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for coconut shell

based activated char (CC1) and 720 °C for wood based activated char (WC) in present study. At higher temperatures, the difference between CO₂ and H₂ volume% increases with H₂ being more than CO₂. This indicates that there is another reaction taking place which is the source of H₂. This difference shows that beyond a temperature, along with water gas shift reaction, steam char reaction also takes place.

5.1.1.2 Consumption and generation rates of species

Table 5.2 presents the consumption and generation rate of different species for CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 on coconut shell and wood based activated charcoal. The generation and consumption data also shows that temperature has a favourable effect on water gas shift reaction. The rates data also validates that up to a temperature, only water gas shift reaction takes place, and as temperature increases char consumption is observed. The char consumption can be attributed to steam char reaction, as H₂ is observed to be more than CO₂. The char consumption for CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 for two activated char bed kicks off at different temperatures. For coconut shell based activated char (CC1), the char consumption can be observed to start at a lower temperature (570 °C) while that for the wood based activated charcoal (WC) is 720 °C. However, in case of coconut shell based activated charcoal (CC1) bed it is evident that there is a steep increase in the steam char reaction rate (char consumption) when temperature increases from 720 °C to 760 °C.

Table 5.2 Production and consumption rates of species – CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 on char bed

Coconut shell based activated charcoal (CC1)					
T	H ₂ O	H ₂	CO ₂	C	Increase in C consumption
(°C)		mmol-h ⁻¹ -gchar ⁻¹			%
520	3.6	3.5	3.6	0.00	No char consumption
570	5.9	6	5.5	0.41	-
620	7.8	7.8	6.9	0.86	110
670	11.3	11.3	9.9	1.33	55
720	19.9	19.9	17.1	2.80	111
760	30.3	30.3	22.2	8.06	188
Wood based activated charcoal (WC1)					
T	H ₂ O	H ₂	CO ₂	C	Increase in char consumption
(°C)		mmol-h ⁻¹ -gchar ⁻¹			%
570	1.6	1.4	1.7	0	No char consumption
620	2.5	2.5	2.5	0	No char consumption
670	4.3	4.3	4.3	0	No char consumption
720	6.6	6.6	6.1	0.6	-
760	9.3	9.3	8.4	1	71.4

From the experimental observation for char bed with CO-H₂O feed, it is evident that as the temperature increases the difference between the generation rate of hydrogen and carbon dioxide widens, with corresponding increase in char consumption rate. In cases when char consumption takes place, the H₂ generation rate is more than the CO₂ generation rate. Char consumption indicates steam char reaction taking place in the system which also contributes to excess hydrogen (hydrogen more than the CO₂). Also, analysis shows that C-CO₂ reaction does not take place in the experimental conditions presented in the present study. The char consumption rate matches the rate of H₂O consumption and H₂ generation rates. The occurrence of the C-CO₂ reaction would have resulted in additional CO in the system and char consumption would be different from H₂O consumption rates. Literature also shows that C-CO₂ reaction takes place at temperatures above 900 °C (Singh, Gupta, N., Shivapuji, & Dasappa, 2022).

In the present analysis, char consumption is attributed to the steam-char reaction, which also generates hydrogen. Based on the total hydrogen generation rate, the stoichiometry of the water gas shift reaction is established. By establishing the stoichiometries of the steam-char reaction and the water gas shift reaction based on char consumption and hydrogen generation rates, the obtained rates of CO₂, H₂O, and CO align perfectly with the experimentally observed values. In other words, as the temperature increases, the rate of the water gas shift reaction increases, with the steam-char reaction occurring in parallel, which also takes place at a higher rate at higher temperatures. In present case of coconut shell based activated charcoal as bed material for CO-H₂O feed at R = 2, it is evident that steam-char reaction kicks off at 570 °C with a sharp increase of 188% when temperature increases from 720 to 760 °C.

The rates of hydrogen generation from water gas shift and steam-char reactions are presented in Figure 5-5. It is evident from the figure that the temperature promotes the water gas shift reaction on char bed. It can also be noted that with an increase in water gas shift reaction rate, hydrogen is also contributed by steam char reaction taking place at higher temperature accompanied by char

consumption. Hydrogen contribution from steam char reaction at 760 °C is about 27% for CC1 while it is about 11% for WC.

Figure 5-5 Rate of hydrogen generation with $CO-H_2O$ feed on coconut shell based activated charcoal bed (CC1) at $R = 2$

Figure 5-6 Rate of hydrogen generation with $CO-H_2O$ feed on wood based activated charcoal bed (WC) at $R = 2$

5.1.1.3 CO conversion

As water gas shift reaction is promoted at higher temperature on char bed, CO conversion increases as it converts to CO₂. Figure 5-7 shows CO conversion with temperature for CO-H₂O feed on CC1 and WC beds. CO conversion increases with the temperature as rate of the water gas shift reaction increased with an increase in temperature. However, when temperature increases from 720 to 760 °C in case of CC1, there is no apparent increase in CO conversion. No increase in CO conversion after 720 °C can be attributed to steam char reaction which adds CO into the system. At higher temperature, water gas shift reaction is kinetically favoured, and rate of reaction increases which consumes CO while char-steam reaction adds CO in the system. At temperature 760 °C, there is steep rise in char consumption rate which generates CO at the same rate. This addition of CO brings down the net CO conversion at higher temperature.

In case of WC bed also CO conversion increases with an increase in temperature. Figure 5-7 presents and compares the CO conversion data for the two char beds. It is evident that CC1 bed has shown higher CO conversion than that in case of WC bed. Though both the biomass samples show the same trend of water gas shift reaction being promoted with an increase in temperature, rate of reaction for CC1 is about 3 times of that for WC. It is conspicuous that coconut shell based activated charcoal is more favourable and shows more activity towards the water gas shift reaction. Higher activity of coconut shell based activated charcoal is due to its physical, structural, and chemical properties due to presence of the minerals. Higher surface area avails greater number of active sites which promote chemical reactions as increased surface area allows activated charcoal to adsorb a large quantity of molecules onto its surface. Presence of certain minerals like potassium, calcium, and manganese create additional active sites on the activated charcoal surface, enhancing its activity.

Figure 5-7 CO conversion for CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 on coconut shell and wood based activated charcoal

5.1.2 Catalytic activity of biomass char

The char samples used in this study showed that temperature kinetically favoured the water gas shift reaction by showing higher CO conversion and higher reaction rates when temperature was increased. Further, to validate about the catalytic activity of activated char bed on water gas shift reaction, the CO-H₂O feed was sent through an inert bed at the same R. The rate of reaction and CO conversion data was compared with the two char samples data. Table 5.3 presents the generation and consumption data of species along with the CO conversion for the two char beds and the inert bed.

The comparison shows that in case of activated charcoal bed, CO conversion was 7 times of that in inert bed showing that the water gas shift reaction in case of activated charcoal took place at higher rate resulting in higher CO conversion. It should be noted that in case of char beds, presented conversion % is for the overall rate which also included the CO generated by steam char reaction as at 720 °C there was char consumption recorded for both char samples (see Table 5.2). Actual CO conversion by only water gas shift reaction would be higher than the presented number. Table 5.3 also shows the rates of species consumed and produced. Presented numbers correspond to overall rates

and numbers for water gas shift reaction can be obtained using the char consumption data as presented in Figure 5-5 and Figure 5-6.

Table 5.3 CO conversion and rates for CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 at 720 °C

Bed material	CO conversion%	Generation rates (mmol/min)				
		CO(-)	H ₂ O(-)	CO ₂	H ₂	C(-)
Coconut shell based activated char bed (CC1)	21	11.9	16.5	14.2	16.6	2.3
Wood based activated char bed (WC)	8.1	4.6	5.5	5.1	5.5	0.5
Inert bed	3	2.8	2.8	2.8	2.7	NA

Figure 5-8 presents the dry gas composition of the product gas in case of inert bed. On comparing the gas composition results from two cases (char beds and inert bed) it is evident that char bed catalyses the water gas shift reaction. The experiment with inert bed at 720 °C generated the dry gas with CO₂ and H₂ at 2.9 and 2.8%, respectively, with bulk of CO exiting the reactor unreacted at 94.3% in the product gas; while in case of coconut shell based activated char bed it was 18.8 and 21.9% for CO₂ and H₂, respectively. The difference in CO₂ and H₂ percentage in product gas at higher temperature is due to steam char reaction that generates additional hydrogen in the system.

Gas composition, rate of reaction and CO conversion data show, on comparison, that in case of char beds water gas shift reaction took place at higher rate than in case of inert bed. The experimental studies on char bed and inert bed at R = 2 with CO-H₂O feed show that char indeed shows a catalytic effect towards water gas shift reaction while steam char reaction takes place in parallel. The reason for the catalytic effect can be attributed to char properties which are discussed in the following section.

Figure 5-8 Dry gas composition of the product gas with CO-H₂O feed at R = 2 on an inert bed

To understand the difference in behaviour of the two char samples, Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was done to know the elemental composition of samples which can further help explain the catalytic effect exhibited by the char samples towards the water gas shift reaction.

Table 5.4 presents the results of EDS analysis performed on the ash obtained from two activated charcoal samples. The analysis shows that coconut shell based activated charcoal ash contained about 47% potassium and about 3% calcium while wood-based char ash showed lower amounts of potassium and calcium at 2.3% and 1.5%, respectively. Presence of potassium has been reported to enhance the steam-char reaction and water gas shift reaction (Kuchonthara, Vitidsant, & Tsutsumi, 2008; Kim, et al., 2013). Though WC contained higher Al and Si levels, CC1 exhibited higher activity due to higher surface area.

Table 5.4. SEM-EDS results of the ash of char samples

	Coconut shell based (CC1)	Wood based (WC)
Element	mass %	
O	36.5 ± 6.9	59.8 ± 4.6
Na	2.9 ± 1	0.5 ± 0.4
Mg	1 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.2
Al	0.1 ± 0.2	13.6 ± 3.6
Si	2.1 ± 0.9	19.3 ± 2.1
P	1.4 ± 0.2	0.1 ± 0.3
S	2.1 ± 0.9	-
Cl	3.9 ± 0.4	-
K	46.9 ± 7.1	2.3 ± 2.1
Ca	2.9 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 1.3
Fe	0.3 ± 0.5	2.4 ± 3.1
Ti	-	0.2 ± 0.5

5.1.3 Arrhenius parameters of the char samples – water gas shift reaction

Rate of water gas shift reaction in the case of activated char samples could be calculated based on char consumption. To arrive at the Arrhenius parameters for the char samples, we can write the chemical equation for the water gas shift reaction at the equilibrium as follows.

In chemical equation 3.1, k_1 and k_2 are the rate constants for the forward and reverse water gas shift reaction. Thus, the rate of reaction can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} r_{WGS} &= k_1 p_{CO} p_{H_2O} - k_2 p_{H_2} p_{CO_2} \\ &= k_1 (p_{CO} p_{H_2O} - \frac{k_2}{k_1} p_{H_2} p_{CO_2}) \\ &= k_1 (p_{CO} p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2} p_{CO_2}}{K}) \end{aligned} \quad 3.2$$

In above equation, K is equilibrium constant which can be used to replace $\frac{k_2}{k_1}$ as any catalytic effects do not change the equilibrium and only reduces the chemical resistance.

As per the Laupicher model, the relation between rate of hydrogen production (r_{WGS}) and $(p_{CO} p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2} p_{CO_2}}{K})$ is linear for the water gas shift reaction (Diniyati, Morishita, & Takarada, 2009; Laupichler, 1938) assuming water gas shift reaction to be a homogeneous bimolecular reaction. In present study, we plotted the (r_{WGS}) and $(p_{CO} p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2} p_{CO_2}}{K})$ for both the samples for experiment at $R = 2$ at various temperature. Figure 5-9 and Figure 5-10 present the plot showing the linear relationship between the two.

Figure 5-9 Rate vs. partial pressure product for CC1 (experiments temperature range 520 – 760 °C)

Figure 5-10 Rate vs. partial pressure product for WC (experiments temperature range 520 – 760 °C)

The above plots show that the Laupichler model fits well with the present work. The rate constant (k) can be expressed in terms of pre-exponential factor (A), activation energy (E_a) and temperature (T) as $k = A \cdot \exp(-\frac{E_a}{RT})$ as per Arrhenius equation. The Arrhenius parameters for the two samples can be

calculated by plotting $\frac{1}{T}$ and $\ln(k)$ for the two samples. The slope of the plot ($-\frac{E_a}{RT}$) gives the activation energy and y-axis intercept gives the pre-exponential factor.

Figure 5-11 Arrhenius plot for WGSR for CC1 (experiments temperature range 520 – 760 °C)

Figure 5-12 Arrhenius plot for WGSR for WC (experiments temperature range 520 – 760 °C)

The slope is $-\frac{E_a}{R}$ and intercept is $\ln(A)$, where E_a is activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and A is the pre-exponential factor also known as the frequency factor.

Table 5.5 Slope and intercept for Arrhenius parameters

	Slope	Intercept
CC1	-8266.1	13.06
WC	-9087.2	12.57

The activation energy and the pre-exponential factor for the char samples can be presented in the Table 5.6 below.

Table 5.6 Arrhenius parameters for the char beds used

	Activation energy, E_a (kJ/mol)	Pre-exponential factor, A (mmol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹ char atm ⁻²)
CC1	68.7	469770.7
WC	75.6	286645.1

The rate expressions for the two char samples are (mol h⁻¹ g⁻¹char):

Coconut shells based, CC1:

$$r_{WGS} = 4.7 \times 10^2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{68728.5}{RT}\right) \left(p_{CO}p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2}p_{CO_2}}{K}\right)$$

Wood based, WC:

$$r_{WGS} = 2.9 \times 10^2 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{75555.5}{RT}\right) \left(p_{CO}p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2}p_{CO_2}}{K}\right)$$

Researchers (Diniyat, Morishita, Li, & Takarada, 2009) calculated the Arrhenius parameters for water gas shift reaction for two different samples of high ash coal char and they report the rate expressions as:

$$r_{WGS} = 2.17 \times 10^9 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{124800}{RT}\right) \left(p_{CO}p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2}p_{CO_2}}{K}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$r_{WGS} = 8 \times 10^8 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{127900}{RT}\right) \left(p_{CO}p_{H_2O} - \frac{p_{H_2}p_{CO_2}}{K}\right)$$

where rate is expressed in mmol h⁻¹ g⁻¹char.

The experiments with CO-H₂O feed at $R = 2$ at various temperature have showed that at temperature between 720 °C and 760 °C, the char reaction with steam takes place with a significant hydrogen contribution of about 27% in case of coconut shell based activated char bed (CC1), rest of it coming from water gas shift reaction. It is apparent from the results that there exists a transition temperature at which hydrogen generation from homogeneous water gas shift reaction and heterogeneous steam char reaction becomes important. The temperature of interest becomes a range between 720 °C and 760 °C. To understand the reactions and effects of partial pressure of steam, thereby varying the H₂O/CO ratio, the study continued with CO-H₂O feed on the char bed at temperature 750 ± 10 °C. The study took place at the constant temperature by varying the H₂O/CO ratio.

5.1.4 CO-H₂O feed on the activated char bed at varying R and fixed temperature

For studying the impact of partial pressures, CO-H₂O feed was passed through the coconut shell based activated char bed (CC2; surface area 930 m²/g) which was maintained at temperature of 750 ± 10 °C. The experiments took place at various H₂O/CO ratios, starting from 2 to 10. The observation from the experiments were the gas composition of the dry gas at the outlet and the weight of remaining char. The consumption and generation of various species was calculated using the elemental balance and the dry gas composition of the product mixture. As R increased from 2 to 10, the partial pressure of H₂O increased from 0.67 to 0.91 bar, while that of CO decreased from 0.33 to 0.09 bar. Net flow rate of the reactant mixture was kept constant for all R to keep the residence time in the char bed same at 0.5 s. The height of the char bed was 100mm in all the cases.

5.1.4.1 Dry gas composition

The dry gas composition of the product mixture is plotted in Figure 5-13. With an increase in steam partial pressure of H₂O (H₂O/CO) the hydrogen concentration increases monotonically. The CO concentration decreases along with a decrease in CO₂. In case of only WGSR taking place, the CO₂

concentration increase should accompany the increase in hydrogen. However, in present case the CO_2 concentration decreases with increasing partial pressure of H_2O . This indicates that increase in H_2O partial pressure favoured steam-char reaction resulting in increase in hydrogen concentration, at the same time, the WGSR seems to be less favourable with an increase in partial pressure of steam. This observation can be attributed to steam-char reaction which generates CO and H_2 . Presence of H_2 can inhibit the WGSR while CO presence can decrease the effective $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{CO}$ ratio in the system which can act against the forward WGSR as evidenced by the concentration variation of CO_2 in Figure 5-13. This can be further analysed by looking at the rates of reactions in the following section.

Figure 5-13 Dry gas composition of the product mixture at various R for $\text{CO}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ feed on a char bed at 750 ± 10 °C

5.1.4.2 Consumption and generation rates

Table 5.7 presents the rates of generation or consumption for all the species. It can be seen that with an increase in R, from 2 to 10, the net rate of hydrogen generation remains unchanged after a decrease when R changes from 2 to 4. The rates of CO and CO₂ decrease as R increases. To understand the reactions taking place over the char bed, char consumption can be conveniently attributed to steam char reaction which would be taking place along with the homogeneous water gas shift reaction. Figure 5-14 presents the char consumption at all R at 750±10 °C.

Table 5.7 Consumption and generation rate for CO-H₂O feed at 750±10 °C

R	H ₂	CO ₂	CO(-)	H ₂ O(-)	C(-)
(H ₂ O/CO)	mmol/h-gchar				
2	40.3	32.9	25.1	40.8	8.1
4	35.5	25.2	14.6	35.9	10.9
6	33.5	21.6	9.3	33.8	12.4
8	34.1	19.7	5.5	33.9	14.1
10	35.8	19.2	2.7	35.7	16.4

Figure 5-14 Char consumption rate for CO-H₂O feed on char bed at 750±10 °C

Figure 5-15 Hydrogen contribution from WGS and C-H₂O reaction with CO-H₂O feed on char bed at 750±10 °C

Figure 5-15 presents hydrogen contribution from the two reactions taking place on the char bed. It is evident that rate of steam-char reaction increased with an increase in R while that of water gas shift reaction decreased from 32.1 to 19.4 mmol/h-gchar. The possible reasons for the rate of water gas shift reaction to decrease can be the steam char reaction taking place in parallel. Occurrence of steam-char reaction generates CO and H₂. CO generation can affect the H₂O/CO for the water gas shift reaction. Addition of CO in the system decreases the effective R for the water gas shift reaction. Also, steam char reaction decreases the H₂O fraction in the system, resulting in decreased partial pressure of H₂O. The decrease in partial pressure of H₂O is further caused by an additional gas mole of by steam char reaction. Although CO is on the reactant side of the water gas shift reaction, the water gas shift reaction is favourable at higher H₂O/CO, addition of more amount of H₂O affects the rate of forward reaction (Reddy & Smirniotis, 2015). Also, production of H₂ poses a strong inhibition effect to the water gas shift reaction as it falls on the product side of the reversible water gas shift reaction. Generation of CO and H₂ from steam char reaction retards the water gas shift reaction to proceed in the forward direction, as evident in the Figure 5-15. A recent study (Mohammed

N, 2023) has also shown that the hydrogen occupies active sites of carbon inhibiting other reactions on the char bed.

5.1.4.3 CO conversion

Table 5.8 and Figure 5-16 present the CO conversion data when CO-H₂O mixture was passed through the char bed at various R. It is evident that the overall CO conversion decreased with increasing R. The reason is clearly the char consumption reaction with steam. However, CO conversion by water gas shift reaction increased with an increase in R. The CO conversion by WGS at R=8 and R=10 is above 100%. CO conversion more than 100% implies that water gas shift reaction converted more CO than sent as reactant, in other words, the reaction also converted some of CO generated due to steam-char reaction. The maximum CO conversion by WGS of about 130% was calculated at R=10.

Table 5.8. CO conversion by WGS reaction

R	CO-in	CO consumption by WGS (mmol/h-gchar)	CO conversion by WGS %
2	55.2	32.1	58.2
4	33.1	24.6	74.3
6	24.5	21.2	86.2
8	18.6	20.0	107.2
10	15.0	19.4	129.6

Figure 5-16 CO conversion – overall and by WGS

5.2 Equilibrium studies for CO-H₂O feed at various R at 750±10 °C – with and without char bed

Figure 5-17 Dry gas composition at equilibrium for CO-H₂O feed on char bed at 750 °C at various R

Equilibrium composition for the reactant mixture containing CO and H₂O with abundance of condensed phase C can be computed to analyze the experimental results. Figure 5-17 presents the equilibrium composition of the gaseous product mixture on dry basis. Plot shows that the hydrogen concentration in dry gas increases from 40.5% to 48% by volume when R increases from 2 to 10. CO volume fraction decreases from about 50% to about 44%. The volume fraction of CO₂ can be seen only to be in small fraction, between 8.4 to 6.5%. Considering water gas shift reaction for the CO-H₂O feed, the H₂ and CO₂ volume fraction should be equal. In present case, the CO-H₂O mixture is subjected to equilibrium in presence of a char bed. Occurrence of char reactions with H₂O and CO₂ can't be ignored. The higher volume fraction of CO can be attributed to steam-char reaction while lower level of CO₂ explains the Boudouard reaction taking place. To bring this point starkly, Figure 5-18 presents the product gas composition on dry basis for CO-H₂O feed at various R without the char bed. It is clear to observe that water gas shift reaction has taken place and H₂ and CO₂ are at same volumetric fractions while CO level being low. The CO levels in case of char bed can be seen in the range of 43.9 to 49.9% while that in absence of char bed can be seen to be in range of 3.8 to 17.3%. In case of CO-H₂O feed on char bed, char heterogeneous reactions with H₂O and CO₂ generate CO resulting in higher molar levels.

Figure 5-18 Dry gas composition at equilibrium for CO-H₂O feed at 750 °C at various R (without the char bed)

Comparing the experimental results with the equilibrium results when CO-H₂O feed passes through the char bed, we see that experimental hydrogen composition is comparable to equilibrium composition. However, experimental CO volume % is much lower than equilibrium CO volume % while experimental CO₂ volume fraction is much higher than equilibrium CO₂ volume fraction. This observation is because of the heterogeneous Boudouard reaction achieving equilibrium. As a reactant system containing solid char and CO₂ is allowed to achieve equilibrium, some CO₂ converts to CO by reacting with C, depending on the temperature. Figure 5-19 shows the equilibrium composition of C-CO₂ system at different temperature. At equilibrium at 750 °C, we can see that less than 20% of initial concentration of CO₂ remains and more than 60% of the product mixture contains CO.

Figure 5-19 Equilibrium composition of C-CO₂ system

5.3 CO-H₂O-CO₂ mixture on the char bed

A gasification system involves a mixture of gaseous species containing CO, H₂O, CO₂, H₂ as the major reacting species that pass through the hot char bed. In oxy-steam mode of operation, the amount of H₂O in the system is higher leading to higher H₂O/CO as presented in Figure 5-2. Higher H₂O/CO prevailing in the gasification system should favour water gas shift reaction. The prediction of higher hydrogen yield due to water gas shift reaction is not straightforward as the system includes char bed and other reacting species. Other species present in the system can either promote or inhibit the water gas shift reaction due to other parallel reactions or just dilution effect. In order to study the impact of CO₂ dilution in the reactant mixture of CO-H₂O over the hot char bed at 750±10 °C at a constant R of 10, the experiments took place with CO₂ in CO-H₂O mixture at 1%, 5% and 10% by volume while maintaining the H₂O/CO at 10. The total flow rate of the reactant mixture was kept constant to keep the residence time same for all the experiments.

5.3.1 Dry gas composition

Dry gas composition for the CO-H₂O-CO₂ feed on char bed is presented in Figure 5-20. The CO₂ was added to the CO-H₂O feed at R = 10 which is made to pass through a hot char bed at 750±10 °C. Observing the dry gas composition of the product gas it is evident that hydrogen concentration in the product gas decreases as CO₂ fraction in the feed gas increases from 1 to 10% by volume. The CO₂ in dry product gas mixture increases while CO volume % increases marginally with an increase in CO₂ fraction in the feed.

Figure 5-20 Dry gas composition for CO-H₂O-CO₂ on char bed feed at R = 10

The composition observed can be compared with the equilibrium composition presented in Figure 5-21. As per equilibrium composition, the H₂ concentration in dry gas decreases with CO₂ addition, as observed experimentally. CO tends to increase marginally as CO₂ fraction increases in the feed. It can also be observed that CO₂ fraction in the product gas is much higher than in

equilibrium and CO fraction much lower than in equilibrium. This observation is due to C-CO₂ reaction achieving equilibrium while in practice C-CO₂ reaction does not proceed at the experimental temperature. It should be noted that effect of CO₂ dilution is not significant in case when the reactant mixture over char bed is allowed to achieve equilibrium.

Figure 5-21 Equilibrium composition of the dry gas with CO-CO₂-H₂O feed on char bed at $R = 10$

5.3.2 Consumption and generation rates

The rates data, presented in Table 5.9, show that addition of CO₂ decreases the rate of hydrogen generation. On comparing the results when there is no CO₂ in the feed, addition of 1% CO₂ causes the net hydrogen rate to decrease by about 33%. As CO₂ addition takes place from 1% to 10%, net hydrogen generation rate further decreases, however, the decrease in rate is only about 4% when CO₂ fraction increase from 5 to 10%. The char consumption rate decreases by 48% when addition of CO₂ takes place from 0 to 1%. Char consumption rate remains almost constant when CO₂ in the feed varies between 1% to 10%. Further, the rate of water gas shift and steam char reaction can be quantified by using char consumption rate being assigned to steam char reaction and total hydrogen

generation rate. The rates of hydrogen generation from the two reactions are presented in Figure 5-22.

Table 5.9 Rates of generation/consumption of the species with CO-H₂O-CO₂ feed on char bed at R = 10

CO ₂ % (in reactant mixture)	H ₂	CO ₂	CO(-)	H ₂ O(-)	C(-)
mmol/h-gchar					
0	35.8	19.2	2.7	35.7	16.4
1	24.1	15.7	7.3	24.2	8.5
5	19.4	10.9	4.2	20.4	8.5
10	18.7	11.3	3.9	18.8	7.5

Looking at the hydrogen generation rate from water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction it is clear that water gas shift reaction rate decreases till CO₂ in the feed is 5%, however, there is appreciable change in rate when CO₂ in feed increases from 5 to 10%. Likewise, for steam char reaction, the rate of reaction decreases by about 48% when CO₂ in the feed is increased from 0 to 1%. However, the rate of reaction remains almost constant when the CO₂ in feed is between 1 to 10%.

The decrease in water gas shift reaction can be explained by using Le Chatelier principle which dictates the equilibrium to shift towards the reactant side when CO₂ is added to the system. The decrease in steam char reaction on CO₂ addition can be attributed to the dilution effect of CO₂. Presence of CO₂ can interfere with the H₂O molecules to adsorb on the char surface hindering the reaction with solid C.

Figure 5-22 Rate of hydrogen generation from water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction for CO-CO₂-H₂O feed on char bed at R = 10

5.4 H₂O - producer gas feed on char bed

To further the understanding of effect of other diluents in the CO-H₂O mixture which in case of gasification are CO₂, H₂, N₂ and CH₄ (N₂ is present in the gasification system when it is carried out with air as the gasifying media), CO – producer gas mixture was passed through the hot char bed. The study intended to understand the behavior of water gas shift reaction and char reactions in presence of all the species that are usually observed in a gasification system.

The experiments took place with varying partial pressure of H₂O (0.29, 0.44, 0.54, 0.61 and 0.67 atm corresponding to R = 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10, respectively) at

the temperature of 730 ± 10 °C. The producer gas feed composition is presented in Figure 5-23.

Figure 5-23 Composition of the producer gas used as the feed with steam

5.4.1 Dry gas composition

The dry gas composition of the output gas for all the R – from 2 to 10, is presented in Figure 5-24. It is evident that H₂ concentration in the product gas increases as the R increases. With an increase in H₂, CO₂ concentration also increases while CO concentration decreases. CH₄ concentration can be seen to decrease with increasing H₂O in the system as R increases. Increase in H₂ and CO₂ shows that water gas shift reaction is promoted as R increases. Occurrence of shift reaction is accompanied with a decrease in CO as R increases, as presented in the Figure 5-24. Decrease in CH₄ with an increase in R can be explained by steam reforming reaction which is promoted with increasing partial pressure of steam.

Figure 5-24 Dry gas composition of the product mixture with PG-H₂O as the feed on char bed

5.4.2 Consumption and generation rates

The composition data presented above shows that water gas shift reaction is favoured when PG-H₂O mixture is passed through a hot char bed. However, char consumption was also recorded during the experiment. Char consumption due to steam-char reaction also generates CO and H₂. To understand the rates of the reaction the rates of consumption and generation of all the species are presented in Table 5.10.

Table 5.10 Consumption and generation rate for PG-H₂O feed at 730±10 °C

R	H ₂	CO ₂	CO (-)	H ₂ O (-)	C (-)
(H ₂ O/CO)	mmol/h-gchar				
2	5.2	3.8	2.0	5.6	2.0
4	5.9	4.4	2.2	6.6	2.6
6	9.9	6.2	2.0	10.4	4.7
8	12.1	7.2	2.0	12.4	5.4
10	15.1	8.2	1.4	15.0	6.7

It can be seen in Table 5.10 that char consumption rate increases with increasing R indicating increased rates of the steam-char reaction. On quantifying the water gas shift and steam-char reaction on the basis of rates of char consumption and hydrogen generation the hydrogen contribution from the two reactions can be plotted in Figure 5-25.

Figure 5-25 Hydrogen contribution from WGS and steam char reaction

The rates data show that H₂ generation rate increases with increasing R. The rates of the two reactions – water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction also increase. On comparing the rates of the two reactions it is evident that the rate of water gas shift reaction is more than that of steam char reaction and hence the contribution in hydrogen generation.

The rates of the reaction can be compared with the case when feed contained CO-H₂O. Comparing the Figure 5-15 and Figure 5-25 we observe that reaction rates are higher in case when reactant mixture is pure CO and steam. The higher rates in case of CO-H₂O feed are due to higher partial pressures of CO and H₂O than in case of PG-H₂O feed in addition to presence of CO₂, N₂, H₂

and CH₄ in PG as diluents. Researchers have also shown that presence of H₂ has a strong inhibiting effect on the steam char reaction (Barrio, et al., 2001).

It is also worth noticing that hydrogen generation rate by water gas shift reaction or the rate of water gas shift reaction shows an opposite trend in the two cases. In case of PG-H₂O as the feed it can be seen increasing with R while it is observed to decrease with R in case of CO-H₂O as the feed. In case of PG-H₂O, even though the rate of water gas shift reaction increases with R, the rates remain lower than that in case of CO-H₂O. It has been explained in the CO-H₂O section that the generation of CO by steam-char reaction affects the water gas shift reaction adversely as it decreases the effective R in the system, in addition to generating H₂ which can have a retarding effect on the reaction as it falls on the product side of the reaction, consequently decreasing the rate of water gas shift reaction. In case of PG-H₂O mixture as the feed, the rate of steam-char reaction is lower which leads to lower impact on the water gas shift reaction. The water gas shift reaction rate thus increases with R as partial pressure of H₂O increases.

Figure 5-26 Char consumption rate with R for PG-H₂O feed at 730±10 °C

Figure 5-27 CO conversion for H₂O-PG mixture feed on char bed

5.5 CO-H₂O mixture on inert bed

The CO-H₂O mixture was also made to pass through an inert bed to study the behaviour of water gas shift reaction at higher temperatures, in absence of any other reacting species like char, and to ascertain any catalytic behaviour of porous char towards the water gas shift reaction. The experiments were conducted at higher H₂O-to-CO ratio of 10 with temperature varying from 590 to 750 °C. The dry gas composition of the product mixture at each temperature is presented in the Figure 5-28. Figure 5-28 shows that the hydrogen concentration in the product gas increases with an increase in temperature. Corresponding increase in CO₂ concentration can also be seen, as per the water gas shift reaction stoichiometry. Experiment on an inert bed with CO-H₂O feed shows that at higher temperatures, in present case from 590 to 750 °C, the water gas shift reaction is favoured kinetically, in contrast to that dictated by thermodynamics. A comparison can be done with the case when CO-H₂O feed is sent through a bed of hot char at similar temperature and R for char's catalytic activity by looking at the reaction rates. The rates of generation and consumption of different species is presented in Table 5.11.

Figure 5-28 Dry gas composition on inert bed with CO-H₂O feed at R10

Table 5.11 Generation and consumption rates for the CO-H₂O feed at R10 on an inert bed

T	H ₂	CO ₂	CO	H ₂ O
°C	mmol/min			
588±8	1.0	0.9	0.8	0.9
637±10	2.8	2.5	2.4	2.6
699±9	5.5	4.8	4.5	5.0
744±9	5.2	4.6	4.3	4.8

The rate of water gas shift reaction in case of CO-H₂O feed at R = 10 over hot char bed is presented in Figure 5-15. However, the rates reported in case of char as the bed material are in the units of *mmol/h-gchar*. To compare this with the rate in case of inert bed, the rate can be represented as *mmol/min*. CO-H₂O feed at R = 10 over char bed shows the water gas shift reaction rate as 32.3 mmol/min at 750±10 °C while with the same feed at R = 10 over an inert bed the rate of water gas shift reaction was observed to be somewhere between 4.3

mmol/min and 5.2 mmol/min. The rate and CO conversion by water gas shift reaction for the two cases at $R = 10$ are presented in Table 5.12.

Table 5.12 WGS rate and CO conversion for CO-H₂O feed at R10 over char and inert bed

Bed material	Rate of water gas shift reaction (mmol/min)	CO conversion by water gas shift reaction (%)
Char	32.3	129.6
Inert	4.3-5.3	17.1

Figure 5-29 CO conversion when CO-H₂O feed at R10 is passed through an inert bed

On comparing the water gas shift reaction over a char bed and an inert bed, it's evident that the presence of char bed promotes the reaction. The rate of reaction in case of char bed is 6 to 7.5 times that in case of an inert bed. CO conversion due to water gas shift reaction in case of char bed was computed to be about 130% while that in the case of inert bed is about 17.1%. In case of char bed, a part of additional CO generated in the system due to occurrence of steam-char reaction also gets converted by the water gas shift reaction. Increased rate of reaction and higher CO conversion due to water gas shift

reaction show that the porous char acts as a catalyst for the water gas shift reaction.

From the experiments with inert bed for CO-H₂O feed at R10, we can establish two points:

1. Water gas shift reaction is kinetically favored at higher temperatures resulting in higher reaction rates.
2. The char bed has a catalytic effect on the water gas shift reaction.

5.6 CO-H₂O feed on demineralized (DM) water washed char bed

The literature shows that by washing with demineralized water, potassium, chlorine, and sulfur can be effectively removed (Suzuki, Nakajima, & Ikenag, 2011). To further the understanding of the effects of the minerals and inorganic materials, the activated char (CC2) was washed with the DM water and used as the bed material. The experiments were conducted at R = 2 and R10. The composition of the dry product gas mixture is presented in Figure 5-30.

Figure 5-30 Composition of the dry product gas mixture for CO-H₂O feed over DM water washed char bed

In case of DM washed char bed also, the increasing trend for the H_2 with increasing R in product gas mixture can be seen as in the case of unwashed char bed (see Figure 5-13). The increasing volume fraction of H_2 when R increases from 2 to 10 is due to increased rate of steam-char reaction as a result of increased partial pressure of steam in the reactant mixture.

Table 5.13 presents the rates of production and consumption for all the species. The rates data show that total hydrogen generation rate decreases when R increases from 2 to 10, as observed in the case of as received activated char bed (Table 5.7).

Table 5.13 Rates of consumption and generation of species for CO- H_2O feed at R10 over DM washed char bed

R	H_2	CO_2	CO	H_2O	C
mmol/h-gchar					
2	31.1	26.9	22.8	31.0	4.1
10	21.3	12.8	4.0	21.7	9.1

Figure 5-31 Rate of hydrogen generation from water gas shift reaction and steam char reaction for CO- H_2O mixture on DM washed char bed

Figure 5-32 Dry gas composition comparison at $R = 2$ for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on different bed materials

Figure 5-33 Dry gas composition comparison at $R = 10$ for $\text{CO-H}_2\text{O}$ feed on different bed materials

Further, we can compare the composition and the rates data for different bed materials to bring out the catalytic effects of char bed. Figure 5-32 and Figure 5-33 present the composition of the dry product gas mixture for the three different bed materials – as received activated charcoal (AC1), demineralized water washed activated charcoal (AC2) and inert bed (IB).

The trend is evident that the activated charcoal (as received) showed the maximum activity towards the hydrogen composition in the yield gas while the activity of same sample after washing with the demineralized water decreased. Washing with demineralized water removes water soluble minerals and their compounds which can result into decrease in catalytic activity of the char bed as evident in Figure 5-32 & Figure 5-33.

Figure 5-34 Comparison of rates of WGS and steam-char reactions at $R = 2$ and $R10$ for different bed materials

Further, Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis of the char samples used as the bed material can be used to understand the difference in catalytic behavior. The EDS results of the two samples – coconut shell based activated char, as received (unwashed) and DM water washed are presented in the table below.

Table 5.14 presents the elemental composition from the EDS analysis. It is evident that potassium from the char is removed on washing with the demineralized water. The presence of potassium shows a favorable effect on the progress of WGSR and steam char reaction as evident from the rates observed and the composition. On washing the char, the rates of WGSR and steam-char reaction decreased by 37% and 45%, respectively, as shown in Figure 5-34

Table 5.14. EDS results of washed and unwashed char ash

Weight%	AC1	AC2	IB
O	43.2	54.5	59.1
Na	2.1	4.1	-
Mg	1.9	2.3	13.6
Al	-	1.4	2.7
Si	2.9	4.3	22.8
P	1.4	0.6	-
K	45.1	29.0	0.4
Ca	-	3.3	1.2
Fe	-	-	-
S	3.4	0.4	-

Summary

Chapter 5 presents the results of experiments done on the biomass based hot char bed to understand its catalytic effects on water gas shift reaction. The reduction zone of a gasification reactor was simulated on a bench scale experimental setup. The first part of the study focused on understanding the temperature effect on water gas shift reaction over the activated charcoal bed. Results showed that temperature favoured the WGS reaction when H₂O to CO

ratio (R) was 2 and temperature increased from 520 to 760 C. The water gas shift reaction is thermodynamically favoured at lower temperatures; however, the kinetics is favoured when temperatures increase. The experiments with 2 char samples also showed that as temperature increased, the char consumption due to steam char reaction also contributes to H₂ enrichment, though, different char samples showed the different rates and the temperatures at which the reaction kicks off. Results concluded that biomass char bed showed catalytic activity towards the water gas shift reaction, which was found to be due to potassium and calcium. The effect of R was also captured in results at a constant temperature of 750 °C. In the presence of char bed, with increasing R, WGS reaction was found to decrease marginally while steam char reaction rate increased. The decrease in WGS reaction rate could be attributed to steam char reaction in parallel contributing to generation of H₂ and CO which could inhibit the WGS reaction. Overall, hydrogen generation rate decreased from R = 2 to R = 6 and increased marginally from R = 6 to R = 10.

Experimental results with producer gas and H₂O mixture were also discussed and compared with those with CO and H₂O mixture. It was seen that the WGS reaction rate in the case of producer gas and steam mixture increased with R, attributable to lower steam-char reaction rate. The chapter also presented results from inert bed experiments and experiments with washed char to bring out the catalytic effect of char bed.

Chapter 6 – Oxy-steam gasification experiments with higher injection temperature ($> 550\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

This chapter explores the performance of oxy-steam gasification system at higher injection temperatures at various SBR. Three kinds of biomass were used for the experiments: casuarina wood chips, coconut shells and corncob. The SBR and temperature ranges for the three kinds of biomass is presented below.

Casuarina: SBR: 1.5 – 3.7, Injection temp.: 610 – 750 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, ER: 0.24 – 0.33

Coconut shells: SBR: 1.3 – 3, Injection temp.: 550 – 640 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, ER: 0.27 – 0.40

Corn cob: SBR: 1.7 – 2.3, Injection temp.: 610 – 690 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, ER: 0.21 – 0.30

The variation of exit gas composition and performance parameters like hydrogen yield and efficiency are analysed and compared with the lower injection temperature data in this chapter.

6.1 Dry gas composition

Figure 6-1 presents the dry gas composition data for all the experiments conducted, for all kinds of biomass. For comparison, the low injection temperature data points have been presented with transparent markers. The data shows that experiments with higher injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture resulted in higher concentration of hydrogen and lower concentration of CO. The plot shows that increase in hydrogen concentration is more than that in CO₂, suggesting a combination of heterogeneous chemical reactions of C with H₂O and CO₂ taking place along with water gas shift reaction. Further, discussion on composition for each species is presented in the following subsections.

Figure 6-1 Dry gas composition for casuarina wood chips, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperature (transparent datapoints correspond to low injection temperature experiments)

6.1.1 Hydrogen

The variation in hydrogen concentration across all steam-to-biomass ratios (SBRs) in the present study demonstrates that temperature has a positive effect on the hydrogen concentration in the product gas mixture. The maximum hydrogen volume fraction in the product gas mixture is observed to be 56.6% at an SBR of 3.1 ($R = 3.9$) and equivalence ratio (ER) of 0.32 with a higher oxy-steam injection temperature of 750°C. In comparison, with a lower oxy-steam injection temperature of 400°C, the maximum hydrogen volume fraction is 49.5% at an SBR of 3.6 ($H_2O/CO = 3.8$) and an ER of 0.34. The injection temperatures in the two cases were 750°C and 400°C, respectively. The difference of 350°C in injection temperature results in hydrogen enrichment by approximately 14% in the product syngas. This phenomenon can be attributed to the enhanced steam char reaction occurring in the char bed, alongside the water gas shift reaction. An independent experimental study of the $CO + H_2O$ reaction on the char bed revealed that at temperatures exceeding 700°C, the

hydrogen generation rate increases steeply, indicating the onset of the steam-char reaction. Moreover, the increase in oxy-steam injection temperature also led to an elevation in the average bed temperature in the reactor, rising from 670°C to 700°C when the injection temperature changed from 400°C to 750°C. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that a higher concentration of H₂ could be achieved at lower steam-to-biomass ratios with the advent of increased injection temperature of the oxy-steam mixture.

Figure 6-2 Hydrogen in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

6.1.2 Carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide

Figure 6-3 & Figure 6-4 show the variation in concentration of CO and CO₂ with SBR. With an increase in SBR, CO concentration in product syngas mixture follows a decreasing trend in both ranges of oxy-steam injection temperature. On comparing the lower and higher injection temperature data points it is evident that CO concentration in case of casuarina wood chips for higher injection temperature is lower. It should be noted that the oxy-steam injection temperature for casuarina wood chips is in the range 610 – 750 °C, the highest temperatures among other biomass types – coconut shells (550 – 640

°C) and corncob (610 to 690 °C), and CO concentration was lowest at the highest temperature of injection. The higher temperature of injection resulted in lower concentration of CO, indicating CO reforming taking place at higher injection temperatures. The increased CO reforming suggests the progress of water gas shift reaction. The WGSR can be favoured kinetically at high temperatures, though it's favoured thermodynamically at lower temperatures. CO₂ concentration on the other hand does not show corresponding increase. Occurrence of water gas shift reaction should also result in increase in concentration of CO₂. In present study, higher injection temperature favours CO conversion, however, corresponding CO₂ concentration increase is not apparent.

Figure 6-3 Carbon monoxide in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

The CO₂ concentration at higher temperature of injection is observed to be lower than that at lower injection temperature. Although decrease in CO concentration at higher injection temperature suggests occurrence of WGSR, the process involves simultaneous progress of several reactions including steam-char reaction and Boudouard reaction.

Figure 6-4 Carbon dioxide in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

6.1.3 Methane

Figure 6-5 presents the methane concentration in dry gas composition of the syngas from oxy-steam gasification at higher injection temperatures. The plot also presents data points with respect to lower injection temperatures for convenient comparison. It is evident that the methane concentration decreases marginally with an increase in SBR in both the cases of temperature ranges. A higher concentration of steam in the system at higher SBRs can favor methane reforming to yield CO and H₂. However, it must also be noted that the system already is inundated with large amounts of H₂ which can have an adverse effect on the progress of the steam-reforming reaction. H₂ in the system varies in the range of 18-29% in case of high injection temperatures while that in case of lower injection temperatures remains between 16 and 34%. It appears that the influence of higher steam concentrations resulting from elevated steam-to-biomass ratios (SBRs) has a minimal impact on methane concentrations. However, the effect of injection temperature on methane concentration becomes noticeable in cases of high SBR. At lower SBRs, the methane concentration remains consistent regardless of the injection temperature. Elevated

temperatures seem to facilitate the reforming reaction of methane, leading to reduced concentrations. This reforming reaction of methane is inherently endothermic and is thermodynamically favorable at higher temperatures. Moreover, higher temperatures can also enhance the kinetics of the reforming reaction. However, at lower SBRs (<2), the temperature effect appears insignificant due to the higher concentration of H_2 impeding the progress of methane reforming reaction. Conversely, in the case of higher SBRs, the kinetics are supported by the higher concentration of steam, favoring the steam methane reforming reaction in the forward direction and resulting in lower methane concentrations in the product gas. Given that methane is present in the lowest concentration (up to 4.5% in dry gas and 2.7% in hot gas) among all other constituents, the reforming of methane contributes insignificant amounts of H_2 , rendering it irrelevant in discussions regarding H_2 enrichment.

Figure 6-5 Methane in dry gas - casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

6.1.4 Composition vs. injection temperature

Figure 6-6 and Figure 6-7 present the variation of composition with the injection temperature. To bring out the temperature effect, the composition variation has been plotted in the Figure 6-6 at an SBR of 2.4. The hydrogen volume

fraction in the dry gas increases with an increase in injection temperature and correspondingly CO component in dry gas decreases. When the injection temperature increases from 445 C to 730 C at SBR of 2.4 and hydrogen fraction in the dry gas increases by about 16% while CO decreases by about 30%. However, the CO₂ fraction remains at similar levels with no significant change in composition. Increase in temperature is kinetically favorable to water-gas shift reaction, as evidenced in current discussion, decrease in CO, and increase in H₂. However, the corresponding increase in CO₂ is not observed. Consistent levels of CO₂ can be attributed to the Boudouard reaction taking place in parallel which is highly endothermic and shows progress in the temperatures above 700 C only. The occurrence of Boudouard reaction consumes CO₂ via char gasification reaction generating CO which further is consumed by water gas shift reaction. The final composition is the result of complex interplay of several chemical reactions taking place in the gasification system, both homogeneous and heterogeneous. An increased temperature of injection at SBR 2.4 also shows that it helped reduce the CH₄ levels as steam-methane reforming being an endothermic reaction is promoted at higher temperatures.

Figure 6-6 Effect of injection temperature on composition at SBR 2.4

Figure 6-7 presents the consolidated data points across a range of SBRs to observe the injection temperature effect at several SBR ranges. It can be inferred that an injection temperature of more than 700 °C helps improve the hydrogen concentration significantly. Corresponding, CO composition is also lower. As observed earlier, CO₂ composition remains moreover at similar levels, however, it shows a decreasing trend when observed across a large injection temperature range for various SBRs, as also observed in Figure 6-4.

Figure 6-7 Effect of injection temperature on gas composition at SBR 1.4, 2.3, 3.1 and 3.6

6.2 Hydrogen yield

Figure 6-8 illustrates the hydrogen yield in grams per kilogram of biomass consumed during the study. The yield ranged from 61.4 g/kg-biomass to 109.7 g/kg-biomass. The highest yield was achieved at an SBR of 2.4 (ER of 0.28) with an injection temperature of 734°C when using casuarina wood chips as the feedstock. At an SBR of 3.1 and an injection temperature of 750°C, the maximum injection temperature tested, a hydrogen yield of 94 g/kg-biomass was obtained, with an ER of 0.32.

Figure 6-8 Hydrogen yield for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

It's notable that the increase in SBR alone doesn't significantly affect the hydrogen yield; the prevailing ER also plays a crucial role in controlling the hydrogen yield in the gasification process. A higher ER facilitates a larger quantity of oxidizer in the system, which consequently consumes fuel gases, including hydrogen, resulting in a lower hydrogen yield in the product gas mixture. The temperature effect is clearly discernible from the plot. Data points corresponding to the injection temperature range of 610 - 750°C, the highest among all other types of biomass used in the study, demonstrate the highest hydrogen yield compared to others.

Figure 6-9 presents the hydrogen yield variation with respect to injection temperature where each data point represents a range of SBR. The plot shows that higher injection temperature has resulted in higher hydrogen yield, at all levels of SBR. The temperature increase favours progress of reactions which contribute to hydrogen enrichment. Water gas shift reaction is an important reaction in a gasification system responsible for hydrogen addition, which being mildly exothermic (41 kJ/mol) reaction is favoured kinetically at higher temperatures. Steam-char reaction also plays a role in hydrogen addition into the system. An injection temperature of above 700 °C has been proven to be

favourable to steam-char reaction as well, as concluded in chapter 5 and evidenced in terms of hydrogen yield in present discussion.

Figure 6-9 Hydrogen yield vs injection temperature at SBR 1.4, 2.3, 3.1 and 3.6

6.3 Gas yield

The gas yield is quantified as the mass of syngas generated on dry basis per kg of dry biomass consumed. Figure 6-10 presents the gas yield for all the biomass types in all ranges of injection temperature. The average gas yield was about 1.8 kg/kg. However, the effect of temperature on gas yield is not significant in present study. The high temperature data points overlap the points with respect to lower temperature of injection. Assimilating the data at all temperatures, Figure 6-11 presents the variation with SBR; the plot shows an increasing trend with SBR, however, marginally.

Figure 6-10 Syngas yield for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

Figure 6-11 Gas yield vs SBR at all injection temperatures

Figure 6-12 Gas yield vs injection temperature at SBR 2.4

6.4 Gasification efficiency

Figure 6-13 Cold/dry gas efficiency for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

The gasification efficiency demonstrates an anticipated decrease with an increase in SBR, which can be attributed to the higher energy input required for generating steam at higher SBR. Figure 6-13 aims to illustrate the temperature effect on the overall gasification efficiency. From the plot, it can

be inferred that both high and low temperatures of oxy-steam injection exhibit similar performance in terms of overall efficiency. However, it's noteworthy that at an SBR of approximately 2.4 for casuarina, the efficiency of the gasification process increases from about 60% to 70% as the injection temperature rises from 630°C to 730°C. In contrast, at an SBR of 2.8, the efficiency decreases from 68% to 63% with an increase in injection temperature from 620°C to 710°C. This observation underscores the significance of an important parameter in the gasification process: the equivalence ratio. The equivalence ratio dictates the efficiency of the process due to the resulting gas composition. A higher ER leads to a higher CO₂ concentration in the product gas, decreasing its calorific value and consequently reducing the overall efficiency of the gasification process.

Figure 6-14 ER vs CO₂ in dry product gas

Figure 6-14 presents the concentration of CO₂ with respect to varying ER, for higher and lower temperature of injection. The plot clearly shows that with an increase in ER, CO₂ in product gas increases. The temperature effect can also be inferred from the plot. Higher temperature of injection (>550 °C) has resulted in comparatively lower concentrations of CO₂ suggesting gasification reaction of char (C) with CO₂ via Boudouard reaction.

Figure 6-15 presents the overall efficiency variation with the oxy-steam injection temperature for all the SBRs. The plot also captures the effects of SBR, different colors of the markers correspond to different SBR. The efficiency decreases with increasing SBR. However, the temperature effect is not clearly discernable. The efficiency at SBR of 2.3 ± 0.1 (ER 0.29) is 68% when the injection temperature is 730 °C while the same at an SBR of 3.1 ± 0.1 (ER 0.32) is 52% when injection temperature is 750 °C. At SBR of 2.3 ± 0.1 , when the injection temperature increases from 400 °C to 730 °C, the corresponding efficiencies are 65 % and 68%, respectively, ER being the same (0.30 and 0.29). It is clear that, temperature effect in overall efficiency gets shadowed by the effect of SBR on it.

Figure 6-15 Efficiency vs injection temperature of oxy-steam mixture

Figure 6-16 presents the percentage of contributions of energy input from biomass and steam, for all the biomass and SBR. As expected, the contribution of input energy from steam increases with an increase in SBR. The high and low injection temperature data points clearly show the impact of increased oxy-steam injection temperature on energy input. The contribution of steam in energy input increased from $\sim 24\%$ to $\sim 34\%$ when oxy-steam temperature increased from 645 °C to 730 °C at SBR of 2.4. The high temperature steam

contributed from $\sim 14\%$ to $\sim 42\%$ in the total energy input when SBR increased from 1.3 to 4.7.

Figure 6-16 Contribution of biomass and steam in input energy efficiency for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

6.5 Hydrogen efficiency

Figure 6-17 presents the further analysis on the efficiency of the gasification process in terms of hydrogen efficiency. To understand the effect of injection temperature on it, low injection temperature data points have also been presented along with the high injection temperature data points. Average H_2 efficiency at higher injection temperature was close to 39% while at that at lower injection temperatures was approximately 36%. To bring out the temperature effect, we can focus on three data points at the SBR of 2.4, corresponding to casuarina wood chips. At the injection temperature of 730 C, the efficiencies are 44.9% and 47.8% at similar ER of 0.30 and 0.28, respectively, while the same for an injection temperature of 630 C is 37.6% at an ER of 0.32. We can infer that at SBR of 2.4 and an ER of ~ 0.30 , an increase in injection temperature of ~ 100 °C has resulted in hydrogen efficiency increase of about 7-10%. We observe a similar trend at SBR of 1.7, 2.1, 2.3, 2.8, 3.1, 3.6 and 3.7. The temperature increase can be understood to have resulted in increased

chemical kinetics in the system favoring increased hydrogen yield. Increase in injection temperature can affect the endothermic char-steam reaction to yield H_2 and CO , resulting in higher hydrogen efficiency. With SBR, we find that H_2 efficiency decreases at higher SBR; at $SBR < 2.5$, the average efficiency was 38.1% while at $SBR > 2.5$ the average drops to 36.1%.

Figure 6-17 Hydrogen efficiency higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

6.6 H_2O conversion

Figure 6-18 H_2O conversion at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

As discussed in section 4.5 H₂O conversion, H₂O conversion % measures the overall utilization of H₂O content in the process of gasification for H₂ generation in the product end. From the Figure 6-18, injection temperature increase is not apparently favorable on the conversion percentage. At an SBR of 1.3, the conversion percentage drops from 49.4% (ER 0.25) and 36.5% (ER 0.26) to 5.3% (ER 0.30) as the injection temperature increases from 401°C and 463°C to 605°C, respectively. This could be attributed to the higher ER (0.30 vs 0.25 or 0.26), leading to further consumption of generated hydrogen in the system and resulting in H₂O on the product side. However, at an SBR of 2.4, the temperature increase is favorable to H₂O conversion. The conversion percentage of 12.2% (ER 0.31) at an injection temperature of 630°C increases to 18.3% (ER 0.30) and 19.2% (ER 0.28) at an injection temperature of 730°C. A 100°C increase in injection temperature at an SBR of 2.4 results in a significant increase in the H₂O conversion percentage by over 50%, with ER being on similar levels.

Figure 6-19 H₂ in the system by H₂O conversion for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

H₂O converted during the gasification process appears as hydrogen on the product side through the water gas shift and steam-char reactions.

6.7 Equivalence ratio

Figure 6-20 ER for for casuarina, coconut shells and corncob at higher injection temperatures (>550 °C)

In the Figure 6-20, we observe that with an increasing SBR, ER shows an increasing trend. It should be noted that as SBR increases the endothermicity inside the reactor increases due to higher amounts of H_2O . This tends to decrease the average temperatures inside the reactor which is unfavorable for important gasification reactions of char (C) with H_2O and CO_2 . To maintain a conducive temperature during the gasification process, an optimized amount of oxidizer is important which consumes just the right amount of combustible to make the process self-sustained without compromising on the product gas quality with respect to composition of combustibles like H_2 and CO . In present observation, it's evident that an increase in the SBR requires ER to be maintained higher in order to maintain the prevailing temperatures inside the gasification system. A higher injection temperature has not affected the ER required for stable operation significantly. The average ER at injection temperatures of above 550 C was 0.32 while that for temperatures below 550 C was 0.33. At an SBR of 2.4, to maintain the bed temperatures at similar levels, for casuarina wood chips, the ER decreased from 0.31 to 0.29 when the injection temperature increased from 630 to 730 C.

6.8 Gasifier bed temperature

A typical bed temperature profile is presented in Figure 6-21 for a gasification system run with coconut shells as the biomass feed. The presented plot corresponds to bed temperature at various levels in the gasifier i.e., at 100mm, 200mm, 300mm, 400mm and 500 mm from the bottom of the reactor (refer Figure 3-2). Figure 6-21 corresponds to an experiment which was stably carried out for about 24 hours. The average bed temperature (100mm – 500mm level) is 650 °C while the injection of oxy-steam took place at 400 °C at SBR of 2.2 and ER of 0.31.

Figure 6-21 Bed temperature profile – SBR 2.2, ER 0.31 and injection temperature 400 C

The temperature profile followed a similar pattern in all stable runs. At higher injection temperatures, average bed temperatures were higher. For example, at injection temperature of 610 °C, average bed temperature was recorded to be 717 °C at an SBR of 1.8 and ER of 0.33 for the case when coconut shells were used as the biomass. Similarly, the average bed temperature corresponding to injection temperature of 734 °C was 716 °C at an SBR of 2.4 and ER 0.28 for casuarina wood chips as the biomass feed.

Summary

This chapter brought out the effects of higher injection temperature (550 to 750 °C), after studying the catalytic effects of hot char bed on important gasification reaction in chapter 5. It was shown that hydrogen concentration could increase with increased oxy-steam temperature, with maximum concentration of 56.6% at SBR of 3.1 and ER of 0.32. The maximum hydrogen yield was 109.7 g at injection temperature of 734 °C at SBR of 2.4; however, the temperature effect was observed to be significant on the gas yield in present study, with an average yield of 1.7 kg/kg at a higher injection temperature. The chapter also presented the results and discussed the important performance indicators such as overall and hydrogen efficiency, and H₂O conversion.

Chapter 7 - Equilibrium studies and exergy analysis of gasification process on oxy-steam mode

This chapter presents the equilibrium and exergy analyses of biomass gasification with oxy-steam mixture as the gasifying agent.

7.1 Equilibrium studies

Equilibrium analyses have been done to compare the experimental results with the theoretical limits as dictated by thermodynamics. As literature (Reed & Das, 1988) says that downdraft gasification systems reach near equilibrium composition at the outlet, this chapter explores the limitation posed by thermodynamics when oxy-steam mixture is used as the oxidizing media. The analysis requires the input components, designated temperature, and pressure to obtain the equilibrium composition. The equilibrium studies have been performed using NASA Chemical Equilibrium and Applications (CEA) program (McBride, 1996). NASA CEA program calculates the equilibrium composition for given reactant mixture, temperature, and pressure (problem type – tp , assigned temperature and pressure).

Present work employs a fixed reactor operating at near ambient pressure. To calculate the equilibrium composition, the gasification system has been assumed to be an isothermal reactor. The calculation requires the input chemical species: biomass (chemical formula, CH_xO_y), oxygen and steam, with the quantity, along with the prevailing temperature in the reactor – average bed temperature. NASA CEA program calculates the equilibrium composition by minimizing the Gibbs free energy of the system containing all possible chemical species on the product side. A detailed discussion on the Gibbs free minimization for calculating the equilibrium composition is presented in the following section.

7.1.1 Equilibrium calculation by Gibbs free energy minimization

Thermodynamic equilibrium is the state where the concentration of reactant and product species do not change with time. There are two ways to calculate

equilibrium composition for given system of chemical species – Gibbs free energy minimization and stoichiometric method.

Gibbs energy minimization is mostly useful in cases dealing with a system of large number of reactions as this method doesn't need any reaction mechanism to be known. This method is based on independent system components whose chemical potentials give a phase-independent values of the chemical potentials of the reactants and products at equilibrium (Koukkari & Pajarre, 2011). Each chemical species is treated independently without specifying a set of reactions a priori. This method applies elemental amounts of system components as conservation constraints in the form of a stoichiometric conservation matrix. The minimization of Gibbs energy is solved by using the Lagrange method with mass balance constraints of independent components as the subsidiary conditions. Temperature, pressure and amount of matter are chosen as the independent variables and equilibrium chemical potentials of the constituents are obtained as a linear combination of component specific contributions.

NASA CEA program uses Gibbs energy minimization formulation to obtain the equilibrium composition. To obtain the equilibrium composition of the gasification product, 'tp' (assigned temperature and pressure) option was chosen as the problem type. For the current study, oxygen and steam could be selected from reactants library available in the program. Biomass as a reactant required exploded chemical formula (CH_xO_y) as the input for defining the reactant not in program's library.

Stoichiometric method for equilibrium composition considers chemical reactions and the species involved. The chemical composition at equilibrium is calculated using the species mass balance and equilibrium constants of the reactions considered. This method requires selection of important chemical reactions which can represent the overall gasification process.

Figure 7-1 presents the average bed temperature across all the SBRs of present study. The average of average bed temperature is ~ 691 °C, however, the maximum temperature in the vicinity of oxidation zone (near the oxy-steam injection point) can go as high as 900 °C, even higher in some cases.

7.1.2 Gas composition

This section presents the experimental composition of dry synthesis gas and compares the same with the calculated equilibrium dry gas composition to discuss the process and its proximity with the thermodynamic equilibrium, across the SBR range of present study. The temperatures considered for the equilibrium composition calculation are on the basis of temperature profile and average bed temperatures prevailing in the reactor.

Figure 7-1 Average bed temperature and ER variation across the SBR

7.1.2.1 Hydrogen

On comparing the equilibrium volumetric composition of hydrogen in dry with those in experiments, as presented in Figure 7-2, it is evident that lower temperature favors higher hydrogen by volume, as dictated by thermodynamics. Water gas shift reaction being a major contributor of hydrogen during gasification is thermodynamically favorable at lower temperatures. On looking at the experimental observations we can say that hydrogen volume fraction approaches equilibrium. It is also evident that the equilibrium hydrogen fraction in dry gas increases initially at a higher rate and goes on to stagnate at higher SBRs, at all SBRs of study, also observed from experimental values. Equilibrium Hydrogen concentration in dry gas increases by about 8%, 4% and

2% when SBR increased from 1 to 2, 2 to 3 and 3 to 4, respectively – at temperatures 800 °C and 900 °C. The observation indicates that with increasing temperature the increase in hydrogen when SBR increases remains same with insignificant change in increase percentage. It should be noted that all the equilibrium numbers correspond to a constant ER of 0.3, which also is the average ER of present experimental studies.

Figure 7-2 Equilibrium and experimental composition of hydrogen in dry syngas

7.1.2.2 CO and CO₂

Figure 7-3 and Figure 7-4 present the equilibrium composition of CO and CO₂ and compare the same with the experimental observations of present work. The CO equilibrium composition consistently decreases with an increase in SBR, at all temperatures. High SBR corresponds to higher H₂O/CO ratio in the system which favors CO conversion through water gas shift reaction, following Le Chatelier’s principle at thermodynamic equilibrium. It is also evident that lower temperature corresponds to lower concentrations of CO at all SBRs indicating higher CO conversion at lower temperatures. This observation is in accordance with that in the case of hydrogen composition. Experimental numbers show that the oxy-steam gasification as a process achieves or approaches equilibrium. Similar conclusion can also be drawn from CO₂ composition, as presented in

Figure 7-4. It should be noted that gasification system involves solid char in the system, which at equilibrium gasifies completely into CO. However, heterogeneous reactions have limitations in attaining equilibrium in practical systems. The same can be observed in Figure 7-4, CO₂ compositions recorded in experimental studies are higher than at equilibrium.

Figure 7-3 Equilibrium and observed CO composition in dry syngas

Figure 7-4 Equilibrium and observed CO₂ composition in dry syngas

7.1.2.3 Hydrogen yield

Figure 7-5 presents and compares the hydrogen yield in g per kg of biomass consumed, as calculated at equilibrium with that obtained experimentally. As observed from concentrations plot, equilibrium studies suggest higher hydrogen yield at lower temperature. At thermodynamic equilibrium, hydrogen yield at an SBR of 2.4 was 102.3, 96.9 and 92.1 g/kg-biomass when the equilibrium temperature was 700, 800 and 900 °C, respectively. Experiments' yield was observed to be ~110 g/kg-biomass at the SBR of 2.4 and ER of 0.28 when the oxy-steam injection temperature was 734 °C and the average bed temperature was 716 °C. On an average, the experimental hydrogen yield at an SBR of 2.4 was 93.4 ± 15 g/kg-biomass when injection temperature varied from 650 °C to 730 °C. The equilibrium studies show that temperature and SBR have opposite effects on hydrogen output from biomass gasification. Also, the increase in yield is only marginal with respect to SBR increase after a certain point. At equilibrium temperature of 800 °C, increasing the SBR from 2.8 to 3.8 increased the hydrogen yield by about only 5%, from 100 g/kg-biomass to 105 g/kg-biomass.

Figure 7-5 Hydrogen yield comparison between experimental and equilibrium

The equilibrium studies presented in this chapter show that while increasing SBR can favour higher hydrogen in oxy-steam gasification product mixture, temperature increase does not result in higher hydrogen. The thermodynamics favours hydrogen at lower temperatures; however, it should be noted that thermodynamics doesn't take into account the kinetics of the chemical reactions. In gasification process, water gas shift reaction is the major contributor of hydrogen in the output gas mixture, also evidenced in the present study. Water gas shift reaction is kinetically favoured at high temperatures as opposed to that dictated by thermodynamics as the reaction is mildly exothermic.

7.2 Exergy analysis

Exergy analysis serves as a valuable tool for assessing the efficiency of energy conversion processes or systems by considering the maximum work obtainable during equilibrium with the environment, known as exergy. This analysis takes into account thermodynamic irreversibilities, which result in energy degradation. In the context of the present study, solid biomass undergoes thermochemical conversion in a fixed bed downdraft reactor to produce synthesis gas. The gasification process occurs within the reactor, while subsequent cooling and cleaning stages remove sensible heat and moisture from the product gas mixture. These stages alter the quality of energy, highlighting the importance of exergy analysis to identify where energy degradation occurs. By pinpointing these areas, the process can be optimized by maintaining appropriate input parameters to minimize energy quality degradation. In addition to the gasification process, exergy destruction also occurs during steam generation, which utilizes electrical energy with 100% exergy. Unlike thermal energy, which consists of both exergy and anergy (energy not transformed into useful work), electrical energy presents a unique challenge in terms of exergy loss. Furthermore, the oxy-steam gasification process necessitates the supply of pure oxygen, obtained commercially in liquid form through cryogenic separation, which adds to the exergy input. The exergy analysis conducted in this chapter encompasses all these inputs, including biomass (chemical energy), steam (electrical input), oxygen (cryogenic separation energy input), and

auxiliary components for the cooling and cleaning system (electrical input). The main focus of this chapter is to investigate the impact of oxy-steam injection temperature on various losses during syngas generation and overall exergy efficiency.

7.2.1 Thermochemical conversion

Thermochemical conversion causes exergy destruction. The chemical energy bound in biomass is released into gases phase when biomass is subjected to high temperatures in oxidizer starved environment during pyrolysis and overall gasification process.

Figure 7-6 presents the exergy loss during the thermochemical conversion with respect to SBR, for high and low injection temperatures of injection. High injection temperature corresponds to a temperature in the range from 550 °C to 750 °C while low injection temperatures correspond to a temperature range of 375 °C – 550 °C.

Figure 7-6 Exergy loss in thermochemical conversion

The plot presents on y-axis the percentage of exergy loss due to thermochemical conversion. On average, higher injection temperatures resulted in lower losses at about 17% of the total exergy input to the gasification system, in comparison

to lower injection temperatures which resulted in exergy loss due to thermochemical conversion at about 20% of the total exergy input in the process. At SBR of ~ 2.4 and ER of ~ 0.3 , the exergy losses during the thermochemical conversion was 22%, 17% and 11% when the injection temperature was 450 °C, 630 °C and 730 °C, respectively. On average, exergy loss during thermochemical conversion constituted about 42% of the total exergy loss during the process. However, thermochemical conversion process inside the gasification system, independently as an isolated process had an exergy efficiency of about 77%, on average.

7.2.2 Steam generation for oxy-steam mixture

The present case utilizes electrical boiler and heaters for generating and superheating the steam for oxy-steam mixture injection in the gasification system and electricity is a form of high-grade energy. Exergy lost during steam generation process has been calculated using electrical energy input as the exergy input while exergy of the steam as the output exergy. With increasing SBR, the losses increased monotonously as a result of higher steam generation rate. Plot also shows an expected comparative trend between the two ranges of injection temperatures. Higher injection temperature resulted in higher losses due to the requirement of higher degree of superheating.

Figure 7-7 Exergy loss in steam generation

Figure 7-7 presents the percentage of total exergy input to the gasification that is lost during steam generation process. It is observed that average loss stands at about 19% of the total exergy input, for both the ranges of injection temperature. Overall, exergy lost in steam generation contributed to about 43% of the total exergy loss. The average exergy efficiency of the steam generation process was about 27%.

7.2.3 Cleaning and cooling of hot gas

The cooling and cleaning unit of the gasification system utilizes pumps and a blower to pump cooling water and induce draft. In the process, hot gas mixture from the reactor loses sensible heat and moisture while being cleaned off dust and tar. Thermal losses and electrical energy input cause exergy losses. The losses have been plotted in Figure 7-8. It is evident that with increasing SBR, the exergy loss at cooling and cleaning unit has increased. This can be attributed to the higher flow rate of hot gases coming out of the reactor. As SBR increases, the amount steam input increases which further contributes to gas generation by gasification reactions with char or remains unconverted. Either way, the flow rate of hot gases increases and correspondingly, so does

the external irreversibility due to heat losses cooling water. It can also be seen that the injection temperature has no or little effect on exergy losses at the cooling and cleaning unit, similar observations pertain to the high and lower ranges of injection temperature.

Figure 7-8 Exergy loss in cooling and cleaning process

The maximum loss recorded was 10.3% of the total exergy input to the system. Average loss was $\sim 8\%$ and 7% for lower and higher injection temperatures, respectively. It should be noted that losses at cleaning and cooling unit were the least ($\sim 16\%$ of the total exergy loss) and were less than half of those while generating steam or at thermochemical conversion process in the reactor.

7.2.4 Exergy efficiency of the synthesis gas generation

Figure 7-9 presents the overall exergy efficiency of the process of dry syngas generation through oxy-steam gasification of biomass. The trend shows that the exergy efficiency decreases with increasing SBR. The decrease in efficiency can be explained by the fact that steam generation rate increased which causes significant losses, more than 40% of the total exergy losses. The average exergy efficiency at lower injection temperatures was close to 52% while that with higher injection temperatures was about little more than 58%. The exergy flow

is presented in Figure 7-10, averaged for lower and higher injection temperatures.

Figure 7-9 Overall exergy efficiency

(a)

(b)

Figure 7-10 Exergy flow - Input to output. (a) average of low injection temperature operations (b) average of high injection temperature operations.

Summary

This chapter started with equilibrium studies to present and compare equilibrium gasification results with the experimental results. The equilibrium results obtained using NASA CEA program by minimizing the Gibbs free energy of the system also showed that hydrogen concentration in product gas increases at slower rate as SBR increases. The lower temperature corresponds to higher hydrogen concentration, as dictated by thermodynamics. Later part of thesis presented an overall exergy flow for the entire gas generation system. The purpose of this analysis was to understand the processes where maximum exergy losses take place. It is evident that steam generation is the source of maximum losses during the process. It also is observed that thermochemical conversion process in itself is a process of significant exergy loss which is comparable to losses in steam generation unit; when looked at the overall process of gasification, both being about 40%. It was found that average exergy

efficiency of the thermochemical conversion process was about 77% while that of the steam generation process was about 27%.

Chapter 8 – Conclusion and future work

8.1 Conclusion

This thesis endeavours to pave the way for the thermochemical conversion of cellulosic biomass as a viable method for generating green hydrogen. The research demonstrates that biomass gasification utilizing an oxy-steam mixture as the gasifying agent can produce hydrogen-rich synthesis gas with a concentration of up to 56% by volume. The experimental investigation provides valuable insights into the behavior of the process and system. The key conclusions drawn from this thesis can be summarized as follows:

- The closed-top downdraft gasification system can accommodate various types of biomass with different physical properties as feedstocks. The study utilized three types of biomass - casuarina wood chips, coconut shells, and corncob - which exhibited different bulk densities but had similar calorific values.
- Maximum hydrogen yield, reaching about 110 g/kg of biomass, was achieved using casuarina wood chips as the feedstock.
- The operation of oxy-steam gasification was found to be stable at higher steam-to-biomass ratios (SBR), contrary to previous reports suggesting instability beyond an SBR of 1.5. The present work indicates that the carbon boundary point can shift with changes in operating conditions, such as an increase in the injection temperature of the gasifying agent.
- Increasing the injection temperature at a constant SBR was shown to enhance the hydrogen concentration in the product gas mixture.
- Higher injection temperatures, particularly above 700°C, resulted in increased hydrogen yields in the generated syngas.
- Different biomass chars exhibited varying behaviors towards water gas shift and steam-char reactions, depending on their sources.
- Small-scale experiments with the hot char bed demonstrated its catalytic behavior towards the water gas shift reaction, contributing to hydrogen enrichment in the product gas mixture during gasification.

- While an increase in SBR improves the hydrogen content in the product gas, the enhancement ceases at higher SBRs. Higher SBR promotes water gas shift and steam-char reactions, but the presence of hydrogen on the product side inhibits the progress of the water gas shift reaction.
- Merely increasing the SBR may not necessarily improve the hydrogen yield; lower SBRs combined with increased injection temperatures are more effective. Higher temperatures kinetically favor the water gas shift reaction.
- Exergy analysis revealed that steam generation accounts for a significant exergy loss during the gasification process, representing over 40% of the total loss.
- Based on the experimental findings, an optimal SBR for efficient operation is suggested to be around 2.5, while maintaining an equivalence ratio of 0.3 and an oxy-steam injection temperature of 700-750°C.

8.2 Contribution from the current work

The present work aimed to contribute towards green hydrogen generation from biomass by furthering the understanding of oxy-steam gasification process. The experimental investigation presented in this thesis intended to utilize steam and hot char bed for maximum possible CO conversion by water gas shift reaction to enhance hydrogen concentration for higher hydrogen yield per kg of biomass. The study also explored the effect of gasifying media temperature on hydrogen concentration and yield. The key contribution from this study is listed below:

- We have an understanding from experimental results that Carbon Boundary Point (CBP) is not a factor of SBR alone. Previous study (Kumar, 2016) has reported a CBP of 1.5, the present study establishes that the CBP can vary with change in the oxy-steam mixture injection temperature. This thesis reports stable operations beyond the previously established CBP by utilizing elevated injection temperatures of the gasifying media.
- This thesis reports that in an oxy-steam gasification system, the water gas shift reaction is favored with an increase in SBR due to higher H₂O/CO ratios prevailing in the gasification system.

- The results from this thesis show that hot char bed in the gasification system shows catalytic effect towards hydrogen generation by water gas shift reaction and steam – char reaction. This catalytic effect is observed due to presence of alkali and alkaline earth metals present in the feed (Potassium and Calcium) and due to porous structure of char providing larger surface area for the reactions to take place. This finding shows that in-situ catalysis due to char enhances hydrogen eliminating the need of external catalytic reactor to achieve higher CO conversion by water gas shift reaction for higher hydrogen yield.
- This study identifies that the temperature above 700 °C can be crucial for hydrogen enrichment in a gasification system. The rate of hydrogen generation increases significantly when temperature is above 700 °C due to onset of steam – char reaction which also contributes towards hydrogen generation along with water gas shift reaction.
- This work also shows that operations with higher injection temperatures of oxy-steam mixture favors higher hydrogen yield. Since, thermodynamics limits the rate of increase of hydrogen at higher SBRs (>3), higher injection temperature can result in higher yields at lower SBRs. This thesis recommends operating the oxy-steam gasification system at around 2.5 with injection temperature above 700 °C and equivalence ratio of about 0.3.

8.3 Future work

This investigation presents several avenues for further research to advance the understanding of the gasification process for hydrogen generation:

- **Modeling and Simulation:** Complementing the experimental work with modeling and simulation can facilitate scaling the investigation across a wider range of gasification parameters. This approach can provide insights into the complex interactions within the system and help optimize process conditions.
- **Carbon Boundary Point:** Further exploration is warranted to understand the carbon boundary point. Previous studies have established a boundary at an SBR of 1.5, but this investigation indicates that the boundary can vary depending on factors like ER and injection temperature. Experimental and

numerical studies could elucidate the combined effects of SBR, ER, and injection temperature on the carbon boundary point.

- **Catalytic Effect of Hot Char Bed:** Investigating the catalytic effect of the hot char bed on the water gas shift reaction warrants further exploration. Future studies could quantify the impact of the surface area and pore structure of activated biomass char on water gas shift and char reactions.
- **Life Cycle Analysis:** Including a life cycle analysis of hydrogen generation would provide valuable insights into the environmental and economic implications of the process. Assessing the cost of hydrogen generation from oxy-steam gasification would complement the study from a commercial perspective.
- **Comparison with Air-Steam Gasification:** Conducting further studies with air-steam as the gasifying agent in downdraft gasification systems could provide a comparative analysis of hydrogen generation economics between oxy-steam and air-steam gasification.
- **Optimization of Oxy-Steam Gasification System:** Continuously refining the oxy-steam gasification system for hydrogen generation would enhance its efficiency and effectiveness. Exploring improvements in reactor design, operation parameters, and feedstock characteristics could contribute to the advancement of the technology.

Summary

This chapter concludes by summarizing the key findings and contribution from the study and proposing topics for future research that can be undertaken to deepen the understanding of hydrogen generation through gasification processes.

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